

Complexities in Water Governance: An assessment of the role of stakeholders in water governance at the River basin level

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ABSTRACT

Water is a vital resource crucial for global socio-economic development, but the 21st century presents unprecedented challenges to its governance. Ghana, situated in West Africa, grapples with balancing economic progress and preserving water resources, particularly in the Densu and Pra River Basins. These basins, essential for water supply, irrigation, and biodiversity, face threats from urbanisation, industrialisation, and climate change. While existing literature often characterises water crisis as biophysical, this study recognises the importance of considering socio-economic, political, and governance factors and presents policy recommendations to accommodate these.

The thesis explores stakeholders, decision-making processes, and participation in water governance at the river basin level, employing a qualitative approach within an interpretive perspective. The research, conducted in the Densu and Pra Basins, uses a cross-case study approach incorporating focus group discussions, interviews, document analysis, and observation to ensure a comprehensive, in-depth understanding of water resource management complexities. The study identifies a participatory decision-making process aligned with the Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) approach, emphasising stakeholder consultation and collective decisions during basin board meetings.

Decision-making occurs at the national and regional levels, with water management experts leading the discussions. While the technocratic governance processes led by the basin board may be deemed acceptable, they are insufficient. The basin boards, tailored to each basin's challenges, are composed of state institutions, NGOs, traditional authorities, and local government representatives. Their effectiveness is contingent on the availability of resources. These boards face various challenges, including limited financial, logistical, and personnel resources. Other barriers to effective water resources management include policy implementation gaps, weak law enforcement, low levels of awareness about water resources management, negative attitudes toward conservation efforts, and political and institutional factors, such as conflicting interests and the influence of powerful actors.

Opportunities lie in the holistic planning approach adopted by the WRC, collaborative support from government institutions, NGOs, and corporate bodies, awareness of climate change and pollution among the public, support from donor agencies and research institutions, availability of regulations, government policies and media advocacy, the introduction of anti-galamsey taskforces, availability of assessments, availability of basin IWRM plans and the concept of Local Water Committee (LWC), proliferation of drinking water-producing enterprises, and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Contributions to help address the challenges.

The study recommends greater inclusion of local communities, the private sector, and diverse interest groups for more wide-ranging regional decision-making. Transformative actions, such as the alignment of economic development with environmental conservation, implementing the 'polluter pays' principle, harnessing the local government system and cultural transformation through education, are identified as strategies for resilience. Introducing incentives for ecosystem services and leveraging the influence of religious organisations can further support conservation efforts. By implementing these strategies, Ghana can achieve a more sustainable and efficient management of the Densu and Pra basins' water resources, safeguarding the environmental and socio-economic well-being of the basins. The study provides a framework that can guide decision-makers on how to enhance the participation of all stakeholders and the public to ensure improved commitment and contribution to water resources management.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this work to my parents, sisters, husband, and children (Jason and Anne-Joanita) who have been the pillars in my life.

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List of Abbreviations

AHK Ghana	Delegation of German Industry and Commerce in Ghana
ANE	Asia and the Near East
ARCC	Ashanti Regional Co-ordinating Council
CILSS	Permanent Interstate Committee for Drought Control in the Sahel
CMA	Chemical Manufacturers Association
CONIWAS	Coalition of Non-governmental Organisations (NGOs) in Water and Sanitation
CREAM	Building Climate-Resilience into Basin Water Management
CSOs	Civil Society Organisations
CWSA	Community Water and Sanitation Agency
CWSP	Community Water and Sanitation Programme
DA	District Assembly
DANIDA	Danish International Development Agency
DDT	Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane
ECOWAS	Economic Community of West African States
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ERCC	Eastern Regional Coordinating Council
EU	European Union
FASDEP	Food and Agriculture Sector Development Policy
GAPVOD	Ghana Association of Private Voluntary Organisations in Development
GHS	Ghana Health Service
GIADA	Ghana Integrated Aluminum Development Authority
GIDA	Ghana Irrigation Development Authority
GPRS	Growth and Poverty Reduction Strategy
GWCL	Ghana Water Company Limited
ICT	Information and Communication Technology

ICWE	International Conference on Water and the Environment
IESWTR	Interim Enhanced Surface Water Treatment Rule
IGF	Internally Generated Fund
INGOs	International Governmental Organisations
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IWRM	Integrated Water Resources Management
KMA	Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly
LI	Legislative Instrument
LUSPA	Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority
LWC	Local Water Committee
MBIs	Market-based instruments
MDAs	Ministries, Departments, and Agencies
MDGs	Millennium Development Goals
MMDAs	Metropolitan, Municipal, and District Assemblies
MWRWH	Ministry of Water Resources, Works and Housing
NCWSP	National Community Water and Sanitation Programme
NEPAD	New Partnership for Africa's Development
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
NWMP	National Water Master Plan
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PES	Payment for Ecosystem Services
RBB	River Basin Board
REGSEC	Regional Security Council
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SIDA	Swedish International Development Agency
SWTR	Surface Water Treatment Rule
UEMOA	West African Economic and Monetary Union

UK	United Kingdom
UNCED	United Nations Conference on Environment and Development
US	United States
WAP	Watershed Agricultural Program
WARM	Water Resources Management Study
WASH	Water, Sanitation and Hygiene
WAWRP	West Africa Water Resources Policy
WFP	Whole Farm Plan
WRC	Water Resources Commission
WRIS	Water Resources Information Services
WRM	Water Resources Management
WRMA	Water Resources Management Authority

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction to the research

Water is an indispensable element for human survival, second only to air (Lozán et al., 2007). It is vital for the human body to function optimally, playing crucial roles in the proper functioning of body organs and for various physiological processes (Kılıç, 2020). Water also plays an important role as a domestic commodity in the development of nations used for domestic purposes such as drinking, cooking, personal and domestic hygiene. At the household level where water is a domestic commodity, access to clean water can improve health by improving personal hygiene. A report by the World Bank reveals that globally, water, sanitation and hygiene interventions can prevent almost 10 percent of the global burden of disease and 6.3 percent of all deaths (Prüss-Üstün et al., 2008).

The environment and nature cannot function without water as it is a fundamental element of the environment, sustaining life and supporting the functioning of ecosystems. In terms of the environment, water is an input to many natural productive processes. It forms part of the ecosystem that provides a range of products and services beneficial to human welfare, such as fish, wildlife, and natural plants. It is also a fact that virtually all sectors of the economy, from agriculture, manufacturing, transportation, construction, and energy to hotels and restaurants, rely on water (Value for Water Campaign, 2017). The World Bank's report on water shows that agriculture is the largest global user of water with irrigated agriculture accounting for about 70 percent of all freshwater withdrawals. Energy in the form of electricity, which is also an important input for most economic activities accounts for 15 percent of global water withdrawals (The World Bank, 2014). In both rural and urban areas, agriculture and other economic activities thrive because of access to adequate domestic water supply for the workers involved. These examples show that water is not only vital for humans and the environment, but it also plays a key role in the progress of every nation. The benefits of water also include intangible contributions to welfare. These intangible contributions may take the form of satisfaction of spiritual needs, as in the case of religiously significant waters, or through the provision of amenity values that add to psychological welfare (Hossain, 2015; Cox, 1987).

Water has always been essential to human civilization, influencing settlement patterns and survival. Historically, communities have thrived in areas with abundant and safe water sources . In the 21st century, however, the increasing global population, heightened water usage, and

the impacts of climate change have intensified concerns about water availability and quality. Rising temperatures have led to more frequent droughts, floods, and wildfires, disrupting access to clean water worldwide. These challenges underscore the critical importance of effective water governance. Ensuring sustainable management and protection of water resources now requires collaborative efforts from governments, businesses, and individuals to benefit both current and future generations

In Ghana, water governance is shaped by a combination of national policies, regulations, regulatory agencies, and customary practices (Yeleele et al., 2018; Agyenim & Gupta 2013). The Water Resources Commission (WRC) serves as the primary regulatory body, managing water resources through instruments like the National Water Policy and the Riparian Buffer Zone Policy. These policies emphasise equitable access, environmental sustainability, and stakeholder participation. Ghana has adopted Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) as a central strategy, aiming for holistic and sustainable water resource management. To implement IWRM at the local level, the WRC has established river basin boards and developed regulations such as the Water Use Regulations, 2001 (L.I. 1692), the Drilling Licence and Groundwater Development Regulations, 2006 (L.I.1827), and the Dam Safety Regulation, 2016 (L.I.2236). These regulations collectively define water use rights, oversee sustainable groundwater development, and ensure the safe design, construction, operation, maintenance, and decommissioning of dams across the country. Despite this robust institutional and legal framework, scholars (Mosello et al, 2017; Agyenim & Gupta, 2012) argue that challenges persist in effectively managing and protecting Ghana's water resources

As a country located in West Africa with a rich cultural heritage, Ghana is currently navigating the complexities of a rapidly evolving economy. Water bodies are crucial for domestic, irrigation, industrial, and habitat purposes and remain vital for human and aquatic survival. However, in Ghana, the abuse of water resources for these benefits is alarming. Water pollution has become a significant environmental challenge, particularly over the past few decades. The Business and Human Rights Resource Centre (2017) reports a concerning statistic that **60** percent of water bodies in Ghana are polluted. Farming and mining encroach on riverbanks, chemicals are used in fishing, and waste is indiscriminately discharged into rivers. The pollution of water bodies in Ghana has wide-ranging consequences. As reported by Yeboah (2023), water pollution in Ghana threatens public health, agriculture, and biodiversity, impacting food security and economic productivity

With a population of over 30 million and a primary sector-based economy, Ghana is heavily reliant on agriculture and natural resources, making the management and conservation of its water resources crucial for the country's progress. Within this context, the Densu and Pra River Basins emerge as pivotal players in the country's hydrological landscape, functioning as lifelines that weave through the socio-economic fabric of both urban and rural communities. The Densu and Pra River Basins are critical for the country's water supply and irrigation needs. These river basins also support a diverse range of ecosystems and wildlife, and as such, their preservation is vital for the country's sustainable development. However, the health and sustainability of these river basins have come under attack due to growing mining activities (both legal and illegal). Aside weak enforcement of regulations, the politics around the collective ownership and management of rivers and water bodies have been cited as a major cause of the challenges in managing river basins in Ghana (Mosello, et al., 2017; Laube, 2009; Agyenim & Gupta, 2013). As Ghana strives for economic growth, balancing development with sustainable water management and addressing the challenges of managing river basins is crucial.

1.2 Problem Statement

Globally, the population is growing fast and putting pressure on water resources. According to the World Bank, if current practices are not changed, the world will face a 40 percent shortfall between demand and available supply of water by 2030 (Guppy & Anderson, 2017). Apart from satisfying the customary needs of the community in terms of providing domestic water, economic activities also need fresh water. The result is that there is now a growing competing demand for water from many different interests and stakeholders. Evidence shows that lifestyles and climate change contribute to the growing pressure on water supply (Pereira et al., 2002; Guppy & Anderson, 2017). UN-Water indicates that the wasteful use of water and water pollution from sources such as domestic, industrial, mining or agricultural also compromise the benefits derived from water resources. Soon, it has been predicted that two-thirds of the world's population could be living in water-stressed countries if current consumption patterns continue (FAO, 2019). This shows the urgency with which countries around the world should be working towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goal on water, which supports the attainment of other SDGs e.g. on poverty (SDG 1), health (SDG3), responsible consumption and production (SDG 12), hunger (SDG 2), climate change (SDG 13), sustainable industrialisation (SDG 9).

Recent global water policy reports indicate that the current water crisis is linked to governance rather than just a scarcity and stress crisis. (UNDP, 2024; OECD, 2011; World Water Council, 2002). Nayar (2013) proposes that attributing water stress or scarcity to natural factors or population growth might be tempting, but the root of the issue actually lies in how water has been managed. The World Water Council (2002) believes that good water governance will catalyse the much-needed investments to expand water services, conserve water resources, and protect the environment. These views in academic literature have made researchers in recent times aware of the need to evaluate the water crisis not only considering environmental factors such as climate change and changes in land-use/-cover (LULC) but also the socio-economic, political and governance arrangements affecting the sustainable management of water resources. However, this awareness has apparently not been translated into studies on water resources management, especially in Ghana. Existing studies in Ghana have focused either on the impacts of climate change (such as (McCartney et al. 2012; Obuobie et al., 2012; Amisigo et al., 2015) or impacts of land use changes on basin water resources (see Boakye et al., 2019; Aduah et al., 2021; Ayivor & Gordon, 2012; Yorke & Margai, 2007). These studies usually characterise the water crisis in Ghana as a biophysical phenomenon that can be solved using technical approaches. These and other similar studies on water resources management do not pay sufficient attention to the political, social and economic realities around water resources management. What this suggests is that current literature does not provide sufficient insight into effective water governance. The grounds on which political, social, and economic issues shape water resources availability and quality and how these factors need to be governed are also not well understood. While managing water resources requires knowledge of the physical sciences and technology, it is equally important to know the institutional, social and political issues confronting water resources actors (Loucks & van Beek, 2017).

International and regional treaties as well as many non-binding documents like the Berlin rules on water resources, Agenda 21 (from the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development in Rio de Janeiro) and the African Water Vision 2025 all encourage the involvement of stakeholders especially affected persons in managing water resources (International Law Association, 2004; Smith & Clausen, 2015; UNECA, AUC & AfDB, 2003). This affirms a break from the approach in which stakeholder needs are taken care of by experts to an approach where stakeholders are at least consulted in a structured way so that they can influence decision-making. Iza and Stein (2009) argue that stakeholder participation can raise awareness, and introduce co-management and citizen initiatives, all of which are necessary for

fostering the capacity for efficient water governance and resilience. Bijlsma et al. (2011) also suggest that involving stakeholders in developing any environmental policy has benefits for the quality of policy, policy legitimacy and implementation, and the development of social capital for the parties involved. Furthermore, stakeholder involvement may lead to social equity and cohesion related to trust, capacity, and knowledge development (Akhmouch & Clavreul, 2016). For water policies and plans to work, there is a need for cooperation among stakeholders. In a complex African setting, an understanding of context, particularly the political, social, and economic incentives facing local stakeholders, can serve as a springboard for effective stakeholder participation (The World Bank, 2017).

Another role of stakeholders is highlighted by Howlett (2014), who indicates that many policy decisions are either irrational or made as a result of pure negotiation and trade-offs among stakeholders. This indicates the influence stakeholders have in the decision-making process in water resources management. It also points to the participatory approach to water management which has been adopted by many developed and developing nations including Ghana. Ghana has adopted participation as part of its development efforts in all sectors including the water sector. The Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) approach which has been espoused by the Water Resources Commission as the way to manage the country's water resources promotes among other things greater participation of stakeholders in water management and decision-making processes. The IWRM approach involves applying knowledge from different stakeholders to plan and implement efficient, equitable and sustainable solutions to water problems.

Though the participatory approach to making water management decisions is crucial, failure to understand and acknowledge the environment within which stakeholders operate can lead to the adoption of simplistic methods for participation which will not meet the required technical, social and political conditions to effectively influence water governance (Laube, 2009). In essence, an understanding of the socio-political dynamics, cultural contexts, power structures, and historical backgrounds of stakeholders is essential. This knowledge is instrumental in designing and implementing participatory mechanisms that genuinely empower stakeholders, promote inclusive decision-making processes, and ensure that diverse perspectives and interests are adequately considered.

Some researchers have looked at stakeholder participation from various angles in water resources management in Ghana. These studies have either focused on the context within

which stakeholders make decisions on water infrastructure investments (Mosello et al., 2017); or the key formal stakeholders and how they carry out their duties in water resources management (Owusu et al., 2016), or even particular stakeholders such as Water User Associations, and their roles and responsibilities as far as the management of water is concerned (GWP/WA, 2009). Also, the importance of stakeholder participation and how it influences water resources management at the basin level in Ghana has been studied (Anokye, 2020). While these scholarly works provide insight into stakeholder participation in the decision-making and implementation processes of water resources management activities, they do not provide information on all relevant actors, their interests, and the full extent of stakeholder participation.

According to Laube (2009) and Agyenim (2012), little interest has been shown in stakeholder participation in the water sector in Ghana. Laube (2009) argues that one key challenge facing the Water Resources Commission in carrying out its mandate to manage the country's water resources involves managing powerful stakeholders with vested interests. This assertion by Laube begs the question, *what is the full picture of Ghana's political economy situation regarding water resources management?* The underlying logic behind seemingly dysfunctional governance arrangements for water resources management at the basin level will be revealed by exploring the political economy realities. This will provide the basis for thinking about how to work with, around, or gradually reshape existing systems to achieve the water policy goal. [JF1]

The water governance system in Ghana seems to be shaped by a complex interplay of ecological, social, economic, and political factors within its basins. These basins are home to diverse ecosystems which support a wide variety of flora and fauna. The balance of these ecosystems is crucial for maintaining biodiversity and ecological resilience. The rivers are deeply ingrained into the cultural and communal identities of the people, serving as sources of life, livelihoods, and cultural practices. The economic importance of these basins is undeniable, as they support crucial sectors such as agriculture, mining, and industry. Moreover, the political landscape in Ghana plays a significant role in formulating and implementing policies related to water resource management.

Water governance in Ghana is a complex landscape involving various stakeholders, including government agencies, traditional authorities, non-governmental organizations, local communities, and private sector actors. Each group brings unique interests, responsibilities,

and influences to the management of water resources. Collaboration among these stakeholders is imperative to achieve sustainable water management, as outlined in national policies like the National Water Policy and the Riparian Buffer Zone Policy.

Effective regulation of water use and protection of water bodies hinges on their ability to work together. Recognizing the roles and challenges each stakeholder faces is crucial for enhancing policy effectiveness. Moreover, understanding the dynamics of their interactions and how they shape decision-making processes is essential for fostering sustainable and equitable water governance in Ghana. By aligning their efforts, these diverse stakeholders can create a more resilient and effective water management framework that benefits all communities.

This thesis aims to examine the different stakeholders involved in water governance at the river basin level, their interests, the decision-making processes and the extent of their participation in decision-making and implementation of water resources management activities. The study provides an enhanced analysis of the social, political and economic context within which water resources management decisions in Ghana are made with a specific focus on the Densu and Pra basins.

1.3 Research Questions

Bottom-up approaches to policy design and implementation have been promoted widely to encourage citizens' participation in the decision-making process and enhance governance to achieve collective goals. The traditional top-down approach to policy decision-making has been criticised on the point that it assumes that those who formulate and decide on policies are the key actors, which, however, neglects strategic initiatives coming from other actors such as actors in the private sector, street-level bureaucrats or local implementing officials, or citizens. Bottom-up approaches start with an analysis of the multitude of stakeholders who interact at the operational level on a particular problem or issue (Sabatier, 1986).

Given the global recognition of bottom-up processes and the acknowledged key role of stakeholders in decision-making and implementation, the actual substance of decisions made by stakeholders over water resources management remains to be studied further. Indeed, most studies conducted on water resources in Ghana have not answered key questions such as how the relevant stakeholders (both formal and informal) are involved in the process of decision-making, what motivates them to participate in the decision-making process, how they make

decisions, and why they make the decisions they do. Responding to these questions can serve as the basis for evidence-based advice on water policy options.

In this light, this research explores the question: How do stakeholders engage in decision-making and governance in the Densu and Pra River Basins in Ghana, what constraints affect this process, and what strategies can enhance water governance at the basin level?

To answer this question four interrelated questions have been answered.

The first question is: *How are decisions made in the Densu and Pra River basins? Who are the key stakeholders (both formal and informal) involved in decision-making, what are their roles, and their interests in river basin management?*

The second question is: *How do stakeholder dynamics affect water resources management in the Densu and Pra River basins?* Understanding stakeholder dynamics is essential for grasping the complexities of water governance, as it reveals the power relations, levels of engagement, commitment, and participation among stakeholders - key metrics for evaluating governance efficacy. By examining these dynamics, the thesis highlights the effectiveness of current governance frameworks and identifies potential shortcomings that may hinder participation.

The third question asks: *what are the key barriers and opportunities to effective management of water resources in the Densu and Pra River basins?* This is important because Ghana aims to meet the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) for water, ensuring its availability and sustainable management for all. The study of the Densu and Pra River Basins will identify current obstacles to the effective implementation of Ghana's water policy and uncover opportunities for improvement. These insights will help inform policy recommendations to enhance resilience and support the achievement of the SDG on water.

The fourth and final question is: *How can stakeholder participation in water resources management at the basin level be improved?* This involves engaging a diverse range of stakeholders in river basin management. Consequently, this question aims to extract insights from the Densu and Pra Basins case studies to develop a framework that promotes greater stakeholder participation in water resources management at the basin level in Ghana. The specific objectives of this thesis are:

- To analyse the decision-making process, the key stakeholders engaged in decision-making within the Densu and Pra river basins and examine their respective interests in river basin management;
- To examine stakeholder dynamics (power relations, level of engagement, commitment and participation) in the management of the Densu and Pra River basins;
- To analyse the barriers and opportunities available to stakeholders for effective water resources management in the Densu and Pra River basins; and
- To propose a framework for improved stakeholder participation in water resources management at the basin level.

1.4 Significance of study

This study plays a crucial role in addressing key challenges in water governance and Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM), with a focus on stakeholder participation in decision-making processes. By analysing how diverse actors engage in water management at the river basin level, it sheds light on the complexities of collaboration between government agencies, local communities, private sector, and non-governmental organisations. The study offers valuable insights into the gaps in stakeholder engagement, highlighting the need for enhanced participation in sustainable water resource management. It contributes to refining decision-making processes, particularly in the Densu and Pra River basins, and explores strategies for overcoming challenges to foster resilience in water governance. Furthermore, the study aligns with Ghana's commitment to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 6, by providing recommendations that support sustainable water resource management and stakeholder collaboration across the river basins.

1.4.1 Enhancing stakeholder engagement for effective water resource management

Managing water resources requires commitment and synergies. The literature (Salamanca-Cano & Durán-Díaz, 2023; Akhmouch & Clavreul, 2016; Hermans, 2006) suggests that decision-making over water resources can be improved by consulting with stakeholders. When stakeholders at different levels of action can voice their opinions, share their knowledge, and be involved in concrete decision-making, then decisions can achieve results. The water sector, however, involves a plethora of stakeholders at basin and national levels. As policymakers seek to engage stakeholders, identifying whom to engage can be daunting and serve as a disincentive for stakeholder engagement. To encourage stakeholder involvement and make it easy for water managers and policymakers, this study, based on empirical evidence, provides information on

the stakeholders who are engaged, their interests, the relevant stakeholders who are not engaged in the decision-making process and assesses the gaps in stakeholder engagement. The study offers recommendations for fostering collaboration and ensuring that all relevant parties are actively involved in decision-making by providing a detailed stakeholder analysis. Particularly, the results of this study include a framework which, when adopted, can help to enhance decision-making and improve stakeholder participation in water resources management at the basin level.

1.4.2 Contribution to enhancing water governance in Ghana's River basins

In Ghana, management decisions significantly impact water availability (Sustainable Water Partnership, 2021), indicating that the water crisis is closely tied to governance and resource management practices. Stakeholders are essential in management decisions regarding water resource conservation, protection, utilisation, and development. Given the vital role of basin water resources in supplying water for agriculture, domestic, and industrial use, it is crucial to explore the constraints stakeholders face in promoting effective water governance. Developing strategies to overcome these constraints and enhance resilience in water resources management becomes imperative for sustainable management and resource utilisation. This study makes a significant contribution to understanding the governance processes, particularly decision-making processes in managing river basins. It assesses the decision-making processes of the Densu and Pra River basins to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the process and make way for the refinement of future decision-making approaches. This is to ensure that decision-making in the Densu and Pra River basins remains responsive to the basin challenges.

1.4.3 Supporting sustainable water resource management in Ghana's River basins

Sustainable water resource management requires due consideration and planning of river basins (Smith & Clausen, 2018). This is because managing water resources at the basin level encourages integrated and coordinated management among various stakeholders, acknowledging the interconnectedness between different water sources and the multiple administrative boundaries they span.

In Ghana, river basins such as the Densu and Pra exhibit clear trends of development and natural resource degradation due to anthropogenic pressures. Human activities such as mining and improper waste disposal have significantly impacted these basins' quality and quantity of water resources. The increasing population and economic activities within these basins have

further exacerbated the strain on water resources. Climate change also poses a significant threat to water resources in Ghana. Variations in rainfall patterns and extreme weather events contribute to water scarcity and reduced water quality. To address these challenges, it is essential to adopt a holistic approach to water resource management that considers the entire river basin. This study of river basins is important because it promotes the integration of different water uses and the coordination of actions among various stakeholders, including government agencies, local communities, private sector entities, and non-governmental organisations. By promoting collaboration and shared responsibility, it becomes possible to develop and implement sustainable management practices that can protect and preserve water resources for future generations.

1.4.4 Addressing key challenges by leveraging the opportunities in water management

To effectively manage and utilise water resources in the Densu and Pra River basins, it is essential to understand the key management challenges. This research identifies a range of issues that impact water resources management in these basins. Addressing these challenges requires developing an effective strategy that leverages available opportunities for stakeholders. This approach aims to illuminate the water governance environment and utilise its conditions to minimise the impact of complexities. As part of its objectives, this research examines critical challenges and available opportunities, offering recommendations based on these findings. By analysing the challenges stakeholders face in water resources management, this study provides valuable insights that contribute to the development of effective strategies for sustainable water management in the Densu and Pra River Basins. This thesis serves as a catalyst for informed decision-making, fostering a good understanding of the challenges and opportunities in water governance within these basins.

1.4.5 A springboard for integrating political, social, and economic realities in water governance

As water is crucial for life and wealth, like no other resource, no weather forecasts or revolutionary ways in water catchment can guarantee efficient water management as long as there are compromises to the established water governance system. Whether the legal or institutional system is in place, if social, behavioural, and political realities are not taken into consideration, water scarcity or quality problems will occur. The World Bank (2017) argues that in a complex African setting, an understanding of context, particularly the political, social and economic incentives facing local stakeholders, can serve as a springboard for effective

stakeholder participation, which will eventually positively impact water resources management. As such, this study emphasises on the practical aspects of the complexities in water governance from the point of view of stakeholders to leverage greater recognition and inclusion of political, social and economic dynamics in water resources management. The study's findings serve as a starting point for understanding the political and social intricacies involved in decision-making at the basin level. The findings from this study are likely to inform future policy reforms in the water sector.

1.4.6 Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals

Finally, Ghana continues to show commitment to attaining the SDGs. This research aligns with several SDGs, emphasising its potential to contribute significantly to the global agenda for sustainable development. The analysis of water resources management directly relates to SDG 6, which aims to ensure the availability and sustainable management of water for all. By examining the complexities in the Densu and Pra River basins, the study recommends many strategies for improving water resources management in the two basins. The study particularly provides measures to improve water quality and availability, thereby contributing to the achievement of SDG 6. Analysing the water resources management in these basins can also contribute to sustainable agricultural practices (SDG 2) and economic growth (SDG 8) by ensuring the availability of water for irrigation, as well as industrial processes. The recommendations from the study can foster collaborations and partnerships among government agencies, communities, water users and other stakeholders. This aligns with SDG 17, which emphasises the importance of multi-stakeholder partnerships for achieving sustainable development. This study provides meaningful perspectives that can inform policies, practices, and collaborations essential for achieving multiple SDGs related to water.

1.5 The structure of the thesis

The thesis starts with an introductory chapter that emphasizes the vital role of water in human survival and national development. It examines existing literature on water resource management in Ghana and identifies a significant limitation: most research has focused on biophysical aspects, such as climate change and land use impacts, rather than providing a comprehensive understanding of stakeholder engagement in decision-making and participation in water governance. This limited insight into Ghana's water governance dynamics has been recognized as a barrier to effective resource management, highlighting the need to examine institutional, political, economic, and social contexts.

The thesis is organised into nine chapters. Following the introduction, the theoretical framework is presented to elucidate water governance and Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM), emphasising the importance of stakeholder participation. A comparative analysis of water governance in Ghana, Kenya, and Uganda is also conducted to draw insights from their experiences in implementing IWRM. The research methodology is thoroughly outlined, justifying the selection of the Densu and Pra River basins, as well as the data collection techniques and analysis method employed. Subsequent chapters present empirical findings, exploring decision-making processes, stakeholder dynamics, and barriers and opportunities for effective water management, ultimately leading to a discussion of research findings and their implications. The final chapter summarises key findings and proposes a framework to enhance stakeholder participation in water governance, alongside recommendations for further research to improve understanding and practice in this field

CHAPTER TWO

CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Introduction

Effective water governance is essential in addressing the global water crisis. Many governments around the world are embracing an integrated approach to ensure water security. The conventional top-down decision-making process in water governance has faced criticism for neglecting the input of local communities and failing to consider the diverse water interests of stakeholders. The Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) approach has been introduced, emphasising participatory water governance. Central to this approach is the development of water policies that establish common rules for stakeholder decision-making to manage water resources sustainably. This literature review delves into water governance, policy formulation, and IWRM while exploring participation and stakeholder theories, which are crucial frameworks for decision-making processes in policies, plans, and programmes. Additionally, the discussion extends to water governance in Africa and West Africa.

To explore the issues, I first look at the subject of water governance and IWRM and its implications for water resources in developing nations. I also discuss policymaking as a decision-making process in the public sector. The discussion encompasses various aspects, such as the context of policymaking, policy formulation, policy instruments and policy implementation. This chapter explores the advantages and disadvantages of different policy instruments and their effectiveness. One significant part of policymaking that is also discussed is implementation. A policy may not be known publicly and will not have effect until it is implemented. Often, this policy implementation process does not run smoothly (Pressman & Wildawsky, 1984). Many factors constrain implementation, and these are discussed under barriers to implementation.

2.2 The concept of water governance

The phrase 'Environmental governance' covers a wide range of regulations, procedures, and organisations used in overseeing the environment. This encompasses both official and unofficial methods and institutions used by individuals, groups, advocacy movements, legislatures, and local governments (see Haque, 2017). Water governance, a subset of this, includes the political, institutional, and administrative rules, practices, and processes that guide decision-making and implementation. It also provides a platform for stakeholders to express their interests and concerns, ensuring that decision-makers are held accountable for water

management (OECD, 2015). Essentially, water governance focuses on how decisions regarding water resource management and development are made and carried out.

Saleth and Dinar (2005) outlined the fundamental elements of water governance as being water law, policy, and organisation. They argue that water governance supplies the essential administrative, economic, and legal structure for comprehensive water resource management. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development formulated 12 governance principles in 2015 to assist in the development and execution of water policies and strategies. These principles are based on the fundamental principles of good governance, which include legitimacy, transparency, accountability, human rights, the rule of law and inclusiveness (OECD, 2015). These principles are expected to help solve key water challenges of ‘too much’, ‘too little’, and ‘too polluted’ water resources (see Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: OECD Water Governance Principles

Principle 1	Clearly assign and differentiate roles and duties for water policy development, implementation, and regulation, and encourage coordination among relevant authorities.
Principle 2	Ensure that water management considers local conditions and involves coordination between different levels of governance within the basin.
Principle 3	Encourage policy coherence through effective cross-sectoral coordination between water, environment, health, energy, agriculture, industry, spatial planning, and land use.
Principle 4	Adapt the capacity of authorities to meet water challenges and carry out their duties effectively.
Principle 5	Produce, update, and share timely, consistent, comparable water data to guide water policy.
Principle 6	Ensure that governance structures enable the mobilization of water financing and the effective allocation of financial resources in an open and prompt manner.
Principle 7	Ensure that sound water management regulatory frameworks are effectively implemented and enforced in pursuit of the public interest
Principle 8	Promote the adoption and implementation of innovative water governance practices across responsible authorities, levels of government and relevant stakeholders
Principle 9	Mainstream integrity and transparency practices across water policies, water institutions and water governance frameworks for greater accountability and trust in decision-making
Principle 10	Promote stakeholder engagement for informed and outcome-oriented contributions to water policy design and implementation
Principle 11	Encourage water governance frameworks that help manage trade-offs across water users, rural and urban areas, and generations
Principle 12	Promote regular monitoring and evaluation of water policy and governance where appropriate, share the results with the public and make adjustments when needed

Source: OECD, 2015

2.3 Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM)

The quantity and quality of water depend on a variety of natural and human factors (Meybeck et al., 2006). The escalating pressure on global water resources due to climate change is of great concern. This has a significant impact on water availability and quality, causing worry for water resource managers and decision-makers. In 2009, climate change was the central focus of the 5th World Water Forum in Istanbul, with more than 25,000 participants, including ministers of state, undersecretaries, parliamentarians, and mayors. The forum emphasised the critical importance of adopting effective water management practices to reduce vulnerability to climate change and to ensure sufficient water availability and quality. National water security stands as a fundamental objective of water resources management, which is essential for social and

economic development. Rather than the traditional fragmented sectoral approach to water management, many global decision-makers have opted for the Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) approach (Hassing et al., 2009) as an alternative. According to the Global Water Partnership, IWRM is:

A “process which promotes the coordinated development and management of water, land and related resources, to maximise the resultant economic and social welfare equitably without compromising the sustainability of vital ecosystems” (GWP, 2000, p. 22)

Since its formal adoption, progress in IWRM is evaluated based on four key elements (Smith & Clausen, 2018):

1. **A supportive environment:** Policies, laws, and plans that set the guidelines for water management using IWRM principles.
2. **A clear, robust, and comprehensive institutional framework:** An effective system for managing water should use the basin as the central unit and involve decentralising decision-making.
3. **Effective use of available management and technical instruments:** Using evaluations, data, and tools for water management and pollution control to help decision-makers make well-informed choices.
4. **Sound investments in water infrastructure with adequate financing:** Ensuring we meet water demand and deal with floods, droughts, irrigation, energy, and nature.

IWRM provides a framework for managing conflicting water uses, involving the public and specialised basin entities to ensure coordination and technical proficiency (Smith & Clausen, 2015). IWRM is characterised by four key trends:

1. Shifting away from regulatory tools that concentrate on managing water supply, like extensive water infrastructure, to integrating the management of water demand through economic tools.
2. Raising consciousness about the significance of sustainable development and incorporating social and environmental factors into water management.
3. Shifting from centralised, top-down strategies to decentralised, adaptable methods to guarantee water security.

4. Emphasising stakeholder collaboration and involving local communities in decision-making (White, 2013).

Cap-Net (2019) argues that the impacts of climate change on the environment are primarily felt through water, and IWRM is crucial for global adaptation to climate change and for the reduction of its effects. Efficient management and utilisation of water resources can aid societies in decreasing or preventing some of the negative consequences of climate change. According to Sadoff & Muller (2009), two main characteristics of IWRM make it a successful approach to tackling climate change challenges. First, it integrates the activities of various sectors that utilise, affect, or are impacted by water, ensuring that actions in one sector do not undermine those in another. Second, it recognises the necessity for effective institutions to manage the trade-offs between different environmental activities and interests. IWRM offers tools to ensure access to water and preserve ecosystem integrity, thereby safeguarding water quality for future generations. By applying IWRM principles, water policies are developed to establish institutions, gather information, and build the capacity to predict, plan for, and cope with climate variability as a strategy to adapt to long-term climate change (Sadoff & Muller, 2009). IWRM facilitates adaptive responses to changes in water availability and pollution. Utilising a bottom-up participatory approach, it identifies and mitigates risks during basin planning. Through awareness campaigns, education, and training, water users are encouraged to adopt sustainable practices amidst climate-induced water fluctuations (Cap-Net & UNDP, 2019). This section shows how IWRM is effective, especially in dealing with climate change. The next section talks about using a worldwide approach to managing water resources, explaining how many countries are adopting IWRM and what this means for water resources in developing countries.

2.3.1 Implications of IWRM on water resources in developing nations

Integrated water management emphasises that water resources should be managed as essential to a nation's social and economic development. As a result, significant attention has been directed towards water policy and national planning to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Governments of developing countries must formulate and update national water policies based on IWRM principles. These policies serve as frameworks for legislation, strategic planning, and operational management of water resources (African Development Bank, 2000). They define the regulations, objectives, and tools governments will use to manage human water use, control water pollution, and fulfil environmental water requirements (CEO

Water Mandate, 2013). According to Smith and Clausen (2018), water policies are generally well-equipped to integrate efforts across different SDGs, fostering synergies and managing trade-offs effectively.

Water is an important sector, but it is generally seen as a challenging area for securing funding, particularly in developing nations. This is because borrowing institutions have poor creditworthiness, tariffs and cost recovery levels are low, there is political interference with operations, suitable collateral is lacking, and major infrastructures require substantial capital investment and have a long-term nature (GWP, 2017). By embracing IWRM principles, developing countries will be better able to explore alternative financing solutions outside the traditional water sector and leverage interdependencies to strengthen and achieve progress on SDG 6 and other related SDGs.

IWRM emphasises the importance of decentralising water management. Water challenges often extend beyond local or hydrological boundaries, such as basins. However, local activities can also significantly impact water scarcity beyond their immediate community, highlighting the inadequacy of national and supranational strategies alone. Local management, as advocated by IWRM, is crucial for achieving SDG 6. IWRM views water as a local issue that requires management at the community level. In many developing countries, centralised water management has historically been the norm (Hassan et al., 2014), sometimes leading to resistance from indigenous communities. In the framework of adapting to a shifting climate and operating with IWRM principles, it is crucial to advocate for stakeholder involvement using both top-down and bottom-up approaches, spanning from the national to basin levels, in order to guarantee effective, fair, and enduring water resource management.

Critics of IWRM argue that it is idealistic and may overlook the institutional capacity of developing countries to implement its principles (Mizutani, 2011; Saravanan et al., 2009). Mizutani (2011) argues that developing nations have fewer institutional resources for water management in comparison to developed countries, which have developed institutional capacity over many centuries. Based on Mizutani's (2011) findings, institutional capacity in developing countries might be insufficient to support principles like the human right to water or to implement water management using river basin divisions. Therefore, he suggests that developing extensive institutional capacity for water resources management should precede introducing the IWRM approach in these countries.

Implementing comprehensive, integrated water management approaches can indeed be challenging. However, it is important to acknowledge that there are different levels and types of integration (Batchelor & Butterworth, 2014). IWRM has demonstrated flexibility as an approach to water management, capable of adapting to diverse local and national contexts. Hassing et al. (2009) argue that IWRM requires policymakers to select the most appropriate recommendations, reform measures, management tools, and institutional arrangements tailored to specific cultural, social, political, and economic contexts.

IWRM goes beyond being a scientific theory that researchers can prove or disprove. Instead, it provides practical principles for crucial aspects of management. As Hassing et al. (2009) note, one of the significant strengths of IWRM is that it provides the water community with a common framework applicable across various levels, from local to national and regional contexts.

2.4 Water policymaking

Countries face various challenges, which are undesirable conditions requiring government intervention. The initiatives and approaches by governments in tackling these societal challenges form the basis of public policy (Dye, 2013). According to Rinfret et al. (2018), public policy is a course of action that the government adopts or creates to address public issues. Public policy involves making choices. It represents what governments choose to do about public problems as much as what they choose not to do (Kraft & Furlong, 2018). Making water policies in a country does not happen in a void. Water policies are created and inhibited by the contexts within which they are developed (Maddison & Denniss, 2009; Kraft & Furlong, 2018). This means that policy processes cannot be devoid of the environment within which they take place. Water policy formulation like all other policies typically takes place within a nation's political, social, cultural, and economic environments.(Rinfret et al., 2018). Apart from these general contexts, Clarke et al. (2012) argue that policymaking also occurs within contexts specific to each policy area.

Water policy formulation is significantly influenced by the political context, encompassing factors such as changes in government, the level of political stability within a country, ideologies, priorities of political parties or regimes, and public engagement in political processes, including public opinion and priorities (Kraft & Furlong, 2018; Marume, 2016). Wolter et al. (2022) argue that policymakers often respond to public opinion regarding water policy preferences. According to Paneque et al. (2018), in Spain, specific environmental

concerns that are priorities for the public, such as drought, push for more support of water conservation policy approaches and less support of water supply-side approaches, such as the construction of major hydraulic infrastructures. Political stability, or the lack thereof, plays a crucial role in water policymaking and implementation. In politically unstable environments, water policy can be inconsistent, poorly implemented, or subject to manipulation by competing interest groups (Tropp, 2007; Swatuk, 2005). Political instability often leads to weak governance institutions, corruption, and inefficiencies that hinder effective water management.

Regarding economic conditions, Kraft and Furlong (2018) argue that policymakers often justify decisions on economic grounds, with the state of the economy strongly influencing the policies that governments formulate and implement. During economic downturns, leaders under pressure from the public often prioritise economic recovery efforts, potentially sidelining policies that could divert resources from economic stabilisation (Maks-Solomon & Stoker, 2019). One school of thought suggests that economic downturns may weaken environmental policy by making it harder for policymakers to raise the ambition of existing policies, implement new ones, or maintain current standards (Kachi et al., 2015). In contrast, others (see Bakaki & Bernauer, 2018) contend that environmental quality, such as water quality, has become a key aspect of overall quality of life. Therefore, even during economic recessions, citizens and governments will likely prioritise environmental quality for its intrinsic value.

Policy decisions are also influenced by social conditions, including demographics and population composition, in various ways. Population growth and urbanisation trends significantly influence water policymaking, heightening the demand for water resources, intensifying water stress, and creating challenges in managing water infrastructure and services. As populations grow, especially in water-scarce regions, the demand for water for domestic, agricultural, and industrial use increases. The increase in water consumption leads to over-extraction of water resources, often outpacing the natural replenishment rates of rivers, lakes, and aquifers. This strain requires policymakers to address water allocation, ensuring equitable distribution across sectors while preserving environmental flows. According to the United Nations (2020), global water demand is expected to increase by 20-30 percent by 2050, driven by population growth, particularly in developing countries. This rising demand compels policymakers to develop more efficient water management practices, such as promoting water conservation, improving irrigation systems, and investing in infrastructure to reduce leakage and waste (UNESCO, 2020).

Urbanisation presents additional pressures on water resources due to the concentration of populations in urban areas. Rapid urban growth often outpaces water infrastructure development, leading to inadequate supply systems and poor sanitation. Cities require significant water inputs for household consumption, industries, and sanitation systems, creating competition for water between urban and rural areas. Urbanisation also exacerbates water pollution through increased industrial and household waste, which can degrade water quality (UN-Habitat, 2016).

Culture plays a pivotal role in shaping the demands placed on policymakers, as it reflects the shared values and beliefs within a nation. The fundamental beliefs, principles, and customs that establish a nation's identity determine the boundaries for the policies that are probable to be implemented and executed successfully (Rinfret et al., 2018). In many cultures, water is not just a physical resource but a symbol of life, purity, and sustenance, deeply embedded in religious and spiritual beliefs. For instance, in Hinduism, rivers like the Ganges hold sacred status, and protecting such water bodies becomes a cultural priority (Alley, 2002). Cultural values prioritising water's sacredness can lead to stricter protection of water sources. In some cases, these values can drive the implementation of policies that restrict industrial or agricultural activities near sacred water bodies to prevent pollution, as seen in the efforts to clean the Ganges River in India (Sharma, 2021).

Again, cultural values often inform communal water management practices. In many rural communities, water is viewed as a collective resource, and its management is based on community needs, shared responsibilities, and local customs. In Ghana, customary land tenure systems significantly influence water access, as traditional authorities manage local resources (Agyenim & Gupta, 2012). These communal values often promote sustainable water use based on centuries-old knowledge of local ecosystems. However, they can also complicate enforcing national water policies that do not fully align with local customs.

Another significant contextual aspect common in many developing countries is the substantial involvement of external agencies, such as donor organisations, in policy formulation (Corkery et al., 1995). These agencies often exert influence over policy environments through conditions attached to policy-based lending or funding specific vertical programmes aligned with particular policy approaches (Okuonzi & Macrae, 1995; Koeberle, 2003; Rutkowski, 2007). Donor agencies, including international financial institutions like the World Bank, bilateral aid agencies, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs), influence water policies through

financial support, technical assistance, and policy recommendations. While these agencies can provide crucial resources and expertise, their involvement often comes with specific conditions and priorities that can shape national water governance in ways that may or may not align with local needs and priorities. For example, international financial institutions like the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) may push for the adoption of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) frameworks, privatisation of water services, or the introduction of market-based mechanisms such as water pricing (Bakker, 2010).

2.5 Water policy instruments

According to Howlett (2005), policy instruments are governance tools that involve exercising state power. While a single instrument theoretically targets a specific policy objective, policymakers often employ a combination of instruments to achieve their desired goals in practice. There are various typologies of policy instruments. Winter (2012) categorises them into mandates, economic incentives, and information strategies.

Mandates, or procedural implementation instruments as termed by Howlett (2014), aim to regulate the behaviour of a target population. These are often referred to in the literature as coercive regulation, regulatory instruments, or command-and-control instruments (Carter, 2007; Cocklin, 2009). Economic incentives, also referred to as economic instruments or market-based instruments, have a direct impact on the production, distribution, and consumption of goods and services within society (Howlett, 2014). Other types of policy instruments mentioned in the literature include voluntary approaches and informational measures (Carter, 2007; Cocklin, 2009; Jordan et al., 2015). Government expenditure is also recognised as a policy instrument by Carter (2007).

Water policies are a subset of environmental policies but also intersect with other sectors, such as energy. Their primary goal is to guarantee a sufficient supply of water that meets quality standards while also dealing with concerns like water pollution and scarcity (Winpenny, 2005). The formulation of water policy generally involves conducting comprehensive studies of water resources, forecasting demand under various scenarios, evaluating options for increasing supply, recommending cost-effective solutions to meet projected demands, and finally implementing these plans through public agencies, often at subsidised rates (Winpenny, 2005, p.22).

Governments employ several instruments to achieve their water policy objectives, including regulatory approaches (command and control), market-based instruments (MBIs), voluntary initiatives, and education and information campaigns.

2.5.1 Regulations/regulatory/command-and-control instruments

Regulations encompass any government efforts to impact the actions of businesses or individuals (Carter, 2007). They are the primary methods used to control the environment (Oh & Svendsen, 2015). Regulatory instruments place legally binding constraints on economic entities to achieve environmental goals (Hamilton & Macintosh, 2008). The authorities outline the necessary requirements and consider it a violation if they are not met (Hodge, 1995). Sanctions or penalties are typically enforced in instances of noncompliance. This method focuses on using penalties to deter noncompliance and promote greater adherence.

In terms of water, regulations refer to laws, rules, or standards set by government authorities that must be followed by water and land users as well as water service providers (Global Water Partnership, 2017). For instance, drinking water needs to be pure, and this is defined by specific standards for various substances, organisms, and characteristics of water in each country. Water quality standards establish guidelines and permissible limits for components and impurities in drinking water. In the United States, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) establishes the standards for drinking water quality, which include regulations for more than 90 contaminants. In the United Kingdom, the standards for drinking water are stringent and encompass microorganisms, chemicals like nitrate and pesticides, metals such as lead and copper, water appearance, and taste (Drinking Water Inspectorate, 2017). Sub-Saharan African countries like Ghana and Nigeria have similar standards outlining the specifications for drinking water from packaged water, water provided by public utilities, and other sources (Ghana Standards Authority, 2018; Olusola et al., 2017).

2.5.2 Pros and cons of regulatory/command-and-control instruments

Regulations are generally easy to introduce and administer. Decision-makers are especially drawn to regulatory tools because they can provide accuracy, consistency, and efficiency (Carter, 2007). By establishing a precise standard, both the regulator and the regulated parties understand what is required of them, and enforcement is theoretically guaranteed by a regulatory agency supported by the authority of the law. With regulatory instruments, requirements are uniform within a given productive sector. This makes management and

monitoring easier. According to Bouwma et al. (2015), another advantage of command and control instruments is that they promote the rule of law by applying equal rules and sanctions to all targeted actors, protecting them from arbitrary governmental decisions.

Public regulations are common in most countries; however, they have been criticised for being inflexible and inefficient (Cocklin, 2009). The rigidity or inflexibility is due to uniform standards that do not take into consideration differences in the local cost of compliance and compliance capabilities of the regulated. Lyon (2013) indicates that the rigidity of command and control regulations leaves the regulated with no option even to choose the least-cost method of compliance. As a result, the regulated have little or no incentives to improve their performance on their initiative (Andersen, 1995). Furthermore, actors are only encouraged to meet the standards required. They do not work to do better once the requirement has been satisfied. The possible inefficiency of regulatory instruments, as has been identified, also concerns implementation. According to Carter (2007), regulatory regimes are often weak, their implementation may be time-consuming, and costs may be high, although there are also examples of effective regulatory instruments. As a result of the cost involved, problems may arise when funds are not adequate for regulatory agencies to enforce rules properly. Regulatory capture is also a concern where regulators may be captured by their interests or the interests of some influential stakeholders instead of the public interest (Prihandono & Widiati, 2023; K' Akumu, 2022). When the responsibility for implementation is passed down from one level of government to another because resources for lower administrative levels are often insufficient, this leads to ineffective regulation and oversight. Benson (2015, p. 555) suggests that while sanctions can be effective, regulatory tools can also encourage the emergence of resistant cultures and a limited approach to compliance among those being regulated. Eventually, this can lead to a confrontational dynamic between regulators and the regulated, leading to higher oversight expenses and diminished effectiveness. It must, however, be noted that despite the many criticisms against regulation in general as a policy instrument, it is still widely adopted in water policies in most countries.

2.5.3 Market-based/economic instruments

In response to the limitations of command and control measures, there has been a push for the adoption of market-based (economic) instruments (MBIs) (Pearce, 1989; Hodge, 1995). Market-based instruments, also known as economic incentives, are regulatory tools that

influence behaviour through price signals rather than explicit mandates on pollution control or resource management methods (Hockenstein et al., 1997).

In general, MBIs can be divided into five primary categories: charges (taxes), subsidies, tradeable or marketable permits, deposit-refund systems (similar to subsidies), and enforcement incentives to ensure compliance with environmental regulations (Pearce & Barbier, 2000). Some researchers (e.g., Zandersen et al., 2009; Arriagada & Perrings, 2009) classify subsidies, such as voluntary and targeted subsidies or performance-based contracts like Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES), as additional economic instruments. These subsidies are designed to improve the provision of goods that are otherwise not adequately provided, encouraging environmentally friendly behaviours or nature-based solutions. Market-based instruments aim to ensure better responses to environmental issues from actors by providing financial incentives/disincentives in many cases (Cocklin, 2009). In the water sector, many economic instruments are employed. Some are aimed at water quality, such as effluent tax, pesticide tax, and trading of permits for polluting water. Others are aimed at water quantity, such as subsidies for drinking water, residential water pricing, agriculture water tariffs, water abstraction charges, and others (Lago et al., 2015).

2.5.3.1 Enforcement incentives

The following penalties are intended to motivate polluters to adhere to environmental standards and regulations (Bernstein, 1997). Enforcement incentives, which are sometimes categorised as regulatory instruments by certain researchers, encompass a range of mechanisms such as:

1. **Non-adherence fines:** Imposed on polluters if their discharges surpass permissible levels.
2. **Bonds for performance:** Payments submitted to regulatory authorities prior to engaging in activities that may cause pollution, which will be returned after proving satisfactory environmental performance.
3. **Liability assignment:** Making actual or potential polluters liable for any environmental damage they cause.

One advantage of enforcement incentives, particularly fines, is their relative ease of imposition and potential for immediate enforcement, often providing significant revenue to governments (UNEP, 2009). Performance bonds enhance certainty in recovering damages from non-

compliant activities initiated by governments or private plaintiffs (UNEP, 2009). However, a notable disadvantage is their reliance on a robust legal framework, leading to prolonged litigation even in well-functioning legal systems (UNEP, 2009).

2.5.3.2 Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES)

When users or beneficiaries of ecosystem services make payments to individuals or communities whose management decisions impact the provision of those services in agreements, this is known as Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) (OECD, 2010). (see Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: Water-related ecosystem services

Source: Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005)

Figure 2.2 illustrates the four primary categories of ecosystem services: supporting services (or habitat services), which are critical for generating all other ecosystem services; regulating services, which control ecosystem functions; provisioning services, which supply tangible benefits like food and fresh water; and cultural services, which offer intangible benefits.

Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) provides various environmental and economic benefits. According to OECD (2010), PES compensates individuals or communities whose land use decisions impact water ecosystem services, covering the costs of maintaining these services. PES encourages positive behavioural changes through incentives rather than mandates. UNDP (2020) highlights that, unlike command-and-control approaches, PES is flexible and adaptable

to local conditions. It can help alleviate poverty by generating cash income in rural areas, often areas with concentrated poverty (UNDP, 2020). PES programme participants also learn sustainable resource management practices through training and technical support (Bakshi, 2019).

The introduction of PES can incentivise individuals to preserve watershed services, such as clean drinking water, as seen in the New York City Watershed Agricultural Program. This program effectively reduced agricultural water pollution, allowing New York City to avoid building a costly filtration plant to meet water quality standards (Lin, 2014). However, despite its benefits, PES schemes have drawbacks. UNDP (2020) notes that the design, negotiation, and implementation of PES schemes can be costly, especially considering the challenges in economically valuing ecosystem services. PES requires substantial and long-term financial commitments (Börner et al., 2011). Successful implementation also demands a deep understanding of local conditions and robust institutional support (Bakshi, 2019).

In many developing countries, the effectiveness of PES is hindered by challenges in securing accurate land property data, which is crucial for implementing and managing PES schemes (UNDP, 2020). Moreover, long-term PES contracts may limit local governments' and communities' decision-making autonomy by prescribing specific land management practices. There are also concerns that landowners might lose rights to their land or restrict their ability to harvest products (Bakshi, 2019).

2.5.4 Pros and cons of Market-based/economic instruments

Market-oriented tools, overall, leverage market dynamics, and if properly implemented, they motivate companies and individuals to take steps that benefit them while also accomplishing public objectives. They appear to be a promising alternative to regulatory instruments but not without some shortcomings. According to Lago et al. (2015), adopting economic instruments is usually met with limited interest and political resistance from political actors. Policymakers are often apprehensive of economic instruments because they tend to prefer tried and tested mechanisms such as regulations. As a result, economic instruments with the least political resistance are often the ones applied (Carter, 2007).

2.5.5 Voluntary action/Information instruments

According to Carter (2007), voluntary action refers to initiatives by individuals or organisations aimed at environmental protection that are not legally mandated or financially incentivised. Encouraging participation through voluntary approaches allows for involvement without directly penalising non-participants, usually with ongoing monitoring to guarantee improvements in environmental performance (Hamilton & Macintosh, 2008; OECD, 2017). Examples include green consumerism, ethical investments, recycling efforts, conservation activities, eco-management schemes, and voluntary agreements among companies (Carter, 2007). Voluntary approaches encompass strategies such as information campaigns, educational programs, nudging techniques, and voluntary agreements to foster environmental stewardship.

2.5.5.1 Information campaigns

Pursuing sustainable development and environmental policy objectives requires the public to be sufficiently sensitised about the environment and its management. By making more information available, it is believed that people can make more informed decisions that are meaningful and environmentally sound (Hepburn, 2009). The dissemination of information aims to reach a wide audience and utilises various media channels for communication. For instance, the 'Love Water' initiative in the UK urges the British population to contribute to the conservation of water sources for the benefit of upcoming generations (Water UK, 2019). There is also 'The Love Our Rivers Campaign' in Malaysia which seeks to raise awareness among the public about the significance of rivers and draw attention to the alarming pollution levels in the country's rivers. According to government estimates, this campaign was successful in reducing the pollution levels of rivers in the country (Department of Irrigation and Drainage, 2017).

2.5.5.2 Environmental education

Education is often seen as a necessary component for changing behaviour (Arlinghaus & Johnston, 2017; Boyes & Stanisstreet, 2012). This is because, through education, people may adopt new ideas and behaviours to which they are introduced. Environmental education is seen as a tool that allows individuals of all ages to participate and learn. In various Asian and Pacific countries, environmental education has been incorporated through specific environmental classes and by integrating environmental issues into other school subjects (Venkatarama, 2017). Environmental education aims to enhance individuals' consciousness and comprehension of environmental concerns and safeguard the environment by enhancing their

ability to address environmental risks (Hamilton & Macintosh, 2008). Apart from formal education, other direct ways of promoting environmental education are through dialogue, interactive workshops, and town hall meetings.

Education and information approaches inform people who may be unaware of their contribution to water-related problems. This might change their behaviour once they get the correct information or learn how to help solve the problem, just as Katz et al. (2016) reported. Education and information campaigns have additional benefits in that they do not enforce stringent mandates or limitations on personal behaviour, unlike command-and-control regulations. However, sometimes, parties who may not be interested in the information or those who do not share a common agenda with the regulator may refuse to receive the information or decide not to act on the information received. Education and information approaches do not directly lead to compliance, making evaluating their outcomes difficult (Silva et al., 2019). The benefits of these types of instruments will only be realised if the appropriate information is made available to those who need it (Hepburn, 2009). Without proper design and a receptive target group education and information instruments may be ineffective for environmental objectives. However, they are generally considered a vital aspect of environmental policy packages. (Hamilton & Macintosh, 2008). Many methods of education and information assume that individuals are able and willing to handle the provided information, make informed decisions, and work towards policy objectives. However, there has been a change in perspective with the introduction of the concept of nudging (Mont et al., 2014).

2.5.5.3 *Nudges*

Nudging became popular in academic discourse after Richard Thaler and Cass Sunstein published the book '*Nudge: Improving Decisions About Health, Wealth, and Happiness*' in 2008 (Mont et al., 2014). The authors argue that two different thought processes or systems drive human actions. System 1 describes the fast, automatic, instinctive, heuristic thought processes. In contrast, the slow, reflective, and systematic thought processes, which are largely conditioned by the environment in which choices are made, are called system 2. Nudges harness the automatic processes of system 1 (Thaler & Sunstein, 2008). Thaler and Sunstein define nudges as "any aspect of the choice architecture that predictably alters people's behaviour without forbidding any options or significantly changing their economic incentives" (Thaler & Sunstein, 2008, p. 6). Importantly, the authors add: "To count as a mere nudge, the intervention must be easy and cheap to avoid" (Thaler & Sunstein, 2008, p. 6). Nudges are

methods that respect people's freedom while guiding them toward specific choices and also allowing them to make their own decisions (Sunstein, 2014). As tools for governance, nudges alter the 'choice architecture' of individuals, which refers to the environment in which decisions are made (Van Deun et al., 2019; Mont et al., 2014). Therefore, nudging is a method of developing public policies that modify the decision-making environment intending to influence individuals to make a specific choice. Nudges inform individuals that they are free to choose, but the options available to them and how they are presented are influenced by expert efforts authorised by the government (John & Stoker, 2017). Nudges encompass a broad spectrum of tactics, such as employing default rules, social standards, and prompts and making environmental objectives easier and more convenient to achieve.

Nudges were observed to be effective in a study conducted by Ferraro and Price (2013). It was found that water consumers in Cobb County significantly decreased their water usage when they were informed about their neighbours' consumption levels. The use of social norms, specifically emphasising the behaviour of the majority, is most influential when it is presented in a localised and specific manner (Sunstein, 2014). According to Thaler & Sunstein (2008) and Nielsen et al. (2016), nudging can either replace or supplement traditional policy tools and provide an alternative method to achieve policy objectives. One claimed benefit of nudges is that policymakers can influence the daily choices and behaviours of citizens inexpensively and effectively without relying on commands or adjusting incentives (Hansen & Jespersen, 2013).

2.5.5.4 Voluntary agreement

Voluntary action by businesses includes industry self-regulation, which involves unilateral initiatives. It also encompasses negotiated agreements between government and industry, voluntary partnership programmes offered by the government, the disclosure of information on products, and environmental labelling (Lyon, 2013). Self-regulation (unilateral initiatives) occurs when companies take voluntary actions to decrease pollution or safeguard natural resources without government involvement (Segerson, 2013). Instances of self-regulation include the climate protection pledge made by the German industry (OECD, 2003). Additionally, there is the European voluntary agreement on washing machines, in which leading European producers and importers of clothes washing machines have committed to halting the production and importation of washing machines with low energy efficiency and high associated emissions within the European Union (Ahmed & Segerson, 2011). Negotiated

agreements are also frequent voluntary arrangements. They are obligatory commitments made by a public authority and a private sector entity, which typically do not have any penalties attached (Carter, 2007). Instances include the Accelerated Reduction/Elimination of Toxics Program and the environmental agreement with the steel company Dofasco Incorporated in Canada, the Pollution Control Agreements in Yokohama and Kitakyushu Cities in Japan (OECD, 2003), and numerous energy efficiency agreements carried out in Europe (Rezessy & Bertoldi, 2011).

2.5.6 Pros and cons of voluntary action/information instruments

One of the main benefits of voluntary approaches is their ability to provide a flexible and cost-efficient way to achieve policy goals. This is especially true because participants can determine the most effective methods for reaching targets, thus promoting swift implementation and adherence (Carter, 2007; Lyon, 2013). Companies that engage in voluntary initiatives can enhance their public reputation and gain valuable information from these programs (US EPA, 2018; Segerson, 2013). Voluntary agreements encourage closer collaboration between regulators and polluters, leading to improved information sharing, reduced conflicts, and faster implementation (Segerson, 2013). It has been suggested that voluntary approaches involve lower administrative expenses compared to other policy tools and, under certain conditions, may be more efficient than mandatory approaches (Hamilton & Macintosh, 2008). This idea, supported by the OECD (2003), suggests that the operational costs of Pollution Control Agreements in Japan have been minimal. The same holds true for Canada. While voluntary approaches may have some advantages, some scholars contend that they lack effectiveness and are unlikely to achieve policy objectives optimally (Hamilton & Macintosh, 2008; Bouwma et al., 2015). This is due to their often modest nature and the lower levels of commitment they typically involve. Carter (2007) suggests that implementing voluntary agreements may pose challenges, as there are no mechanisms in place to ensure compliance. There is a risk that certain producers will try to take advantage of environmental protection efforts made by others. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) explains that it may seem counterintuitive for companies to voluntarily take steps to improve the environment, such as reducing pollution, but they may do so when the benefits are equal to or greater than the costs of such actions (OECD, 1999). In practice, Carter (2007) argues that voluntary agreements can be effective when the government threatens to impose stricter measures if the industry does not reach a voluntary agreement, as seen in the case of Swedish firms that

voluntarily agreed to stop using chlorine in paper-bleaching, presumably to avoid tougher regulations when the EPA was crafting laws to prohibit its use.

According to Sterner and Coria (2012), voluntary methods may be more appropriate in situations where the government lacks the power to force the polluter to comply. Additionally, voluntary approaches can be utilised to address the widespread violation of mandatory regulations in many developing nations (Blackman, 2007). Evaluating the actual effectiveness of voluntary approaches presents challenges. Furthermore, they are rarely implemented in isolation and are often used alongside other tools to promote sustainable development. Voluntary approaches are typically included as part of policy packages as a useful complement to other instruments (Sterner & Coria 2012; OECD, 2003).

With a good knowledge of the different policy instruments and an understanding of the context of policymaking, policymakers can develop good policies. However, a new challenge is presented when policy strategies must be implemented. The next section discusses policy implementation with an emphasis on barriers to implementation.

2.6 Policy implementation and barriers to implementation

The implementation of a policy starts after it has been developed and approved. Maddison & Denniss (2009) argue that a policy that is not put into action has no practical importance. Therefore, implementation is crucial as it involves translating policy plans into actionable steps aimed at achieving stated objectives (Gerston, 2015). Policies at this point are put into practice through specific action plans. This may include dividing objectives into individual projects for implementation. Winter (2012) emphasises that achieving goals is the primary measure of successful implementation, serving as the outcome variable. This perspective is also supported by Grindle (2017), underscoring that the effectiveness of policy implementation hinges on executing plans designed to meet policy goals. From another perspective, implementation involves governmental agencies turning policy regulations and commitments into practical realities (Dye, 2013).

Policy implementation could involve establishing new organisations, restructuring existing institutions, departments, and agencies, or assigning additional responsibilities to current organisations. These institutions, departments, and agencies can also be referred to as bureaucracies. Bureaucracies comprise all public sector organisations comprising public officials appointed through public service recruitment processes rather than elections

(Poocharoen, 2015). Bureaucracy represents the institutional arrangement, while bureaucrats are the individuals within that arrangement responsible for implementing policies and enforcing laws. According to Poocharoen (2015), most public policies are intricate, often very extensive and ambiguous, mirroring the complexities of public issues. The complexity of policies often necessitates involvement from multiple bureaucracies. Gerston (2015) contends that even though policy implementation may seem uncomplicated, it is not simple and often does not happen automatically, highlighting a significant disparity between policy goals and their actual implementation. This disparity can be comprehended within the realm of obstacles to implementation. Winter (2012) asserts that multiple stakeholders are invested in policy implementation. Ultimately, the various viewpoints and priorities expressed by these stakeholders impact implementation by causing postponement, distortion, and policy ineffectiveness. Poocharoen (2015) argues that when policies are implemented, different bureaucracies may interpret and adjust the rules and instructions to align with their own perspectives and local contexts. This adaptation of policy goals and the use of diverse strategies during implementation can lead to policy failure. According to scholars like Winter (2012) and Poocharoen (2015), the barriers to implementation resemble a bottom-up approach, acknowledging that those responsible for the implementation of policies will influence and modify them to suit real-world situations. Different actors with varying understandings of the issue and its resolution can influence implementation from various angles. When implementation is approached as a hierarchical process, barriers may include insufficient institutional capacity, inadequate legal frameworks, political pressures, limited funding, and lack of intersectoral coordination (Kalaba, 2016; Carter, 2007; Winter, 2012). Implementation may also face technical obstacles due to the structure of the policy itself. As Winter (2012) points out, ineffective implementation can also be traced back to the formulation and design of the policy. This could happen when the policy has unclear objectives, is overly ambitious or lacks focus, utilises ineffective policy tools that fail to address policy objectives, or lacks coherence between goals and methods, such as unclear actions and responsibilities for policy implementation. Organisational and inter-organisational behaviours can also impact implementation, reflecting varying levels of commitment and coordination. Winter (2012) suggests that a lack of coordination among organisations can lead to disagreement on a fundamental understanding of implementation. Additionally, if one organisation relies on outputs from another as input for its contribution to the implementation, a lack of cooperation from the first organisation can hinder the implementation process. In his study, Winter (2012) also points out that the behaviour of frontline workers, known as street-level bureaucrats, can

impact the implementation of most policies. These public officials have significant discretion in their interactions with citizens and businesses, often operating under numerous demands and limited resources. To improve their effectiveness, they may take shortcuts that can systematically influence how they carry out their policy responsibilities. Collaborative efforts among street-level workers, whether imposed or encouraged from higher levels of authority, also play a role in the successful implementation of policies (Hill & Hupe, 2002). Acknowledging that the behaviour of the intended recipients of public policies, such as citizens or businesses, plays a significant role in the implementation process is crucial. The behaviour of these groups not only affects the outcomes of policies, but also impacts the performance of street-level bureaucrats as they collaborate in delivering public services and enforcing regulations (Winter, 2012). Generally, obstacles to implementation can lead to either non-implementation or unsuccessful policy implementation. Unsuccessful implementation is when a policy fails to achieve its intended outcomes despite being fully implemented (Maddison & Denniss, 2009).

Implementing most environmental policies is intended to preserve the environment and natural resources. Water policies are no exception as they target managing water resources efficiently. The World Bank in 2014 called for greater attention on water resources management because water management underlies every development challenge the world is facing now. The next section focuses on water resources management with particular attention to governance practices in Africa.

2.7 Governance frameworks for water resource management in Africa

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have the challenging aim of ensuring that clean water is universally accessible by 2030. This objective goes beyond just drinking water and includes the sustainable management of water resources. Dealing with these issues is essential for addressing the major development challenges of the 21st century, such as access to safe drinking water and sanitation, creating sustainable cities, ensuring food and energy security, fostering economic growth, and maintaining healthy ecosystems (The World Bank, 2014). The OECD (2015) states that addressing water challenges brings up important questions about what needs to be accomplished, who is responsible, why it is significant, and how it should be put into action. This section focuses on the governance systems in place, specifically the policies, strategic plans, or action plans for water resources management at continental and regional (the Economic Community of West African States, ECOWAS) levels.

2.7.1 Water resources management at the continental level

The African Union, working with the African Development Bank and the UN Economic Commission for Africa, has developed a new strategic approach for water management known as the Africa Water Vision policy for 2025. This policy is designed to guide efforts to realise the vision. The Africa Water Vision 2025 recognises that maintaining the status quo will not be enough to tackle the water resource challenges encountered at regional and national levels throughout Africa. As a result, the vision puts forward the idea that new approaches and actions are necessary to address these challenges. The vision proposes “*an Africa where there is equitable and sustainable use and management of water resources for poverty alleviation, socio-economic development, regional cooperation, and environmental sustainability*” (Economic Commission for Africa, 2000, p. 2).

Central to this vision is acknowledging water's crucial function in supporting life, promoting development, and maintaining important environmental resources. The Vision outlines essential elements for effective water resources management, focusing on five critical factors: population and demographic trends, lifestyles and consumption patterns, economic development structure and level, technological advancements and choices, and governance, policies, and institutions. These factors are considered integral to achieving the Africa Water Vision 2025 goals.

The plan of action provides a strategic pathway to accomplish the Africa Water Vision, covering four main sets of activities. Within the ‘Improving water resource governance’ classification, member countries are urged to embrace and execute Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) principles and policies. This involves carrying out organisational changes and building capabilities at local, national, and transboundary river basin levels, with a focus on adopting the river basin as the primary unit for managing water resources and improving the management of river basins and aquifers.

2.7.2 Water resources management at the regional level

The West Africa Water Resources Policy (WAWRP) was created and approved by the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) in partnership with the West African Economic and Monetary Union (UEMOA) and the Permanent Interstate Committee for Drought Control in the Sahel (CILSS). This policy received official endorsement at the 35th Session of the Conference of Heads of State and Government held in Abuja on December 19,

2008 (IUCN, 2016). It aligns with the West African perspective on water, life, and environment for 2025, originally adopted in March 2000 by the ECOWAS Council of Ministers for Water and Environment (Department of Agriculture, Environment and Water Resources, 2019). The West Africa Water Resources Policy aims to help reduce poverty and promote sustainable development by providing guidance to ECOWAS and its Member States on water resource management. This policy highlights the importance of taking a balanced approach that incorporates economic development, social fairness, and environmental preservation (ECOWAS, 2008).

WAWRP envisions that by 2025, water resources across the region will be effectively managed in a sustainable manner, ensuring access to safe drinking water for every individual (ECOWAS, 2008). The policy specifically aims to promote harmonisation and integration between national and regional water resources management policies. It encourages member states to establish suitable frameworks for water management that support sustainable development goals (IUCN, 2016).

The policy upholds several fundamental principles aimed at achieving equitable, efficient, and sustainable water resources management. One key principle advocates managing water resources based on hydrological basins or aquifer systems, emphasising natural units for water management (ECOWAS, 2008). Economic principles such as 'user pays' and 'polluter pays' are promoted to ensure sustainable water sector financing (ECOWAS, 2008). Additionally, principles fostering collaboration among stakeholders in the water sector, including cooperation, fair and reasonable use, partnership, solidarity, and complementarity, are emphasised (IUCN, 2016). Gender equality is also integral, ensuring that policies, capacity development, planning, and implementation in the water sector consider the interests and contributions of women, men, and vulnerable groups (ECOWAS, 2008).

After an extensive analysis of relevant concepts in the literature, the subsequent section dwells on theories that underpin this research.

2.8 Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework of this study encompasses selected theories that supports the researcher's understanding and approach to investigating the problem identified (Raef, 2016). These theories not only offer a lens through which the research problem can be viewed but also inform the development of research methodology. By integrating various theoretical

perspectives, the researcher draws upon established concepts and frameworks that have been validated through previous studies, enhancing the robustness and credibility of the study. This framework serves as a guide, helping to clarify the relationships between different variables at play within the context of the research. Furthermore, it allows the researcher to position the study within the broader academic discourse and makes it easier to identify gaps in the existing governance mechanisms for basin water management.

2.8.1 Theory of Participation

Encouraging citizens to participate in development processes is considered a best practice. It ensures that decision-making is inclusive and democratic, as Arnstein (1969) described. The participation of citizens, or the power of citizens, allows those who are often left out of development processes to be purposefully involved in the future. Citizen participation aims to influence the outcome of the process so that all sides are considered rather than just benefiting some parties (Arnstein, 1969). According to Fagence (1977), citizen participation should not be viewed as an alternative to traditional decision-making processes by authorities and institutions. Rather, it should be seen as a collaborative effort – a decision-forming partnership. Participation involves active engagement of citizens in decision-making beyond just being present and encourages meaningful contributions (Arnstein 1969: p. 216). Concerning the environment, Simmons (2007) asserts that participation occurs when citizens are allowed to voice their opinions on an environmental decision before its implementation. In this scenario, their views, interests, and concerns are considered, elevating their role to that of decision-makers and giving them power.

A crucial aspect of participation is that the participants must be motivated to act (Fagence, 1977). By participating in decision-making processes, citizens may gain a sense of ownership and influence over the results. However, Simmons (2007, p.6) notes that authorities may hesitate to promote citizen participation. This is often due to technical experts claiming ownership over technical issues and limiting public discourse, even though these issues have substantial impacts on the public. According to authorities, the general public often lacks the time, knowledge, and personal motivation to participate in technically based problem-solving. As a result, experts are often relied upon to make more rational decisions (Fiorino, 1990). This is also referred to as indirect participation, where professional administrators act on citizens' behalf and in the state's best interest. The general public is considered to lack the necessary 'technical knowledge, authority, and status' to be involved in decisions that directly affect their

lives. Nonetheless, Simmons (2007) argues that all decisions involving technical information are made through discussions, and non-technical elements like social, economic, and political factors often guide decision-making.. Advocates for greater citizen participation state a variety of its positive effects, including promoting democracy, building trust, increasing transparency, enhancing accountability, reducing conflict, ascertaining priorities and promoting legitimacy (Callahan, 2007).

2.8.1.1 Levels of participation

Participation can take several forms. As a continuum, there can be different levels of citizen involvement in decision-making, as explained by Arnstein (1969). Arnstein's typology of citizen participation includes eight distinct levels that span from non-participation to citizen power, where citizens have complete control over the decision-making process. The levels in between reflect varying degrees of participation, such as tokenism, where citizens are present. However, their input is not taken seriously, and delegated power, where they have some influence but not full decision-making power (see Figure 2.5). Arnstein's framework provides a useful tool for understanding and organising citizen participation processes and can help identify areas where further engagement and empowerment of citizens is needed.

Figure 2.3: Levels of citizen participation

Source: Arnstein (1969, p. 217)

Arnstein (1969) identifies the last two levels of manipulation and therapy as indicating a lack of true participation. These levels serve as a substitute for genuine participation, in which those in power engage in a one-way flow of information in an attempt to bring public perceptions into conformity with technical experts. The aim is to educate or cure the public. The third, fourth, and fifth levels describe tokenism, which refers to a superficial or symbolic form of participation that creates the appearance of inclusion without granting citizens any substantial influence or power in decision-making processes. *Tokenism* involves including citizens in discussions or activities to create the illusion of participation, but their presence is merely symbolic, and their views are not given due consideration by those in power. In practice, institutions might hold public meetings and allow for public comments to pacify the public, but these comments will not influence the final decision or outcome. At the tokenism level, citizens have a voice, but the authorities still have the ultimate decision-making power. Beyond tokenism, there are higher levels of citizen influence with increasing levels of decision-making authority. *Partnership* represents a higher degree of citizen power. Citizens and decision-makers work together collaboratively. The process of decision-making involves active participation from citizens, who contribute to creating and carrying out policies, plans, and programmes. *Delegated Power*: At this stage, decision-makers delegate significant powers to citizens or citizen groups. Citizens have substantial control over certain aspects of decision-

making, and their decisions directly impact the outcomes and in the ideal situation of *Citizen Control*, citizens possess the greatest level of authority. This signifies that citizens not only possess the privilege to take part in decision-making but also wield the ultimate power and authority over the entire process. According to Fagence's (1977, p. 273) perspective, the potential for citizen involvement in decision-making is influenced by the proficiency of citizenship skills among the interested parties (active and competent citizens are better equipped to contribute to the conversation) and the willingness of the government entity to embrace a more expansive democratic approach beyond the boundaries of the council chamber.

While citizen participation may sometimes be associated with delays, frustration, and challenges, many scholars argue that a high level of citizen involvement is beneficial as long as the decision-making system can handle it. Fagence (1977) suggests that there comes a point when public participation must come to an end, and a decision must be made. There are also instances where the involvement of laypeople is not encouraged, such as when sensitive issues are being discussed, and a smaller audience is necessary.

In 1977, Fagence noted that while many public administrators acknowledge the lack of public involvement in government decision-making, few have proposed effective methods for decision-makers to obtain valuable input from citizens. This highlights the importance of exploring different techniques for citizen participation.

2.8.1.2 Means of participation

According to Fiorini (1990), institutions can use five different techniques for public participation in environmental issues. These techniques include public hearings, initiatives, public surveys, negotiated rulemaking, and citizen review panels, as discussed in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Means of citizen participation.

Means of participation	Characteristics
Public hearings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -A conventional means of participation -The commonest form of administrative participation -Loosely structured, open forums, involves interested members of the public to hear the proposals of institutions and respond
Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -A broad participation mechanism -Enable citizens to place issues on the ballot for voter approval often through a petition process -Citizens can initiate an initiative at any time, gathering the required number of signatures.

	-A tool to directly influence the legislative agenda and address issues important to citizens, bypassing the traditional legislative process
Public surveys	-provide a more representative portrait of public opinion -can complement other means of participation such as hearings -can be used to incorporate the views of the "uninterested but affected public" that would otherwise lack representation
Negotiated rulemaking	-involves stakeholders who have a direct interest in the regulations, including affected communities, in a collaborative process to develop regulations to protect the environment -the primary goal is to achieve consensus among stakeholders, aims to reduce conflict and build understanding -It is used less frequently
Citizens review panels	-Panels are designed to provide a means for ordinary citizens to contribute their perspectives and insights on aspects of public policies, plans, programmes, or projects -Panel is made up of individuals from the community who may be randomly selected or volunteer to participate -They serve as a check and balance mechanism, ensuring accountability and transparency in decision-making -It is innovative and used less frequently

Source: Fiorini (1990)

2.8.2 Stakeholder Theory

In order to succeed in strategic management, it is crucial to go beyond a limited emphasis on shareholders and take into account the interests and issues of all stakeholders participating in an organisation (Freeman, 1984). As defined by Freeman (1984), stakeholders include any group or individual who can affect or be affected by an organisation's objectives. This broader perspective encompasses shareholders and other entities with a vested interest in the organisation. Freeman emphasises the complex and interconnected relationships between stakeholders and notes that their interests may overlap or even conflict. Effective strategic management requires a deep understanding of these intricate relationships and the ability to navigate them skillfully. Donaldson and Preston (1995) define stakeholders as individuals or groups with legitimate interests in both procedural and substantive aspects of corporate activity. Stakeholders are identified based on their interests in the corporation, irrespective of whether the corporation has any functional interest in them. The authors also differentiate between two perspectives of stakeholder theory: the descriptive perspective, which analyzes how organisations behave regarding stakeholders, and the instrumental perspective, which concentrates on managing stakeholder relationships to enhance corporate performance.

According to Donaldson & Preston (1995, p. 66), each stakeholder group should be evaluated on its own merits rather than solely for its ability to advance the interests of another group.

For this research, a ‘stakeholder’ is defined as an individual, group, or other organisation that possesses an interest in the activities of a particular organisation and can influence it (Savage et al., 1991). Fagence (1977) discussed that the greater the diversity of interests represented in the decision-making process, the more innovative the proposals will be. Hence, organisations must engage with their stakeholders while making decisions, as they can provide valuable insights and perspectives that could contribute to the organisation's success. Since managing stakeholder relationships is important, managers must find a way to properly identify stakeholders and understand their practices, expectations, and interests for onward engagement.

In 1997, Mitchell, Agle, and Wood contributed to Freeman's concept of "The Principle of Who or What Really Counts" by clarifying which entities are considered stakeholders of a firm and which stakeholders managers should pay attention to. They presented a normative theory of stakeholder identification, which logically explains why managers should consider certain classes of entities as stakeholders. They also provided a comprehensive framework for understanding how organisations recognise and prioritise their stakeholders, suggesting that organisations evaluate them based on Power, Legitimacy, and Urgency (see Table 2.3). The level of salience of a stakeholder in the eyes of the organisation is determined based on these attributes (see Figure 2.2).

Table 2.2: Attributes of stakeholder salience

Attribute	Definition
Power	The ability of a stakeholder to exert influence over the organisation.
Legitimacy	The perceived appropriateness or validity of a stakeholder's claim to a stake in the organisation's activities.
Urgency	The degree to which a stakeholder's claim demands immediate attention or response.

Source: Mitchell et al. (1997)

The authors argue that managers' perception of stakeholder attributes - power, legitimacy, and urgency - positively correlates with stakeholder salience (Mitchell et al., 1997).

Figure 2.4: Model of stakeholder salience

Source: Mitchell et al. (1997)

Table 2.4 below explains the eight-part stakeholder typology developed by Mitchell et al. (1997). Their assessment is based on the strength of the three attributes of power, legitimacy, and urgency. The eight stakeholder classes are grouped into three main categories - latent, expectant, and definitive - depending on a combination of these attributes. This typology is illustrated in Figure 2.4 and Table 2.3.

Table 2.3: Typology of stakeholders

Classes	Category	Definition	Type
Classes 1, 2 & 3 Dormant, discretionary and demanding	Latent stakeholders	Possess only one attribute, and managers may not be interested in these stakeholders.	<i>Dormant stakeholder</i> has power, but no urgency or legitimacy. Therefore not interested in using power.
		Latent stakeholders are not likely to give any attention or acknowledgement to the organisation	<i>Discretionary stakeholders</i> possess only legitimacy
		Stakeholder salience is low	<i>Demanding stakeholders</i> has only urgency
Classes 4, 5 & 6 Dominant, dependent, and dangerous	Expectant stakeholders	Higher engagement with managers because they are regarded as ‘expecting something’	<i>Dominant stakeholders</i> possess both power and legitimacy
		Possess two attributes leading the stakeholder to an active stance, with a corresponding increase in firm responsiveness to the stakeholder's interests.	<i>Dependent stakeholders</i> possess urgency and legitimacy
		Stakeholder salience is moderate	<i>Dangerous stakeholders</i> have urgency and power but lacks legitimacy
Class 7	Definitive stakeholders	Possess all three attributes therefore managers have a clear and immediate mandate to attend to and give priority to that stakeholder's claim. Stakeholder salience is high	<i>Definitive stakeholders</i> possess power and legitimacy with an urgent claim

Source: Mitchell et al. (1997)

Mitchell et al. (1997) assert that stakeholders who are perceived as more salient are likely to capture managerial attention and influence decision-making processes within an organisation. It is worth noting that they also acknowledge that stakeholder salience is dynamic and can change over time, and all attributes are temporary, subject to both acquisition and loss. Changes in the external environment or within the organisation can impact the salience of specific stakeholders. Consequently, management must recognise that a party needs at least one

attribute to be acknowledged as a stakeholder. However, possessing power alone is insufficient to categorise a stakeholder as a high priority. Legitimacy is needed to confer authority, while urgency is crucial for implementation. Therefore, a stakeholder must be conscious of their power and willing to exercise it.

2.9 Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework illustrates a web of relationships where each component relies on and responds to the others. Effective water governance requires understanding the socio-political context, active stakeholder participation, and robust policy implementation mechanisms. The interactions among these concepts create a dynamic system for sustainable water resources management in Ghana. Each element feeds into and shapes the others, creating a holistic approach to addressing water challenges.

Figure 2.5 Conceptual framework

Source: Author's construct, 2024

From Figure 2.5, the overarching political, socio-economic, and cultural context is the foundation for the entire framework. It shapes the values, norms, and priorities that inform water governance, stakeholder dynamics, citizen participation and policy implementation. For example, political stability may facilitate stakeholder engagement, while socio-economic challenges can hinder effective governance.

Water governance establishes the framework within which water policies are developed and executed. Governance structures (policies, laws, regulations, institutional arrangement) dictate how resources are allocated and managed, directly influencing the decision-making process, such as the implementation of IWRM strategies. Regarding stakeholder dynamics, the engagement and interests of stakeholders influence both water governance and policy implementation. Diverse stakeholder interests can drive more inclusive governance practices, ensuring that policies reflect the needs and concerns of different groups. Citizen participation is also critical to strengthening water governance by ensuring transparency and accountability. When citizens are involved in decision-making, they can hold authorities accountable, leading to more effective governance. Also, active citizen engagement can facilitate smoother implementation and greater acceptance of policies.

Policy implementation culminates the interactions among governance frameworks, stakeholder dynamics, and citizen participation. Effective implementation reflects the quality of governance and the level of stakeholder engagement. The results of implementation (outputs and outcomes) serve as indicators of governance effectiveness. Positive results can reinforce existing governance frameworks, while negative results may prompt a reevaluation of policies and stakeholder engagement strategies. Successful implementation of policies can also enhance stakeholder trust and engagement, leading to stronger collaboration in future governance processes. Identifying barriers and opportunities is crucial for understanding the practical challenges and possibilities within the governance framework. Addressing barriers and leveraging opportunities can lead to significant improvements in governance and policy implementation, reinforcing the interconnectivity of all elements in the framework.

2.10 Summary of Emerging Issues

This section has shown that policy instruments seem to complement each other. The weakness of one instrument, such as regulations, appears to be the strength of another. Therefore, to

develop a water policy that will achieve its objectives, there should be a policy mix of most, if not all, categories of policy tools. The caution here is that the instruments selected must be consistent with each other without conflicts. The choice of instruments should be based on political feasibility, technical feasibility, implementation capacity, the instrument, and the type of instrument. Generally, type, market-based instruments, voluntary instruments, and other kinds of policy tools complement the regulatory instruments used in the water sector. The State must always set the right legal and institutional framework, including regulations within which individual agents and firms operate. Thus, regulatory instruments are still necessary to maintain a minimum acceptable level of performance. Market-based instruments may offer benefits over other policy tools by providing incentives to change behaviour, establishing user priorities, and helping to raise revenue to support water resources management activities. However, they are unlikely to be effective working alone.

In designing effective and efficient water policies, governments must ensure that regulatory duties are stated, how decentralised regulation should be have been decided, the level of independence and discretion given to regulators have been specified, regulatory accountability and transparency have been ensured, and regulators can implement and monitor implementation. Each policy tool has weaknesses and can be effective given certain conditions. For example, command and control instruments can only be effective if the agency involved has enforcement capacity and the regulations are regarded by the regulated and the general public as necessary and appropriate. As a result, the selection, design, and implementation of instruments must be done through a careful analysis of a country's environmental, social and economic context. It must be rooted in the critical debate on their relevance, limitations, and potential interactions and conflicts with other forms of governmental action.

This chapter shows that using an integrated approach to water resources management includes a shift from supply-side water management to demand-side management. An outcome of implementing IWRM is the ability to manage the water demand. The demand-management approach emphasises strategies that ensure increased efficiency in water uses for domestic, agricultural, and industrial purposes and efficiency of water utilities. Such strategies require improved stakeholder participation, awareness-raising campaigns, and unprecedented levels of coordination with other institutions. Also, there is a need for strong political commitment, and trade-offs are required between different water uses. The demand-management approach

also emphasises decentralising water resource management decision-making to the basin or sub-basin/catchment level.

Encouraging citizen participation in development processes is crucial in upholding the principles of inclusivity and democracy. Arnstein's typology of citizen participation, which ranges from non-participation to citizen power, provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the diverse levels of involvement. The aim of citizen participation, as highlighted by Arnstein (1969) and Fagence (1977), is to be present and influence outcomes in collaboration with authorities and institutions. Fiorini's (1990) techniques for public participation in environmental issues, such as public hearings and surveys, provide practical avenues for involving citizens in decision-making related to the environment. This aligns with Simmons' (2007) assertion that true participation occurs when citizens' voices are heard and their views, interests, and concerns are considered, transforming them into decision-makers with real influence.

Looking beyond the citizen-centric perspective, stakeholder theory, as articulated by Freeman (1984), Donaldson & Preston (1995), Savage et al. (1991), and Mitchell et al. (1997), emphasises the need for organisations to consider the interests of all stakeholders in all the organisational decisions they make. The identification and classification of stakeholders based on attributes such as power, legitimacy, and urgency provide a strategic approach for organisations to navigate complex relationships and prioritise stakeholder engagement. The recognition of stakeholder salience as a function of these attributes underscores the dynamic nature of stakeholder relationships in strategic management.

2.10 Conclusion

In this section, I reviewed the literature on water governance and water policymaking and introduced the concepts of participation and stakeholder engagement. I also discussed the advantages and limitations of policy measures employed in water policymaking. Additionally, I explored the concept of IWRM. I examined the initiatives and policies developed by the African Union, the African Development Bank, and regional bodies such as ECOWAS and UEMOA to promote sustainable water resources management in Africa.

I presented the participation and stakeholder theories as valuable frameworks for creating more inclusive and effective decision-making processes. Both perspectives stress the importance of understanding and incorporating diverse voices to achieve meaningful and sustainable

outcomes. Finally the conceptual framework of this study was presented. The conceptual framework is essential for understanding how various factors interact to shape water governance in Ghana. It emphasises the importance of context, stakeholder engagement, and citizen involvement in ensuring effective management of water resources. By identifying barriers and opportunities, it provides a roadmap for improving water policy outcomes and achieving sustainable water governance.

CHAPTER THREE

WATER RESOURCES MANAGEMENT IN SELECTED AFRICAN STATES

3.1 Introduction

The concept of water governance has an international perspective, with international agreements that are accepted worldwide. Focusing on developing countries, I examine water governance in Ghana, Kenya, and Uganda. I look at the background of developing water policies in these countries, policy strengths, weaknesses, and policy implementation. On this basis, I compare water resources management in Ghana, Kenya, and Uganda.

Ghana, Uganda, and Kenya, the selected African nations, are notable for their unique characteristics, challenges, and efforts in water resources management, offering several advantages. These countries provide valuable insights into managing water resources within a developing context, emphasising diverse water resources, policy changes, and community involvement. Ghana and Kenya have achieved lower-middle-income status, while Uganda is progressing toward middle-income status, as acknowledged by the World Bank. As these nations make economic advancements, they face the dual challenge of sustaining effective water management while promoting economic growth. The management of water resources in these countries has greatly benefited from the assistance of two external organisations: DANIDA (Danish International Development Agency) and SIDA (Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency). These organisations have played a crucial role in offering technical knowledge, financial assistance, and capacity building, contributing to the establishment of resilient water management frameworks and practices.

The countries have various sources of freshwater, including rivers, lakes, and groundwater. However, Kenya has less annual freshwater than Ghana and Uganda (World Bank, 2019) and is below the UN's recommended threshold of 1000 m³ per capita per year. These nations share similar water challenges, such as pollution in river basins and variations in climate. All three countries have implemented reforms in the water sector and have made significant progress in establishing policy, legal, and institutional frameworks to support IWRM. Uganda and Kenya have emphasised the importance of involving local communities in making decisions about water resource management and have introduced innovative approaches, such as water user associations, as community-based organisations in water management (Nicol & Odinga, 2016; Richards, 2018). The utilisation of water user associations represents a shift of water resource management from a centralised to an example of how decentralised water resource

management can be more effective and sustainable than centralised systems. Ghana, Kenya, and Uganda have extensive experience with water reforms, providing valuable insights into applying IWRM principles and the potential for replicating successful strategies in similar developing world contexts.

3.2 Ghana

Ghana is located in the western part of Africa and has a population of approximately 31 million people (Ghana Statistical Service, 2021). The country's water resources consist of surface and groundwater sources. Major surface water sources include the Volta, Southwestern, and Coastal River systems. Urban areas primarily rely on surface water for domestic and industrial purposes, while rural areas mainly depend on groundwater sources (WRC, 2020). Water is used for domestic, industrial, irrigation, and livestock needs. Ghana had 1,113 m³ of renewable freshwater resources per capita in 2014, indicating a condition of water stress (World Bank, 2019). Despite the abundance of water resources, Ghana's available water is declining due to factors such as climate change, rapid population growth, increased environmental degradation, and river pollution, according to the EPA (2017).

Ghana's water sector has undergone several evaluations regarding its operations and the roles of different organisations since the early 1990s. With the enactment of the 1992 Constitution of Ghana, water resources were entrusted to the President on behalf of the people, effectively abolishing private ownership of water resources (Republic of Ghana, 1996). Agyenim and Gupta (2012) observed that the Community Water and Sanitation Programme-1 (CWSP-1) was introduced in 1991 by the World Bank as part of the restructuring of the water sector to manage water resources in rural Ghana. By 1993, the National Community Water and Sanitation Programme (NCWSP) was formulated and launched in 1994 as a component of the restructuring endeavours. The 1992 Constitution did not explicitly create a structure for overseeing and coordinating water resource policy but did establish the Lands, Minerals, and Fisheries Commissions to manage related resources such as land, fisheries, and forestry (Sarpong, 2008). The Water Resources Commission (WRC) was later formed by the Legislature under the Water Resources Commission Act 522 of 1996. The WRC's responsibilities include regulating and managing water resource utilization and coordinating related policies (Republic of Ghana, 1996). While the WRC exercises overall control over Ghana's water resources as a central government agency, it operates at the basin level through River Basin Boards with delegated management structures (Agyenim & Gupta, 2012). Prior to

the establishment of the WRC, water resources management functions and authority were fragmented across different ministries and commissions. Regulation of water resources management in Ghana has been carried out directly or indirectly through various enactments by different ministries, departments, and state agencies (MDAs) (Agyenim & Gupta, 2012). (see Table 3.1).

Table 3.1: Laws and policies guiding water resources management in Ghana

Date	Name of Law or Policy
1993	Ghana Water Company Limited; Act 461
1996	Water Resources Commission; Act 522
1998	Community Water and Sanitation Act; Act 564
2011	Community Water and Sanitation Regulation, LI 2007
1999	PURC; LI 165151
1999	Environmental Assessment Regulation; LI 1652
1999	Forestry Commission Act; Act 571
2001	Water Use Regulation Law; LI1692
2003	By-laws of WSDB and WATSANs
2005	CWSA Policy Guidelines
2006	Drilling Licence and Groundwater Development Regulations; LI 1827
2007	National Water Policy
2011	Riparian Buffer Zone Policy

Source: Agyenim & Gupta, 2012; Community Water and Sanitation Agency, 2014

Among the 13 enactments, five are administered by the Water Resources Commission and directly regulate water resources management: the Water Resources Commission Act 522, the Water Use Regulation Law (LI 1692), the Drilling Licence and Groundwater Development Regulations (LI 1827), the National Water Policy, and the Riparian Buffer Zone Policy.

Until 2007, Ghana did not have a comprehensive water policy that covered all aspects of water resources management. The Ghana National Water Policy was created in 2007 through an inclusive process involving consultations with stakeholders nationwide and collaboration between ministries. The Water Resources Commission (WRC) drafted the policy in 2002 under the then Ministry of Water Resources, Works and Housing. In 2004, creating the Water Directorate within the Ministry initiated a more extensive consultative process to update the policy. The development of this policy greatly benefited from technical assistance and funding from the Danish International Development Agency (DANIDA). The policy goal is “*to achieve sustainable development, management and use of Ghana’s water resources to improve health and livelihoods, reduce vulnerability while assuring good governance for present and future generations*” (Government of Ghana, 2007b, p. 13).

The National Water Policy starts by acknowledging the institutional, environmental, and social contexts in which it was developed (Government of Ghana, 2007b). Global and regional frameworks, such as the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and the 'Africa Water Vision' of the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD), provide support to this policy. It is also guided by principles outlined in the Constitution of Ghana. The goal of the policy is to assist the country in reducing poverty and achieving sustainable social and economic development, aligning with the Growth and Poverty Reduction Strategy (GPRS II), which serves as Ghana's framework for economic growth and poverty alleviation. The policy promotes holistic approaches to managing water resources by endorsing the IWRM concept, as suggested by the Water Resources Management Study (WARM) initiated by the Ghanaian government in early 1996. The Water Resources Management Study (WARM) recognised significant issues and challenges related to water resources. It suggested that Ghana should embrace an integrated, cross-sectoral method for managing water resources, using the river basin as the unit for planning and management (UNDP, 2004). The report describes the principles of IWRM, which to be employed to manage the nation's water resources. The policy recognises that water was previously perceived as limitless and easily accessible; however, due to population growth, urbanisation, and rapidly increasing and diverse needs, water is now becoming increasingly scarce and often of lower quality (Government of Ghana, 2007). Among the IWRM principles adopted were utilising the river basin (or sub-basin) as a planning unit, incorporating river basin management with coastal zone and wetlands management, and integrating gender equality approaches into IWRM.

Since it was put into effect, six (6) IWRM plans have been created for six different river basins. The Densu River Basin was selected as the first basin to test participation, strategies for public awareness, and water resources planning within a decentralised administrative framework. An IWRM Plan for the Densu River Basin, completed in mid-2007, now directs water resource management activities in the basin (Agyenim & Gupta, 2012). After this, IWRM plans for the Ankobra and White Volta basins were developed in 2008. In 2011, an IWRM plan was formulated for the Dayi River Basin. The fifth IWRM plan was established in 2012 for the Pra River Basin (Water Resources Commission, 2012). The Tano River Basin IWRM Plan, produced by the Water Resources Commission in October 2012, is the most recent and sixth of its kind (Water Resources Commission, 2012c). The 14 guiding principles in the National Water Policy focus on ten key areas. The importance of gender equality in Water Resources Management is underscored by the fourth principle, which emphasises improving equity and

gender sensitivity, while the other principles also contribute to this objective (Water Resources Commission, 2011). Gender mainstreaming is being implemented to integrate gender considerations into Ghana's water sector. The Water Resources Commission (WRC) has formulated a strategy to integrate gender in Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) in Ghana. The strategy recommends ensuring active participation of both men and women, with women not being perceived solely as passive recipients or a vulnerable group in IWRM (Water Resources Commission, 2012a). Climate variability and change are also key areas of focus in the policy. Goals related to climate change encompass reducing its impacts and putting in place measures to lessen the harm caused by floods and droughts. The strategies outlined to achieve these goals include regulatory and informational measures. The government is responsible for establishing and enforcing appropriate buffer zones along riverbanks and ensuring effective land-use planning and building regulations in waterways and flood-prone areas. The policy's emphasis on water access is in line with Sustainable Development Goal 6, specifically in terms of ensuring universal access to water.

The policy goal will be attained through various policy tools and measures. The regulatory tools mentioned in the policy include water quality standards, effluent standards, codes of practice for efficient water usage and cleaner production in industrial activities, specifications for the construction of boreholes and hand-dug wells, as well as standards for small towns. The economic principle of 'polluter pays' in the policy is noteworthy, as it is intended to act as a discouragement against the uncontrolled discharge of pollutants into the environment (Government of Ghana, 2007b).

Moreover, the policy describes additional economic tools, such as permits for water usage, permits for discharging wastewater, water tariffs, and fees. According to the policy, the tariffs are set to reflect the complete, efficient cost of water supply. Additionally, water fees will control water usage and cover the expenses of maintaining an effective system for IWRM activities. The policy stresses the importance of creating suitable institutional frameworks and developing capacity. The policy also encourages collaboration between the public and private sectors in the management of water resources. Regarding information and education, the policy supports the creation and dissemination of IWRM information to the public. It also advocates for the use of suitable technology to provide essential information for early warning systems for floods and drought, as well as for integrating IWRM into relevant curricula at all levels of the education system. The Government of Ghana will adopt a sector-wide (programme)

approach to implement the water policy through its various agencies. The Ministry of Water Resources, Works and Housing's Water Directorate will be in charge of creating the implementation plan for the entire policy. Additionally, sector agencies responsible for specific areas will formulate implementation strategies and plans to execute the relevant policy actions. The Ministry of Water Resources, Works and Housing is tasked with proposing appropriate legislation to support policy implementation. The key water sector agencies and their responsibilities are summarised in Table 3.2 below.

Table 3.2: Water sector institutions and their roles

Principal water sector institutions and their roles	
Agency	Roles
The Ministry of Water Resources, Works and Housing (MWRWH)- the principal water sector ministry	Responsible for formulating policies, planning, coordinating, collaborating, monitoring and evaluating programmes for water supply and sanitation.
The Water Directorate of the MWRWH	The focal point for organising the water and sanitation sector to align policies, oversee the progress of SDG targets, and coordinate international aid
The Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development and Environment	Responsible for managing and regulating solid and liquid wastes by local government bodies.
The District Assembly (DA)	In charge of organising, executing, and maintaining water and sanitation facilities, as well as overseeing communal infrastructure ownership in rural communities and small towns.
The Water Resources Commission	The focal point to promote cooperation and teamwork among different entities involved in managing water resources.
The Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL)	Overall responsibility: planning, managing, and implementing urban water supply.
The Community Water and Sanitation Agency (CWSA)	The main coordinator for providing water and sanitation services in rural areas and small towns.
The Ghana Irrigation Development Authority (GIDA)	Responsible for managing the nation's water resources to support irrigated agriculture and livestock watering, as well as facilitating fish farming in irrigation ponds and dams..
The Ministry of Fisheries	Oversees fishing and fish farming and enforces rules for both freshwater and ocean fishing.
The Ministry of Harbours and Railways	Oversees water transportation and navigation and governs operations in Ghana's inland and coastal areas.
The Ministry of Energy	Responsible for water usage for energy generation and governing the supply of hydroelectric power, including its distribution.
The Ministry of Health	Responsible for developing policies and carrying out its plans and initiatives through the Ghana Health Service (GHS).
Allied institutions in the water sector	

The Water Resources Information Services (WRIS) institutions i.e. the Water Research Institute under the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, Hydrological Services Department, and Ghana Meteorological Agency.	Provide information and services related to water resources and other data to assist with decision-making and planning.
The Public Utilities Regulatory Commission	Regulates the quality of services, such as the standard of drinking water provided by the GWCL, as well as the tariff established by the company for urban water supply.
Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)	Preservation of water sources and oversight of operations in watershed areas, such as establishing rules for wastewater discharge.
The Ghana Standards Board	Responsible for the development and establishment of drinking water quality standards, including certification and other associated applications.
Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority	Provides town layouts that define land use and directs the development of services like roads, drainage networks, electricity and water supply distribution lines.
The Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning	Manages all government water investments, which involves seeking grants and loans through negotiations.
The Ministry of Women and Children	Responsible for executing policies related to water that impact the welfare of women and children.
The Parliamentary Committee on Works and Housing and the Parliament of Ghana	Provides legislative oversight of the water sector.

Source: Government of Ghana, 2007b

The policy lacks one essential component, which is implementing Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) programs. These measures could have ensured the consistent availability of water for sustaining life and promoting health. Additionally, the absence of voluntary approaches in the policy is notable. Upon examining the policy document, I agree with Monney and Ocloo (2017) that the policy overlooks critical national issues, such as safeguarding water resources from potential oil spills resulting from oil exploration activities in the country's water sources.

Ghana has been implementing IWRM through water policy and IWRM plans for river basins. However, there have been some challenges. One of the main obstacles in Ghana's implementation of IWRM is the deficiency of skilled human resources at all levels. For instance, Agyenim & Gupta (2010) argue that decentralised water management units, like the District Assemblies, depend on regional or national offices for personnel (e.g. water engineers) to adequately assess and monitor water infrastructure development. Another challenge is the insufficient funding for water resources management. The centralisation of financial resources

affects the operations of decentralised units at the basin or local level. A report from the EU Water Initiative noted that Ghana's budgetary allocations to the Water Resources Commission have decreased over the years, falling from GHc 94,500 in 2007 to GHc 60,845 in 2009. It is particularly concerning that the actual disbursements were much lower than the budgeted amounts, amounting to only GHS 6,043.47 in 2007, GHS 7,935.88 in 2008, and GHS 1,996.86 in 2009. These disbursements represented only 6.4 percent of the allocation in 2007, 11.8 percent in 2008, and 3.3 percent in 2009.. (see Table 3.3).

Table 3.3: Budgetary allocations to WRC

Year	Budgetary allocation (GHc)	Actual release (GHc)	Percentage (%)
2007	94500.00	6043.47	6.4
2008	67437.00	7935.88	11.8
2009	60845.00	1996.86	3.3.

Source: EU Water Initiative – Finance Working Group (EUWI-FWG), 2012

Challenges that hinder the implementation of IWRM also include inadequate enforcement of current regulations and water permit conditions, insufficient monitoring of industrial and domestic effluent discharges, and the absence of regulations governing activities in river basins that contribute to catchment degradation and deteriorating water quality (Water Resources Commission, 2012). To address these issues, the WRC has been proactively dealing with the development of a plan to enact and enforce legislative measures related to the National Buffer Zone Policy and pollution control measures for effluent discharge in river basins (Water Resources Commission, 2022).

3.3 Kenya

Kenya faces water scarcity issues. In 2014, the renewable freshwater resources per capita were measured at 443 cubic metres, indicating absolute water scarcity (less than 500 m³ per year per capita) (World Bank, 2019). Surface water availability in Kenya fluctuates significantly over time and across regions. Though water resources are scarce, Huggins (2002) argues that these resources are increasingly used for domestic, industrial, and agricultural purposes.

In addition to water scarcity, Kenya's water resources face pollution, degradation, and overexploitation threats. In response to these challenges, the government introduced the 1999 National Policy on Water Resources Management and Development, which outlines principles for effective water resources management (Mogaka et al., 2006). Before 1999, Kenya's water management relied on approximately twenty-six different legislative pieces (Huggins, 2002).

The Sessional Paper Number 1 of 1999, known as the National Water Policy, was developed with funding from the Swedish International Development Agency (SIDA) and was approved by parliament in April 1999.

The water policy of Kenya starts by acknowledging the difficulties in the sector, such as insufficient funding for managing water resources, institutional deficiencies like a lack of qualified staff and skills for operating and maintaining water supplies, and unequal distribution of water over time and space, among other issues. The main objective of the policy is to realise sustainable development and administration of the water sector. It centers on four key areas: management of water resources, development of water supply and sanitation, institutional frameworks, and funding for the water sector. These areas are supported by four objectives outlined in the policy (Government of Kenya, 1999). The policy promotes integrated approaches to water resources management, emphasising adopting a river basin approach to manage water resources effectively.

After describing the four policy areas, the policy moves on to a plan of action that consists of policy statements or tasks, approaches, and specific timeframes for completion. As stated in the policy, this action plan underscores the importance of transferring decision-making authority in water resources management (Huggins, 2002). The execution of this plan began with the establishment and strengthening of government institutions responsible for water management at national, basin, and sub-basin/catchment levels, ensuring equal representation of genders across all levels.

Following the introduction of its initial water policy in 1999, Kenya underwent changes in its water sector in 2002, leading to the passing of the Kenyan Water Act (No. 8 of 2002). This law emphasised the principles of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) as the foundation of water governance. It separated water resources management from the provision of water services and established two separate public agencies. One of these agencies was responsible for regulating the management of water resources, while the other supervised the regulation of water supply and sewerage services. Creating the Water Resources Management Authority (WRMA) empowered it to oversee, regulate, and preserve all water resources, promote stakeholder participation, ensure fair water allocation, and promote environmental sustainability (Global Water Partnership, 2015).

According to the Water Act, the national government of Kenya retains the responsibility for water regulation and enforcement at the national level. Meanwhile, community-based organisations and private corporations are responsible for managing water resources and providing water services at the local level using participatory methods (Global Water Partnership, 2015). The Water Act (No. 8 of 2002) was revised to the Water Act (2016) (No. 43) following the adoption of Kenya's new constitution in 2010 (Global Water Partnership, 2015). Mumma (2007) noted that while the Water Act 2002 (No. 8) decentralised water functions to lower-level public institutions, it did not fully devolve these functions, as ultimate decisions continued to reside with the central government. The Water Act 2016 (No. 43) was introduced to align the previous Water Act (Water Act 2002) with the 2010 Constitution of Kenya, specifically aimed at achieving constitutional devolution (Gachenga, 2018). Kenya's 2010 constitution reorganised the country's political structure into two levels, consisting of a central national government and 47 decentralised county governments (Olendo, 2019).

Under the 2016 Water Act, county governments are mandated to deliver water and sanitation services and construct county water infrastructure. Simultaneously, the national government is responsible for safeguarding, preserving, and overseeing the use of water resources and managing national public water infrastructure that extends across counties (Water Integrity Network, 2017). The national government is also tasked with developing policies and regulations to protect water resources, with counties participating in enforcing these measures (Kibugi & Saltiel, 2013).

Gachenga (2018) points out a significant modification made by the 2010 constitution to the Water Act of Kenya. This change states that all of the country's resources, including water sources such as rivers, lakes, and other bodies of water, are now the property of the people of Kenya. In the previous Water Act (No. 8 of 2002), water resources were owned by the state, with allowances for other usage rights granted by law. However, the revised Water Act (No. 43 of 2016) specifies that while the state, particularly the national government, serves as the guardian of these resources, it holds them in trust for the benefit of the people of Kenya.

The policy implementation in Kenya started with the passing of a water act, and the creation of the National Water Master Plan 2030 (NWMP), which outlines the nation's strategy for water resource development and management from 2010 to 2030 (Kibiiy & Kosgei, 2018). One important action Kenya took to improve water resource management was separating this function from water service provision. Mumma (2007) highlights that this choice was made

because water supply had been receiving more attention and resources than water resource management at that time. Currently, different institutions are responsible for overseeing water resource management and water supply. The Water Act (2002) was replaced by the Water Act 2016 to better address present-day needs in Kenya. These efforts collectively aim to advance sustainable water resource management through an integrated approach. A major challenge facing water resource management in Kenya is the inadequate funding allocated to the sector. This financial limitation hinders the adoption of water management practices to address the impact of climate change. Hirji (2000) emphasises that the financial support for catchment board activities is weak, leading to slow and sometimes distorted decision-making processes. Insufficient financial resources also contribute to inadequate monitoring of water resources, which in turn impedes effective planning and management efforts, including those related to transboundary waters.

Furthermore, weak monitoring and enforcement of water abstraction regulations, compounded by inadequate funding for conservation measures, have led to a gradual decline in both the quality and quantity of water from its sources (Hirji, 2000). Additional challenges in efficient water resources management include conflicts and competition among various water users and communities. For instance, in the Tana River Basin, conflicts periodically arise between competing upstream activities, such as irrigation and hydropower and downstream uses, like irrigation and livestock watering (Chepyegon & Kamiya, 2018). According to Hirji (2000), weak water apportionment, allocation, and enforcement practices significantly contribute to these conflicts.

3.4 Uganda

Uganda, located in East Africa, has remarkable water assets, including Lake Victoria, the largest lake in Africa and the second-largest freshwater body in the world. Lake Victoria is also the origin of the Nile River, the longest river globally (Pedersen, 2016). The country's water sources encompass rivers like the Nile River, Katonga, and Semliki, all located within the Nile Basin, which contributes to Uganda's wealth of water resources (Nicol & Odinga, 2016). Despite this abundance, Uganda experiences variations in water availability based on both seasons and locations.

Like many African nations, Uganda faces mounting pressure on its water resources due to rapid population growth, improved living standards, increased agricultural output, urbanisation,

industrialisation, and the impacts of climate change. These factors collectively contribute to the accelerated depletion and degradation of water resources (Nsubuga et al., 2014; Global Water Partnership, 2013). Certain regions of Uganda experience water scarcity during specific periods of the year, while others contend with excess water.

Freshwater for drinking in Uganda primarily comes from groundwater sources, which are perceived as less vulnerable to pollution compared to surface water (Sasakova et al., 2018). According to Nsubuga et al. (2014), approximately 61 percent of Uganda's water is sourced from groundwater, accessed through springs and boreholes located around Lake Victoria and southwestern Uganda.

Since the 1990s, Uganda has received substantial aid, including support from DANIDA, following the 1992 Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro, which facilitated initiating IWRM initiatives (Nicol & Odinga, 2016). Before formulating a national water policy in 1999, Uganda had already begun managing its water resources comprehensively. The Department of Water Resources in Uganda embarked on the path towards IWRM in 1993 (Rethink et al., 2016). During this period, civil unrest disrupted the country's water monitoring and information systems, and institutional capacity was weak, with underdeveloped water policies and legislation (Nicol & Odinga, 2016).

The implementation of IWRM in Uganda commenced with the creation of a Water Action Plan in 1995, outlining the necessary resources, such as a water policy, legislative frameworks, institutional capacity building, and management tools (Ministry of Water, Lands and Environment, 1999). Uganda's national water policy utilises several key policy tools, including regulatory measures such as drinking water quality standards and allocating water rights to districts. Economic incentives are crucial and include water tariffs, charges for waste discharge and effluent, fees for water abstraction permits, and government subsidies provided to many water suppliers. Regarding education and information, the government aims to enhance public awareness by gathering data on water resources and distributing it to various stakeholders and the general public (Ministry of Water, Lands and Environment, 1999).

After more than two decades of implementing Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM), Uganda actively participates in joint decisions with other countries concerning the sustainable development of the Nile River waters. The country has established consistent policies and legislation that provide guidance and regulations on water use, allocation,

wastewater discharge, stakeholder participation, and decentralisation, ensuring local engagement in water resources management (Jønch-Clausen, 2004).

Uganda's water resources department has evolved into the Directorate of Water Resources Management, tasked with integrated and sustainable management and development of Uganda's water resources. Its mandate is to ensure sufficient quantity and quality of water to meet current and future social and economic needs (Ministry of Water and Environment, 2020). Notwithstanding the long-standing implementation of IWRM in Uganda, several challenges persist. These include inadequate funding and prioritisation of the water resources management sector, lack of consistent political support at all levels, insufficient compliance and enforcement of water permit regulations, heavy reliance on donor funding, and limitations in human resources capacity (numbers, skills, focus, experience, attitude, and knowledge) (Ministry of Water and Environment, 2013).

The Ministry of Water and Environment notes that water resources management often receives lower budget allocations compared to infrastructure-focused water supply projects, which yield more immediate and tangible results. Moreover, certain water laws and regulations are viewed in some regions as hindering economic growth, complicating their enforcement. Additionally, competition among different water users for access to the same water sources, such as rivers or streams, adds to the complexities of water management (Rubarenzya, 2008).

3.5 Key Points from water resources management in Ghana, Kenya, and Uganda

Kenya and Uganda, neighbouring countries in East Africa, appear to be more advanced than Ghana in establishing a legal and policy framework for Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM). According to a report from the Global Water Partnership in 2015, Kenya's Water Act (No. 8 of 2002) served as a model for developing water regulations in the newly independent state of South Sudan. A comparison of Ghana's water policy with those of Kenya and Uganda reveals that donor agencies, such as SIDA and DANIDA, played crucial roles by providing technical and financial support throughout the policy formulation processes.

Prior to adopting comprehensive frameworks to guide the water sector development in Ghana, Kenya, and Uganda, none of these countries had a single ministry or department solely responsible for water management; instead, water resource management responsibilities were fragmented among various sectoral agencies. However, all three countries have clearly

articulated policy objectives, focus areas, principles, and recommendations aimed at enhancing water resources management.

The water policies adopted in Kenya, Uganda, and Ghana advocate for decentralising decision-making processes in water resources management. In Ghana, decision-making is decentralised to the basin level, while in Kenya and Uganda, it extends to the sub-basin/catchment level. Unlike Ghana, Kenya and Uganda have comprehensive legislation in the form of water acts that support the implementation of their national water policies. Kenya, in particular, revised its Water Act to align with the 2010 constitution, replacing the Water Act 2002 (No. 8) with the new Water Act 2016 (No. 43) enacted in 2016 (Government of Kenya, 2017).

In contrast, Ghana does not have a single comprehensive water act but rather different legislation governing the water sector. The Ministry of Sanitation and Water Resources in Ghana is expected to propose appropriate legislation as needed to support policy implementation. Establishing a clear legal and regulatory framework in Ghana is crucial to effectively implement policy objectives and actions. Such a framework could encompass legislation on technical standards, codes of practice, and equipment inspection and define the mandates of relevant water and water-related sector institutions. Therefore, having a unified water act would be beneficial for Ghana.

An examination of the water policies in these nations also highlights the influence of their respective constitutions. Specifically, the constitutions of Ghana, Kenya, and Uganda recognize access to clean and safe water as a fundamental human right, with the state obligated to ensure its fulfilment. The water policies of these countries reflect a clear alignment with their constitutional provisions.

One notable observation is that Ghana's water policy currently lacks an action plan. In contrast, Kenya has integrated its water action plan with its policy document, and Uganda developed its action plan prior to finalizing its water policy. Ghana's existing national water policy can be seen more as a visionary statement, lacking a detailed roadmap for achieving its goals, which may limit its practical implementation potential. Advocacy groups, such as the Delegation of German Industry and Commerce in Ghana (AHK Ghana), have emphasised the need for Ghana to develop a clear and defined action plan to effectively support the implementation of its water policy (Ghana News Agency, 2018).

It is important to note that while these countries have supportive policy frameworks in place, implementing them effectively at all levels remains a significant challenge. Issues such as governance challenges, limited financial commitments from both public and private sectors, and a shortage of qualified technical personnel at various levels continue to hinder the successful implementation of water policy frameworks and effective water resources management across Sub-Saharan Africa (Global Water Partnership, 2015).

3.4 Conclusion

We see in this chapter that developing countries such as Ghana, Kenya, and Uganda, though they have diverse water resources, seem to be experiencing similar challenges in the water sector, such as pollution and climate change. These countries have created an enabling environment that constitutes policies, plans and legislation for sustainable water resources management. When these countries adopted IWRM, it was clear that water policies in Kenya and Uganda had supporting pieces of legislation and action plans that facilitated the implementation of the policies. Kenya and Uganda have developed a comprehensive legal and policy framework to support IWRM. Aside from its considerable history and international acceptance, IWRM provides a promising approach to water resources management. However, there are some challenges to implementing IWRM. Countries such as Kenya and Uganda still face major challenges in its implementation, though they have been implementing IWRM principles for more than two decades.

The literature has documented that donor influence can direct the decisions or priorities of national policymakers (Okuonzi & Macrae, 1995; Koeberle, 2003; Rutkowski, 2007). For low- and middle-income countries, there are implications of receiving donor support from governments, multilateral agencies, and private agencies for policy development. As has been identified in the preceding sections, countries like Ghana, Kenya, and Uganda heavily depend on donor funding for IWRM activities. Agyenim and Gupta (2012) argue that this has led to policy prescriptive approaches that do not consider the existing political structure, the nature of the social and economic problems, the available resources in the country, or existing stakeholder perceptions. This, in turn, has impacted the relevance and ownership of and commitment to the concept of IWRM and serves as a challenge to implementing IWRM successfully.

ⁱ (i.e. Water Use Regulation LI 1692, Water Resources Commission Act 522, Drilling license and groundwater regulations)

CHAPTER FOUR

METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the research design adopted and justifies the methods used to explore stakeholder constraints to effective basin water governance. Utilising a qualitative research methodology, the four research questions of this study were addressed. Qualitative research, according to Bryman (2016), emphasises understanding human behaviour and values in terms of the specific environment in which they operate. This approach is well-suited for exploring issues, such as stakeholder dynamics and water governance, in-depth. The cross-case study design was adopted to identify the key stakeholders and their interests in decision-making, to understand how stakeholder dynamics impact water resources management, and to explore barriers and opportunities in effective management in the Densu and Pra River basins. The inclusivity of the cross-case study design was beneficial and allowed for a broader understanding of stakeholder involvement and the diversity of stakeholder interests across the Densu and Pra River basins. To capture the complexity of the research questions, a variety of data collection tools were employed, including semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, document analysis and observation. The study utilised the snowball and purposive sampling methods. The snowball sampling method was initially used to identify all relevant stakeholders involved in managing the Densu and Pra River basins, ensuring that all perspectives were considered. Due to the country's multilevel governance character of water resources management, interviewees were selected at national, regional and local levels of governance. Purposive sampling was also employed to select interview participants to ensure diversity in roles, interests, and experiences related to water resources management and decision-making in the Densu and Pra River basins. Thematic analysis was employed to examine the gathered data to discern recurring themes and correlations that effectively address the research questions. The information provided consists of narratives centring on the meanings, perspectives, events and experiences of individuals involved in the policy sectors of water resource management and environment. These individuals include officials from state agencies, departments, local government authorities, the private sector, leaders of civil society

organisations, and traditional leaders. Data were also obtained from focus group discussions with major water users in the two river basins. The list of participating institutions and departments is itemised in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: List of participating institutions

	Densu Basin	Pra Basin
National level	Water Resources Commission Fisheries Commission Energy Commission	
Regional level	Ghana Water Company Limited Community Water and Sanitation Agency Environmental Protection Agency Densu River Basin Secretariat	Ghana Water Company Limited Environmental Protection Agency Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority Pra River Basin Secretariat
Local level	-Abuakwa South Municipal Assembly -Nsawam-Adoagyiri Municipal Assembly -Ayensuano District Assembly -Weija-Gbawe Municipal Assembly -Water and Sanitation Department, Ga-West Municipal Assembly -Department of Agriculture, Abuakwa South Municipal Assembly -Nsawam-Adoagyiri Headworks of the Ghana Water Company Limited -New Juaben South Municipal Assembly -New Juaben North Municipal Assembly -Kyebebi water Treatment Plant	-Environmental Health Department, Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly -Bosomtwe District Assembly -Shama District Assembly -Twifo Atti Morkwa District Assembly -Upper Denkyira East Municipal Assembly -Obuasi Municipal Assembly -Atwima Nwabiagya North District Assembly -Asante Akyem Central Municipal Assembly -Kwaebibirem Municipal Assembly -Denkyembour District Assembly
Non-Governmental Organisations	-4-H Ghana -AROCHA Ghana	Friends of River and Water Bodies
Private sector	SIRCOOL Water Bottling Company	Special Ice Company Limited

Traditional Authority	Effiduase Traditional Council Adoagyiri Traditional Council Akwadum Traditional Council	Adum Traditional Council Presentease Traditional Council
Other	Assemblymember of Kyebi Elder of Koforidua Effiduase	Member of Pra basin board

Source: Densu Field Data Collection, December 2021
Pra Field Data Collection, December 2022

This chapter is structured as follows: The forthcoming sections will cover the rationale for emphasising the significance of water resource management at the basin level, the justification for choosing the Densu and Pra River basins, a description of the two study areas, the research philosophy, the approach to cross-case study analysis, the data sources, the method of data analysis, the communities where focus group discussions were conducted, and the conclusion of the chapter.

4.2 River Basin Planning

River basins remain relevant as geographical units for water resources management and studies into integrated water resources management. The concept of river basin has become more widespread with the concept of Integrated Water Resources Development (IWRM). Beginning from the 1992 Dublin conference to the United Nations Conference in Rio de Janeiro, it has been advocated that water resources should be managed at the basin or sub-basin level. Countries' commitment to implementing the principles of IWRM has been to adopt the river basin as the management unit to plan for sustainable utilisation, conservation and protection of water resources. The study focused on river basins because they present a good context for understanding water governance better, as they are the natural unit for managing a river and its tributaries. In Ghana, the national water policy clearly states that the river basin should be used as the planning unit for water resources management in the country. The Ghana National Water Policy thereby defines a river basin as 'the land area drained by a river and its tributaries or the land area surrounding one river from its headwaters to its mouth' (Government of Ghana, 2007).

Figure 4.1: River Basins in Ghana

Source: Namara et al., 2011

From Figure 4.1, Ghana is drained by three main river basin systems, namely the Volta, Southwestern, and Coastal River systems. The Volta River system is made up of the White Volta, Black Volta, the Oti and Lower Volta. This river system drains about 70 per cent of the country's total land area of 240,000 km². The Southwestern River system consists of the Tano, Bia, Ankobra, and Pra Rivers, covering 22 percent of the country's land size. The Coastal river system is made up of the Densu, Ayensu, Ochi-Nakwa, Ochi Amissah, and Tordzie rivers and extends over eight percent of Ghana's total land area (Namara et al., 2011).

4.3 Rationale for Selecting the Densu and Pra River Basins

The Densu and Pra rivers and their tributaries are of immense economic importance to Ghana, as they contribute significantly to the livelihoods of basin dwellers through mining, irrigated agriculture, drinking water production, and other industrial activities. However, the current state of these rivers is a cause for concern. The Water Resources Commission has identified the selected basins as among the priority river basins that require IWRM plans and effective river basin boards to ensure better water management. The Commission's 2019 report highlights the importance of these measures in addressing the water management challenges faced by these basins and ensuring the sustainability of water resources for the future.

The Pra and Densu basins in Ghana have been chosen as focal points for study due to their concerning levels of water pollution. A report from the USAID/Sustainable Water Partnership in 2021 highlighted that these basins currently exhibit the highest rates of surface water pollution in the country. Additionally, these areas face numerous challenges related to water resource management, including small-scale and illegal mining (galamsey), deforestation, unsustainable farming practices, and indiscriminate disposal of waste into the rivers. Consequently, water quality in these basins has markedly deteriorated, resulting in insufficient water supply to meet demand and a shift in the demand for water from surface water to groundwater (USAID/Sustainable Water Partnership in 2021; EPA, 2017; Duncan et al., 2019).

Figure 4.2 Densu and Pra basins in national context

Source: Derived from SRTM Data, 2020

4.4 Study Areas

4.4.1 Densu basin

The Densu basin is part of Ghana's coastal river system and can be found in the southeastern region of the country. The basin spans an area of around 2600 square kilometres and is situated between longitudes 10°30'W - 10°45'W and latitudes 50°45'N - 60°15'N. The Densu basin runs through three regions: the Central, Eastern and Greater Accra Regions. The Eastern Region covers about 72 percent of the basin, while the Greater Accra Region and the Central Region make up 23 percent and five percent, respectively. The basin is home to 23 administrative districts, with nine of them - Abuakwa South, New Juabeng North, New Juaben South, Suhum Municipal, Ayensuano, Akwapim South, Ga West, Weija-Gbawe and Ga North - occupying almost 85 percent of the basin (WRC, 2007). About 300 settlements are located in the Basin (Ofosu et al., 2020)

The basin is primarily characterised by agricultural activities, which are the main source of income for the rural communities. These activities include crop cultivation and livestock rearing. Fishing is also practised in some sections of the basin, contributing to the livelihoods of communities along the riverbanks. Urban areas in the basin have a more diversified economy, with wholesale and retail trading, manufacturing, and other commercial activities being the prominent occupations (Oti et al., 2020). It is worth noting that rural communities around the river rely heavily on its water for drinking and other domestic purposes. However, it is concerning to know that the water is used without any treatment, which poses a potential health risk to the people (Duncan et al., 2019). The Densu River is supported by major tributaries, including Adeiso, Suhyen, Doboro, Nsaki, and Kua. These major tributaries run through densely populated areas, forests, and areas with intense industrial and farming activities. This makes it crucial to manage the river and its tributaries carefully to prevent contamination of the water and protect the health of the people who depend on it (Amoako et al., 2010).

The Densu River originates from the Atewa Mountain Range near Kyebi, in the Eastern region of the country. It flows for about 120 kilometres, passing through the Weija reservoir before reaching the sea through the Densu Delta Ramsar Site (Paintsil, 2010). The river is a crucial water source for the Weija reservoir, supplying drinking water to more than four million people residing in the Greater Accra, Central, and Eastern regions of Ghana (Koranteng, 2015). The Densu River is a lifeline for the people living in the Accra metropolitan area, which is the capital of Ghana. The river supplies drinking water to about 47 percent of the population in the area and treated water to the industrial and commercial hub (Duncan et al., 2019).

The Densu Basin supports the Densu Delta, a significant Ramsar Site. Being a Ramsar Site, the Densu Delta holds global importance. It provides habitat for a diverse range of plant and animal species, many of which may be rare, endangered, or endemic to the area. Wetlands like the Densu Delta also offer valuable ecosystem services, such as flood control, water purification, and carbon sequestration, benefiting wildlife and humans. The Densu River is a crucial resource supporting a variety of domestic and commercial activities and preserving biodiversity and ecosystem services within the basin. Its reliable water supply is essential for households, agriculture, industry, and commerce, playing a pivotal role in sustaining and enhancing the economic vitality of the basin, and ensuring the well-being and livelihoods of local communities. However, the Densu Basin faces challenges in managing its water resources

due to urbanisation and developmental activities, especially in areas near Accra, the capital city of Ghana. The basin is experiencing rapid urban growth, industrialisation, sand mining, stone quarrying, and excessive agrochemical use, which contribute to problems such as pollution, encroachment, waste management, and increased demand for water resources.

Figure 4.3 Map showing administrative districts of the Densu basin

Source: Ghana Statistical Service, 2021

4.4.2 Pra Basin

The Pra basin is the largest river basin among the four southwestern basin systems in Ghana, namely Ankobra, Tano, Bia and Pra. It covers an area of about 23,200 square kilometres, with its boundaries lying between latitudes 4°58' N and 7°11' N, and longitudes 0°25' W and 2°13' W. The basin flows through the regions of Ashanti, Eastern, Central, Western, and Western

North in Ghana, making it an essential water resource for these areas (Water Resources Commission 2012b). The Pra River, which is the primary river within the basin, takes its source from the highlands of the Kwahu Plateau in the Eastern region and flows for some 240km southwards before entering the Gulf of Guinea at Shama (Water Resources Commission, 2012b). The Pra River is formed by the convergence of several tributaries, such as the Anum, Birim, Offin, and Oda rivers. The Pra basin has around 1300 settlements, making it the basin with the highest settlement density in the country, according to Bessah et al. (2020). Additionally, the basin is home to Lake Bosomtwe, the only significant natural freshwater lake in Ghana and a popular tourist site.

The Pra River Basin is home to a variety of different land covers, including forests, grasslands, and agricultural lands. This diverse ecosystem supports a wide range of flora and fauna, contributing significantly to the country's biodiversity (Water Resources Commission, 2012b). The fertile lands in the basin are essential for agriculture, enabling the cultivation of crops such as cocoa, oil palm, rubber, maize, and cassava, which are crucial for the country's food security. Agriculture is a significant economic activity for communities in this region, and many of the towns in the basin are also known for their mining activities. Agriculture and mining have been the two primary competing land uses in the area, with large-scale mining companies such as AngloGold Ashanti in Obuasi, Newmont Ghana Gold Limited in New Abirem, and Perseus Mining in Ayanfuri. Additionally, many small-scale mining companies and illegal artisanal mining operations can be found throughout the basin. Nearly the entire Pra basin is known to be an active artisanal mining area.

The Pra Basin provides water supply to three regional capitals - Cape Coast, Sekondi, and Kumasi - and other densely populated urban areas such as Takoradi, 73 districts (see Figure 4.4), and over 1300 towns (Bessah et al., 2020). Managed by the Ghana Irrigation Development Authority (GIDA), the Pra Basin has three formal irrigation schemes - the Nobewam (Anum Valley-Bottom) Irrigation Project, Adiembra Irrigation Project, and Gyadam Irrigation Project - which aim to provide efficient irrigation to crops and ensure farmers have access to necessary water resources (Water Resources Commission, 2012b). Unfortunately, the basin faces challenges of water scarcity and pollution due to mining, farming, and deforestation activities.

Figure 4.4 Map showing administrative districts of the Pra basin

Source: Ghana Statistical Service, 2021

4.5 Research philosophy

The philosophical position of this research is inclined towards the interpretivist philosophy. This is due to the social nature of this research, which studies institutions and people engaged in water governance at the river basin level. Interpretive research philosophy focuses on

understanding and interpreting human behaviour, experiences, and social phenomena within specific contexts. It emphasises the subjective nature of reality and the importance of understanding human experiences and meanings (Creswell, 2014; Bryman, 2016; Hammersley, 2013). It stands in contrast to positivism, which focuses on objective, measurable phenomena. Ontologically, this study proceeded with the notion that there are multiple realities shaped by social, political, cultural, and economic values. This view is important to water governance and sustainable basin water management in the Densu and Pra basins because these concepts are social constructs that involve people's actions within a given political, socio-economic, and cultural context. Since people's experiences shape knowledge, the study was conducted in the participants' natural environments, where they live and work. These real-life settings are essential for understanding their perspectives and providing deeper insights into their experiences. This approach aligns with the researcher's epistemology, emphasising that knowledge is context-dependent and best understood through direct interaction with participants in their everyday surroundings. The general position of this study is that though bias is typically seen as undesirable in social science research, it is inevitable. This research is value-laden; therefore, the narratives presented are shaped not only by the participants' experiences but also by the researcher's interpretations. Consequently, the findings reflect a blend of the researcher's perspectives and the subjects of the study.

The following outlines the key aspects of adopting an interpretive research philosophy. Firstly, the study aims to understand better the subjective experiences, perceptions, and interpretations of stakeholders involved in water governance in the Densu and Pra River Basins. This involves investigating how various actors, such as government agencies, local communities, NGOs, and industries, view and interpret water resource management issues. Secondly, the study focuses on comprehending the intricacies of water governance within Ghana's specific socio-cultural, economic, political, and environmental contexts, notably within the Densu and Pra River Basins. The aim is to reveal the cultural, political, and institutional factors that affect water resource management practices and the contextual nuances that shape decision-making and practices in managing water resources within Ghana's Densu and Pra River Basins. Thirdly, the research aims to develop a thorough understanding of the tensions and challenges within water governance systems in the Densu and Pra River Basins. This encompasses examining multiple perspectives, conflicting interests, and the roles and relationships of diverse stakeholders, which are detailed in chapters four, five, and six. Lastly, interpretive research typically employs qualitative methods such as interviews, focus groups, and document analysis, which are

explained in the next sections. These methods allowed the researcher to delve deeply into the lived experiences, perspectives, and interactions of stakeholders involved in water governance, providing rich, context-specific data.

4.6 Qualitative research approach

The features of this study were following the qualitative research approach (Creswell, 2013). Its focus was concise, and the scope was narrowed to Ghana's Densu and Pra river basins. The study employed semi-structured interview guides to collect data, allowing for a flexible yet focused approach to gathering information from participants (Bryman, 2012). This method provided a balance between structured questions that ensured key topics related to stakeholder roles in water governance were covered while also allowing the researcher the flexibility to explore emerging themes and insights during the conversation. The semi-structured format enabled participants to express their perspectives in their own words, encouraging deeper exploration of complex political and social issues. Validation was achieved through the use of multiple data sources and methods to provide corroborating evidence (Creswell, 2013). Also, through peer debriefing by engaging with other researchers and experts (as the CREAM Project provided the opportunity) to review and discuss the research process and findings, helping to identify potential biases and refine interpretations. According to Creswell (2013), reliability refers to how consistently different people code the same data. Reliability in this study was ensured by maintaining detailed field notes throughout the data collection process and using high-quality voice recorders to capture interviews and discussions accurately. The recordings were carefully transcribed to preserve the authenticity of participants' responses, ensuring consistency and precision in the data analysis.

4.7 Cross-case study design

The water resources management systems and decision-making dynamics of Ghana's Densu and Pra River basins were analysed using a cross-case study approach. This approach helped to understand the complexities of water resources management and governance by examining similarities, differences, patterns, and variations across both basins. Firstly, the cross-case approach helped to draw meaningful comparisons from the two cases experiencing similar events (Yin, 2014). The Densu and Pra River basins are both treated as priority river basins in Ghana, with the oldest basin boards established to support IWRM. This shows a substantial amount of experience in how stakeholders are contributing to sustainable water resource management. Both basins face environmental challenges such as small-scale mining,

deforestation, and waste disposal into rivers, which have led to deteriorating water quality and a shift in water demand from surface to groundwater. However, there are notable differences between the Densu and Pra basins in terms of size, location, and settlement density.

Secondly, the cross-case study approach was chosen for its compatibility with other case study methodologies, enabling data collection from various sources within each case, as Yin (2009) highlighted. These sources include interviews, focus groups, official reports, policy documents, and field observations. This comprehensive data-gathering strategy facilitated a nuanced exploration of diverse facets of water governance in the Densu and Pra basins. Stakeholder perspectives, policies, practices, challenges, and successes within each basin were thoroughly examined. The study compared two basins, exploring various factors affecting water governance complexity. This comparative analysis revealed intricate interactions and how different contextual factors impact decision-making processes.

Thirdly, the cross-case approach involves the examination of multiple cases (Yin, 2014), exemplified by the exploration of the Densu and Pra River basins, to amass a broader spectrum of data for a more exhaustive analysis. Employing this methodology facilitated the collection of diverse data, encompassing stakeholder perspectives, policy implementation, contextual factors, and outcomes pertinent to governance structures, stakeholder participation, resource allocation, environmental conservation efforts, and the influence of socio-economic factors on water resources management. By scrutinising multiple cases, the study could extract nuanced insights and connections, contributing to a more holistic comprehension of the dynamics surrounding water resource management and governance complexities.

Lastly, by conducting a comparative analysis, conclusions were drawn regarding the barriers and opportunities inherent in water resources management and governance. The study identified key factors that contribute to ineffective water resource management strategies, as well as successful practices. Based on the findings, the study provides recommendations for improving governance in both basins. Although the focus was on these specific river basins, the cross-case approach used in the research allows for insights that may apply to similar contexts or cases beyond the ones specifically studied, such as other river basins within Ghana.

4.8 Data collection tools

The study utilised three primary data-collection instruments: interviews, focus group discussions and observation.

In-depth interviews were conducted with 41 key informants and stakeholders actively involved in water resources management within Ghana's Densu and Pra River basins. To gain broader insights, an additional three interviews were carried out at the national level. The distribution of interviews included 22 in the Densu basin and 19 in the Pra basin, strategically capturing region-specific insights.

The national-level interviews provided a comprehensive perspective on water management policies and strategies at the national scale. The selection criteria for interviews focused on identifying organisations with a vested interest in utilising the basin's water resources and ecosystem services.

A reconnaissance survey was conducted employing the snowball sampling method to map key stakeholders influencing decision-making processes at both the basin and national levels. The selection process continued until all key actors were identified and met the predetermined criteria.

For the actual study, key actors who were interviewed were purposively chosen based on their roles or mandates, expertise, influence, and involvement in decision-making processes related to water governance. This encompassed governmental bodies, regulatory agencies, local government authorities, traditional leaders, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and industries.

To secure participation, identified actors were contacted and briefed on the research's purpose and significance. Stakeholders' offices served as convenient and confidential locations for conducting scheduled in-depth interviews (see plates 1-4). The interviews aimed to gain insights into policies, regulations, power structures, stakeholder interactions, conflicts of interest, resource allocations, and strategies in the governance and management of the basins' water and associated ecosystem services.

The stakeholders were categorised into five groups: water managers (WRC and River Basin Secretariat), governmental organisations, non-governmental organisations, traditional authorities, and the agriculture office. Different semi-structured interview guides tailored to each group were used to collect information on topics such as water policy awareness, stakeholder interests, attitude towards water resources management, participation in river basin management, factors influencing stakeholder support, and opportunities for improving water governance. The research questions served as the foundation for developing the interview

guides for data collection. By aligning the interview guides with the research questions, it was ensured that the data collected directly addressed the key aspects of stakeholder interests, dynamics, barriers, opportunities, and participation in water resources management in the Densu and Pra River basins.

To prepare for the interviews, policy documents and reports related to water resources management in Ghana were reviewed. This analysis helped identify themes specific to policy design and implementation, which informed the development of interview guides for engaging key informants and stakeholders.

Data was triangulated from multiple sources through multiple data collection methods, including interviews, focus group discussions, participant observations, and document analysis, to help corroborate the research findings and enhance the reliability of the study.

Plate 1: Meeting with officials of EPA

Plate 2: Meeting with Upper Denkyira East Municipal Assembly

Plate 3: Meeting with officials of Obuasi Municipal Assembly Plate 4: Meeting with Officials of CWSA

Source: Densu Field Data Collection, December 2021
 Pra Field Data Collection, December 2022

In addition to interviews, focus group discussions were held with water users to elicit diverse perspectives, experiences, and recommendations related to water governance. Through the Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies, Assembly members were contacted to help organise a group of about ten water users from communities in the Densu and Pra river basins. This included farmers, fishermen and fishmongers, community representatives, and other stakeholders directly reliant on the basins' water resources.

4.8.1 Focus group discussions in the Densu basin

In the Densu basin, focus group discussions were held with two farmer groups from the Ayensuano district. Each group consisted of 10 people. The focus groups were organised in the Coaltar community. Ayensuano district was selected because it is relatively rural and predominantly agrarian since the majority of its labour force is in the agricultural sector. Moreover, the Ayensuano district is drained by the Densu and Kua rivers. Farmers in the district were quite organised; therefore, it was envisioned that it would not take a long time to arrange them for a discussion. The Coaltar community, in particular, has the Kua River running through it and is used by farmers for irrigation of their crops, especially vegetables. Though five municipalities were visited during the data collection in the Densu basin, and the plan was to organise a focus group discussion in each district, it became clear during the data collection

process that it would be difficult to achieve this goal because of the delay of the contact persons to organise the groups; therefore, two focus group discussions were organised instead of five.

4.8.2 Focus group discussions in the Pra basin

In the Pra basin, more focus group discussions were organised. Lessons were learnt from the difficulty in organising focus groups in the Densu basin, and this informed a revised strategy for getting more focus group discussions organised going forward into the Pra basin. Focus group discussion was held in each district and municipality visited except the Denkyembaour district. In all, eight focus groups were organised in the Pra basin. The communities that were chosen for the focus group discussions were carefully selected based on some criteria. In particular, it was ensured that these communities were representative of the broader population in terms of demographics, socioeconomic status, and cultural backgrounds. Additionally, the significance of these communities in the context of water governance, such as their proximity to water sources or their relationship with water management, was also considered. By choosing communities that met these criteria, the research ensured that the focus group discussions provided a comprehensive and insightful perspective on water governance issues.

During the data collection process, a separate semi-structured interview guide was used for the community focus group. The interview guide was designed to collect information on knowledge of water policy instruments, perceptions of water quality, challenges of water quality, governance issues, and suggestions for improvement. The focus group discussions were held in a neutral environment that was conducive to open conversation (see plates 5-8), ensuring that all participants felt comfortable and encouraged to share their views. Every participant was given an equal opportunity to express their opinions, experiences, and concerns regarding water resources management in the Densu and Pra River basins. Gender representation was taken into consideration during the organisation of the focus groups. While the initial plan was to have an equal representation of men and women, it was ensured that women made up at least 25 percent of the focus group.

Plate 5: Focus group discussion with water users at Coaltar

Plate 6: Focus group discussion with water users at Amakye-Bare

Plate 7: Focus group discussion with water users at Abono

Plate 8: Focus group discussion with water users at Bankyease

Source: Densu Field Data Collection, December 2021
Pra Field Data Collection, December 2022

Table 4.2: List of community focus groups organised

Densu Basin		Pra Basin	
Community	District/Municipality	Community	District/Municipality
Coaltar	Ayensuano District	Abono	Bosomtwe District
		Bedieso	Obuasi Municipal
		Nyaboo	Asante Akyem Central Municipal
		Amakye-Bare	Atwima Nwabiagya North District
		Okyinso	Kwaebibirem Municipal
		Presentease	Upper Denkyira East Municipal
		Bankyease	Twifo Atti Morkwa District
		Kumunamu	Shama District

Source: Densu Field Data Collection, December 2021
Pra Field Data Collection, December 2022

Throughout the interviews and focus groups, a combination of notetaking and voice recording was employed to document participants' responses. To ensure the utmost respect for the participants' privacy, the researcher obtained their consent before using the voice recorder. Notetaking and the voice recorder were both used to ensure that no detail was overlooked and that all narratives were accurately represented. Throughout the process, the stakeholders' responses were documented, key themes were identified, and significant insights recorded. This approach ensured that the information gathered was exhaustive, well-rounded and captured the essence of the discussions accurately.

Observation was also a valuable data collection tool employed in this study. It was used to note visible signs of water pollution, deforestation and other environmental factors impacting water resources in the Densu and Pra basins. Through observation, how decision-making processes unfolded during basin board meetings related to water resource management was also documented. Physical infrastructure, such as dams and water treatment plants in the two basins, were also observed to assess their condition and functionality during the study.

4.8 Data analysis

All of the data was analysed using the NVivo 12 software. The analysis involved a thematic analysis of the responses, which were initially divided into two cases - the responses from actors in the Densu basin and the responses from actors in the Pra basin. All of the recordings were transcribed, and the interviews and focus group discussion transcripts were imported into the NVivo software. Prior to coding the data, the content was thoroughly reviewed through repeated readings of the transcripts and notes to ensure a comprehensive understanding.

The data was coded separately for the Densu and Pra basins, and codes were developed to represent themes relevant to water governance in each data set. A combination of deductive predefined themes based on the topics in the interview guides and an inductive coding approach (emerging themes from the data) were identified and used. For instance, themes such as 'behaviour of people and companies' and 'Atewa forest and government' emerged from the data.

During the analysis, participants' perspectives, opinions, and experiences from focus groups were compared and contrasted. The shared agreements reached by the groups during their discussions were recognised while giving particular attention to the contributions made by individual participants to these common agreements. The data collected from interviews and focus groups were integrated and analysed for each basin.

After the analysis, conclusions were drawn based on the findings, which provided valuable information to enhance decision-making and inform future actions.

4.9 Study limitations

It is worth mentioning that the study faced some limitations, although these were overcome, and they did not affect the reliability of the data and the findings. It was difficult to conduct interviews with all the relevant stakeholders in water resources management in the Densu and Pra River Basins. These stakeholders include Ministries at the national level, as well as other agencies like the Forestry Commission and the Minerals Commission. The main challenges encountered were bureaucratic hurdles and the limited time and personnel available, which restricted the capacity to conduct interviews with the extensive range of stakeholders. Additionally, some stakeholders were located far apart, making it difficult to reach them within the given timeframe. It is important to note that if all relevant stakeholders were interviewed, the study findings would have represented a complete view of the water governance landscape

in the Densu and Pra River Basins. However, since some stakeholders were excluded, there is a possibility that critical insights from the excluded stakeholders were lost. Nonetheless, the study utilised additional document analysis to gather perspectives from stakeholders who could not be interviewed directly.

It should be noted that only two out of five planned community focus group discussions were held in the Densu basin. This is due to practical constraints and difficulties in engaging with water users at the local level. The time for organising focus group discussions in all intended communities was limited for Assembly members to organise the people. When some of the groups were finally organised for discussion, the researcher had already left that part of the basin. This may have resulted in an incomplete representation of local community perspectives on the part of the Densu basin, as different communities have diverse experiences, challenges, and opinions that may not have been fully captured. However, to supplement the insights obtained from the limited focus group discussions, a thorough analysis of the data collected from the conducted focus group discussions and individual interviews was performed.

The study had a limitation in focusing solely on the interactions between the basin office and other stakeholders while ignoring the interactions between the various stakeholders, which could have provided additional insight into the dynamics of the stakeholders. Due to the large number and diversity of stakeholders involved in water governance, a more targeted approach was necessary, which led to the selection of the basin office and other stakeholders for in-depth analysis. Moreover, analysing the interactions among all stakeholders identified in the study would have resulted in a vast amount of data, making it difficult to manage and interpret the data. By limiting the study to the interaction between the basin office and other stakeholders, the findings may provide a narrow view of stakeholder dynamics in water governance. This may limit the understanding of collaborative efforts, conflicts, and power dynamics that exist within the broader network of actors involved in water resources management. Nevertheless, the study still provides valuable insights by offering a thorough understanding of the dynamics between the selected stakeholders, with the understanding that stakeholder engagement in water governance is a multifaceted and interconnected process involving various actors.

4.10 Conclusion

This study follows a qualitative approach that emphasises a detailed in-depth exploration of the complexities inherent in water governance. By adopting an interpretive perspective, the study aimed to uncover the perceptions and lived experiences of stakeholders involved in water resources governance and a cross-section of water users in the selected basins. To capture the diversity of experiences and practices in the Densu and Pra River Basins, this study employed a cross-case study approach. This allowed for the identification of commonalities and differences in water governance, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of water resource management in the two river basins. Through a multi-faceted approach, including focus group discussions, interviews, document analysis, and observation, this study triangulated findings to enhance the reliability and validity of the research outcomes. The involvement of various stakeholders ensured a holistic perspective on water governance complexities. Thematic analysis was employed to uncover patterns, themes, and emergent insights from the rich qualitative data. Overall, this study provides a nuanced and comprehensive understanding of water governance complexities in the Densu and Pra River Basins, offering valuable insights that can inform effective water management strategies across different contexts.

CHAPTER FIVE

DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES, ACTORS, THEIR INTERESTS AND PRIORITIES

5.1 Introduction

The study of water resources management in the Densu and Pra River basins builds on three main elements, namely (i) the key actors involved in decision-making, (ii) their interests and motivations, and (iii) the factors that influence their decision-making. Analysing the interaction between these three elements reveals how water resources management decisions matter for different actors. It also shows the relative importance of factors influencing decision-making and how the actors overcome barriers to effective water resources management in the Densu and Pra River basins.

This chapter concentrates on the first two elements of the framework. For each basin, I describe the decision-making process, stakeholders involved in decision-making, the interests and motivations of stakeholders, and the selection of stakeholders in the basins for decision-making. The objective here is to show the current decision-making framework for both the Densu and Pra River basins, to identify stakeholders who are part of the decision-making process and those who may be relevant but are not involved in making decisions in the Densu and Pra River basins. This addresses the first research objective, which is to identify the decision-making process and the key stakeholders involved in the decision-making process in the Densu and Pra River basins.

The chapter is organised in a cross-case fashion as follows: data is analysed on the basins, in turn, the Densu basin and then the Pra basin, apart from a summary of interview questions and responses. For both of the basins, I describe (a) the nature and scope of decision-making, (b) the decision-making process, (c) key stakeholders involved in decision-making, (d) the interests and motivations of stakeholders, (e) stakeholders not involved in decision-making, and (f) the selection of stakeholders for decision-making.

Table 5.1: Summary of interview questions and responses under decision-making process, actors and interests

Theme	Questions	Responses
Nature of decision-making; Decision-making process	How are decisions made regarding water resources management in the basin?	Decisions are made by the basin board (instituted by the WRC) during quarterly meetings. The secretariat proposes a date, checks the availability of members, and confirms the meeting. Meetings are held at the Densu Basin office or conference centre for the Pra Basin. Plans are agreed upon during meetings especially the IWRM plan.
	How are meetings arranged?	Meetings are scheduled when a quorum (10 or more members) is reached. Invitations are sent via call, email, and WhatsApp.
	What is the typical structure of a meeting?	Proceedings include an attendance sheet, prayer, self-introduction, agenda review, validation of previous minutes, presentation of activity progress reports, and discussions.
Stakeholders involved in decision-making	Who participates in decision-making processes?	Decision-making is handled by the basin board, composed of 18 members from WRC, District Assemblies, government agencies, NGOs, Regional Coordinating Council, traditional authorities, and the basin officer.
Stakeholders not involved	What are the bottlenecks in the decision-making process?	Irregular meetings due to funding challenges, COVID-19, and availability of board members. Virtual meetings face challenges with

		computers and internet access.
	How can bottlenecks be overcome?	Increase IGF, seek donor support, and engage more stakeholders, especially NGOs working in environmental sectors.
Stakeholder interests and motivation	What are stakeholders' interests in the river basin?	<p>The basin board oversees decisions on water resource protection, conservation, and use, while also contributing to IWRM plan formulation, led by the WRC.</p> <p>Interests are shaped by mandates and objectives, e.g., the Bosomtwe District Assembly focuses on Lake Bosomtwe due to its tourist value and revenue generation potential.</p>
	Who participates in meetings, and how are they invited?	Board members are invited through calls, emails, and WhatsApp messages. A dedicated WhatsApp platform is used for board members.
	Who leads the meetings?	The chairperson of the basin management board leads and moderates the meetings.
Stakeholder conflicts	How are conflicts resolved?	Disagreements are prolonged until a consensus is reached; no significant conflicts have been reported.
Stakeholders' selection process	How are stakeholders selected?	Key District Assemblies are selected based on specific features; stakeholder composition follows the basin IWRM plan.
Scope of decision-making	Do decisions cover the entire basin?	Decisions made by the Densu Secretariat and Board also cover Ayensu and Birim Basins. The Pra Basin board

		only covers the upper part, ending at Dunkwa-On-Offin.
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Source: Densu Field Data Collection, December 2021
Pra Field Data Collection, December 2022

5.2 The nature of decision-making

Interviews with the WRC, basin secretariats and some members of the basin boards revealed that decision-making by stakeholders was in two spheres, covering IWRM planning and then the practical part of water resources management, namely the protection, conservation and utilisation of water resources in the basin. The data collected revealed no significant difference between the Densu and the Pra River basins regarding the nature of decision-making. Decisions are made by the Densu and Pra basin boards, like most state agencies. In the Densu and Pra basins, decision-making processes regarding water resources management are carried out in a participatory manner, where stakeholders are not just consulted, but their opinions and concerns are actively considered. This approach is consistent with the Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) framework adopted by the country's Water Resources Commission (WRC). Additionally, it aligns with principle 10 of the OECD's principles on good water governance. The IWRM framework and the OECD water governance principles highlight the significance of involving stakeholders in decision-making processes to ensure the sustainable management of water resources. The WRC oversees stakeholder engagements to ensure effective, equitable, and efficient management of water resources while considering stakeholder needs. Through this participatory approach, the WRC promotes a collaborative and inclusive decision-making process that not only fosters transparency, accountability, and trust among stakeholders, but also empowers them to be an integral part of the decision-making process.

This stakeholder consultation is in the form of a meeting with members of the basin board to deliberate on issues of concern. Board meetings are scheduled with an agenda that usually matches the functions of the board, the basin IWRM Plan, matters arising from the previous meeting minutes, and the progress of planned activities of the basin office. The media's coverage of water-related issues in the basin, findings from monitoring activities, and complaints received by the basin office, along with the influence of the basin board chairperson, play crucial roles in determining which topics receive more attention and make it onto the agenda. The meeting agenda is prepared by the basin officer, who is also secretary to the basin board and made known to board members before the meeting. It is important to note that board

meetings are not scheduled until the availability of at least all board members is confirmed.

The Pra basin officer commented on the organisation of board meetings. She indicated that:

“We have 18 board members, and we hold meetings outside the office at a hotel conference centre. We incur costs for sitting allowance, travel and transportation, and lunch. We only schedule meetings when almost all board members can attend” (Pra Basin Officer, December 2022).

Interviews with some members of the Densu Basin Board also alluded to this statement made by the Pra Basin officer. A member of the board stated that:

“For the Densu basin, board meetings are held at the office premises of the Secretariat. At the end of each meeting, some allowance is paid which covers the sitting and travel and transportation (T&T)” (Densu basin board member, December 2021).

Discussions with some board members, corroborated by observation during one of the Densu Basin’s board meetings, revealed that the board chairperson usually chairs the board meetings. For each item on the agenda, there is a round of discussions where members' inputs are solicited, different courses of action are suggested, and members agree on the best course of action. When disagreements arise, time and effort are dedicated to the dissenting party to express their viewpoints and engage in constructive dialogue with the other stakeholders to clarify and elaborate on the matter to reach an agreement. The discussion is focused on common ground, where most board members share agreements to help solidify consensus and provide a clear foundation upon which decisions can be based. Decisions of the board are made collectively, and all members are allowed to express their opinions without inhibitions. Where the board lacks adequate information, certain board members are tasked to secure information from relevant sources to update the board. During meetings, board members are reminded of their commitments and duties to the board, such as the importance of the basin board in securing and protecting water resources in the catchment area and ensuring improved sanitation in the basin so that the river Densu or Pra and their tributaries can continue to serve the needs of present and future generations. Decision-making often results from the influence of technical considerations and cultural, political and economic factors. Decisions are finally made to reflect the mandate of the Densu or Pra Basin board and that of the Water Resources Commission.

The Densu Basin Board comprises four standing sub-committees, while the Pra Basin Board has two. Both boards have the authority to create ad-hoc committees to address specific issues

and implement decisions. These committees can co-opt other organisations when necessary and follow specific guidelines while performing their duties. They report to the board during their meetings. During each board meeting, the members receive a report on the current state of affairs of the basin. This report is known as the ‘activities progress report’, which covers the basin secretariat's work in implementing the annual plan and proposals suggested by the basin board.

Between the Densu and Pra basins, the Pra basin secretariat incurs higher costs for organising board meetings because they must rent a venue to host the board. In contrast, the Densu basin conducts its meetings at the basin office premises, eliminating the need for additional rental expenses. Consequently, the basin officers from the Pra basin have expressed their agreement that they would prefer not to incur these costs if all members cannot attend the meetings. This situation highlights the financial burden faced by the Pra Basin secretariat and underscores the importance of ensuring full participation from board members to make the best use of resources.

5.3 The decision-making process

The formal decision-making process in the Densu and Pra River basins follows a similar pattern. This is because, in both basins, the process is led by and involves almost the same institutions. Following its mandate, the Water Resources Commission created the river basin boards and the basin secretariats as decentralised committees of the WRC. The Densu and Pra River basin boards operate with the same guidelines provided by the WRC. The decision-making process highlighting the institutional setting in which the process takes place is depicted in Figure 5.1. The findings suggest that Ghana’s approach to IWRM has been to first build the institutional capacity to carry out water resources management based on the river basin unit by establishing the board and basin secretariat. Subsequently, an enabling environment is created that includes plans to implement the principles of IWRM.

Figure 5.1: The decision-making framework for the Densu and Pra River Basins

Source: Author's construct, 2023, based on Winter 2012

From Figure 5.1, the decision-making process in the Densu and Pra basins begins with preparing an Integrated Water Resources Management Plan (IWRM) for each basin. This plan is developed to align the basin's water management practices with the national water policy and the national Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) plan. The water policy and national IWRM plan are broader frameworks that provide a structured approach to decision-making at the basin level. According to the WRC and basin officials, in addition to integrated

water resources management planning, the River Basin Board (RBB) also makes decisions on practical aspects of water resources management, which involves the protection, conservation and utilisation of water resources. These decisions are often based on monitoring activities by the secretariat or stakeholder complaints in the basin.

According to officials from the WRC and basin secretariats, the WRC is the primary body responsible for developing the river basin IWRM plan, and it does so with active involvement and participation from the Densu and Pra River basin boards. It is important to note that forming the basin board and establishing basin secretariats is an integral part of the WRC's more extensive IWRM planning process. It occurs before the preparation of the basin IWRM plans to ensure that the interests of all stakeholders are represented. Findings from discussions with the WRC and basin officers, which were corroborated by the relevant stakeholders, were that, in addition to the basin board and WRC, other stakeholders are also invited to participate in the decision-making process. These stakeholders include representatives from District Assemblies and government departments not part of the basin board, water user organisations associated with prominent NGOs, and private consultants. Following the river basin IWRM plans, annual plans are prepared by the basin secretariat, which are then discussed and approved by the basin boards. The Densu and Pra basin boards also prepare budgets for each financial year to cover the programmes and activities of the board and the secretariat, which are contained in the annual plan. The plans and budgets are submitted to the WRC for approval to be part of the consolidated national annual work plan and budget. In addition to the annual plans, the basin boards make decisions based on monitoring activities and requests from interest groups. Another responsibility of the basin board is to keep track of the various activities and initiatives implemented to manage the water resources in the Basin. The board then reports its findings to the WRC, which helps review the Basin IWRM plan. It is important to note that the plan is supposed to be reviewed every five years. For the Densu and Pra basins, the basin secretariat executes the annual plan by engaging other organisations/bodies with the regulatory, management, and coordination actions outlined in the plan. The various organisations that aid in executing the plans of the basin boards are described as follows:

Regulation: Water-related regulatory and information/data institutions include the Environmental Protection Agency, Forestry Commission, Minerals Commission, Fisheries Commission, Hydrological Services Department, CSIR-Water Research Institute, and Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority.

Management – Ministries such as the Ministry of Food and Agriculture, Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection, Metropolitan, Municipal, and District Assemblies (MMDAs), major water users – Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL), Community Water and Sanitation Agency (CWSA), and Ghana Irrigation Development Authority (GIDA), and small water user groups.

Coordination: Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), Civil Society Organisations (CSOs), Traditional Authorities, MMDAs.

The RBB is expected to meet quarterly to discuss implementation progress. The Board also advises the WRC on matters likely to impact the basin's water resources.

5.4 Stakeholders involved in decision-making

According to the study's findings, the decisions made in water resources management significantly impact virtually everyone, as water is an essential resource for daily life. The Water Resources Commission acknowledges the challenges of ensuring the inclusion of all stakeholders during the decision-making process, given time and resource constraints. As a result, specific individuals and institutions have been selected to participate in the Densu and Pra basin boards, focusing on traditional actors at the basin level, following the National water resources management structure. The Densu and Pra basin boards consist of members from the Water Resources Commission, regional-level government departments, ministries and agencies, Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies, statutory bodies, Non-Governmental Organisations, and traditional authorities.

5.4.1 Composition of the Densu Basin Board

1. Basin board chairperson appointed by the WRC
2. A representative of the WRC
3. The Densu Basin Officer
4. One person representing each of the following institutions within the basin:

Local Government Authorities (from Greater Accra and Eastern Regions)

- Ga South Municipal Assembly, Ngleshie-Amanfro, Accra
- Ga West Municipal Assembly, Amasaman, Accra
- Suhum Municipal Assembly, Suhum
- Abuakwa South Municipal Assembly, Kyebi
- Nsawam-Adoagyiri Municipal Assembly, Nsawam

- New Juaben South Municipal Assembly, Koforidua

Ministries, Departments and Agencies

- Environmental Protection Agency, Eastern Region
- Forestry Services Division, Forestry Commission, Eastern Region
- Ministry of Food and Agriculture
- Ministry of Health, Eastern Region
- Ghana Water Company Limited Head Office
- National Commission on Culture, Eastern Region
- Department of Gender, Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection, Eastern Region

Statutory organ of government

- Eastern Regional Coordinating Council

Others

- Earth Service/GAPVOD
- Akyem Abuakwa Traditional Council, Kyebi

Similar to the Densu basin, stakeholders involved in decision-making in the Pra basin are the 18 basin board members from six local government authorities, representatives from Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs), the Ashanti Regional Co-ordinating Council, Non-governmental Organisation, and the traditional authority.

5.4.2 Composition of the Pra Basin Board

1. Basin board chairperson appointed by the WRC
2. A representative of the WRC
3. The Pra basin officer
4. One person representing each of the following institutions within the basin:

Local Government Authorities (from Ashanti and Central regions)

- Asante Akim South Municipal Assembly, Juaso
- Obuasi Municipal Assembly, Obuasi
- Atwima Nwabiagya North District Assembly, Barekese
- Bosomtwe District Assembly, Kuntense
- Upper Denkyira East Municipal Assembly, Dunkwa-On-Offin

- Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly, Kumasi

Ministries, Departments and Agencies

- Minerals Commission, Ashanti Region
- Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority, Ashanti Region
- Environmental Protection Agency, Ashanti Region
- Ghana Water Company Limited, Ashanti Region
- Forestry Commission, Ashanti Region
- Ministry of Food and Agriculture, Ashanti Region
- Department of Gender, Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection, Ashanti Region

Statutory organ of government

- Ashanti Regional Co-ordinating Council

Others

- Friends of Rivers and Water Bodies, Kumasi
- Kumasi Traditional Council, Kumasi

Like the Densu Basin, the Pra River Basin Board primarily consists of stakeholders from governmental organisations. However, the Pra board includes the Minerals Commission and the Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority, in addition to the ministries, departments, and agencies represented on the Densu Basin Board. The Pra board lacks representation from the Ministry of Health and the National Commission on Culture. Another difference is that while all local government authorities on the Densu Basin Board are Municipal Assemblies, the Pra Basin Board includes representatives from Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies to cover all levels of local authorities. The Water Resources Commission (WRC) emphasises that each basin board is specifically designed to reflect the unique and diverse characteristics of the particular basin it governs. Therefore, it is common to observe variations in the institutions represented on each basin board. In other words, the composition of each basin board is based on the specific needs, challenges, and opportunities of the basin.

5.5 Interests and motivations of stakeholders

5.5.1 The Densu basin

The decision-making process in the Densu basin involves various stakeholders with diverse interests driven by their respective mandates concerning water resources. This section discusses each stakeholder's interests, priorities, and unique features in the Densu basin. Additionally, these stakeholders' relationship with the Water Resources Commission is analysed. The interests of these stakeholders are a crucial reason for their selection to be part of the decision-making body of the basin.

5.5.1.1 Municipal Assemblies

Ga South Municipal Assembly

WRC documents reveal that the Ga South Municipal Assembly is one of the 23 administrative districts in the Densu basin (see Figure 4.3). Located in the Greater Accra Region of Ghana, its capital is Ngleshie-Amanfro. Legislative Instrument 2316 established the Assembly in 2018 after it was carved out of the former Ga South Municipal Assembly (Weija-Gbawe) (Ga South Municipal Assembly, 2019). Before the division in 2018, the former Ga South Municipal Assembly included both the current Ga South Municipality (Ngleshie-Amanfro) and Weija-Gbawe Municipality.

Ga South Municipal Assembly is responsible for the municipality's overall development. Its goal is to improve the quality of life for its citizens through the equitable delivery of services, which include environmental management, water conservation, waste management, and environmental health monitoring.

The Assembly identifies the Densu and Ponpon rivers as the municipality's main water resources. The Densu River, dammed at Weija, provides raw water to the Weija water treatment plant, which serves urban areas within the municipality. Parts of the municipality also fall within the Densu Delta and Ramsar site, which significantly impact residents' livelihoods. The Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation (2020) notes that fishing in the

Weija Dam/Densu River is a key economic activity, alongside oyster harvesting by women in some communities within the delta.

Ga West Municipal Assembly

The Ga West Municipal Assembly was established in 2008 by Legislative Instrument 2313. Before this, the municipality was part of the Ga District, created in 1988 as part of the government's decentralisation policy. Ga West Municipal Assembly officers explained that 2004 the Ga District was divided into Ga East and Ga West Districts. In 2008, the western part of the Ga West District was used to form the Ga South Municipality, while the remaining area was upgraded to municipal status, becoming the Ga West Municipal Assembly.

The Ga West Municipal Assembly focuses on improving the well-being of its residents by efficiently allocating resources to deliver high-quality socio-economic services. The Densu and Nsaki rivers primarily drain the municipality, with the Adeiso, Doblo, and Ntafrafra rivers serving as tributaries of the Municipal officials revealed that the Ga West area is located near the Weija and Nsawam Water Treatment Plants, both of which draw water from the Densu River. Most urban households in the municipality rely on the Densu River for potable water supplied by the Ghana Water Company Limited. Additionally, some residents depend on the river for livelihoods, such as artisanal fishing and flood-recession agriculture during the dry season.

Abuakwa South Municipal Assembly

The Abuakwa South Municipal Assembly, formerly known as the East Akim Municipal Assembly, was established as a District Assembly in 1988 by Legislative Instrument (LI) 1420, with Kyebi as its capital. According to officers of the Assembly, in 2008, it was elevated to municipal status under LI 1878. In 2018, after the creation of the Abuakwa North Municipal Assembly, its name was changed to Abuakwa South Municipal Assembly under LI 2304. The municipality is located in the Eastern Region of Ghana.

Abuakwa South lies within the Atewa forest, which is known for its rich biodiversity and as the watershed for three major rivers: the Densu (116 km), Birim (175 km), and Ayensu (103 km) (ASMA, 2021). The municipality is also rich in mineral resources, including gold, diamond, bauxite, and kaolin. Municipal officials report that bauxite deposits have been discovered in the Atewa forest, and the government has plans for their exploitation. The Assembly is responsible for the development of the municipality through the provision of services and the management of resources such as water, land, forests, and minerals. It operates under the Local Governance Act 2016 (Act 936) and the National Development Planning (System) Regulation, 2016 LI 2232, which mandate it to prepare and implement development plans for the overall growth of the municipality.

Suhum Municipal Assembly

The Suhum Municipal Assembly, located in the Eastern Region of Ghana with Suhum as its capital, was established in July 2012 by Legislative Instrument (LI) 2048. It was part of the former Suhum/Kraboah/Coaltar District, created in 1988 until the southern portion was separated to form the Ayensuano District in June 2012. That same year, Suhum Municipal Assembly was elevated to municipal status (Ghana Statistical Service, 2014).

The Densu River is the primary water resource that drains the municipality, with the Kua River serving as a major tributary. Farmers use small-scale irrigation systems, drawing water from the Densu with pumps to irrigate their crops. In addition to crop irrigation, the Densu River supports aquaculture activities in the municipality. Suhum is also a significant groundwater site in the Densu basin. Duah et al. (2021) highlight that the Suhum municipality hosts the largest groundwater-based pipe-borne water supply system in the basin, the Suhum water supply system, which provides potable water to Suhum and surrounding communities.

Plate 9: Suhum groundwater-based water supply system

Source: Blessedfieldltd.com

Nsawam-Adoagyiri Municipal Assembly

Nsawam Adoagyiri Municipal Assembly, one of the 23 administrative districts in the Densu basin, was established in 2012 by Legislative Instrument (LI) 2047, according to data from the Ghana Statistical Service. It was originally part of the larger Akuapim South Municipality, created in 1988. In 2012, the Akuapim South Municipality was divided to form the new Akwapim South Municipality and Nsawam-Adoagyiri Municipality, with Nsawam as the capital.

Under the Local Governance Act 2016 (Act 936), the Nsawam-Adoagyiri Municipal Assembly is responsible for developing, improving, and managing human settlements and the physical environment within its boundaries. The Assembly implements programs to protect water resources and wetlands, including raising awareness in communities near waterbodies about proper waste disposal.

The municipality is drained by the Densu River and its tributaries, including the Ntua, Pompon, Ahumfra, and Dobro rivers. Discussions with the traditional authority and the Nsawam-Adoagyiri Headworks of GWCL revealed that some communities use small-scale irrigation schemes that draw water from the Densu River for vegetable farming, especially during the dry season. The Densu River is also the primary source of potable water for the municipality, supplying the Nsawam water treatment plant, which provides water to residents. Additionally, the Municipal Assembly sees tourism potential in the Densu River, which it hopes to develop in the future

New Juaben South Municipal Assembly

The New Juaben South Municipal Assembly, the oldest district in Ghana's Eastern Region, was established in 1988 under Legislative Instrument 1426. Initially known as the New Juaben Municipal Assembly, it was divided in 2017 to form the New Juaben North Municipal Assembly. This restructuring led to its current name, with Koforidua serving as the capital.

A key natural resource in the municipality is the Densu River, which plays a crucial role in local water supply. Along with its tributaries—Nsukwao, Obopakko, Bompom, and Afena—the Densu provides water for treatment and distribution to urban and surrounding areas. The river is dammed at Densuagya, where water is treated and supplied to residents, as noted by Assembly officials

During an interview, officers from the New Juaben South Municipal Assembly stated that they have implemented by-laws to improve environmental sanitation and protect water resources. These by-laws specifically prohibit dumping waste into water bodies to prevent pollution.

Figure 5.5 below illustrates the specific geographical locations of the six Municipal Assemblies that form part of the Densu basin board.

Figure 5.5 Municipal Assemblies on the Densu basin board

Source: Derived from SRTM data and Ghana Statistical Service 2021

5.5.1.2 Ministries, Departments and Agencies

Environmental Protection Agency

Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) is one of the agencies under the Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation. Regarding the environment, it is the foremost public agency for protecting and improving the environment in Ghana. According to officials of the EPA, the EPA ensures a healthy environment by ensuring that the air, land and water are well taken care of. For water resources, the EPA works with the Water Resources Commission to ensure pollution control and effluent control into water bodies. According to the discussions held with officials from the EPA and corroborated by the WRC, the EPA establishes effluent quality guidelines specific to each sector for discharging wastewater into natural water bodies. This means that the EPA sets the standards for industrial wastewater discharge into surface waters, such as the Densu River. Officials of the EPA further added that,

through the Environmental Assessment Regulations of 1999 (L.I. 1652), the EPA defines procedures for obtaining environmental permits for development projects that may have adverse effects on the environment including water resources. Again, through LI 1652, the EPA provides guidelines for assessing the impact of development projects on the environment, including water resources, known as the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA). The EPA has regional and area offices across the country in some selected towns. In line with the Environmental Protection Agency Act of 1994 (Act 490), the EPA performs regulatory and enforcement roles (EPA, 2021). Through the enforcement powers given to the EPA by Act 490, the agency is enabled to identify any activity that impacts negatively on land, water and air, notify the person perpetuating such activity or act, direct the person to take the action needed to stop the wrongful act within a specified period. If the person fails, the EPA takes legal action or ensures the arrest of the person. According to interviews with top officials, until 2016, the EPA relied on state funding. In 2016, it became an autonomous public body after being weaned off government subvention.

Forestry Commission of Ghana

The Forestry Commission of Ghana, established by Act 571 in 1999, regulates the use of all forest and wildlife resources. It manages forest areas like the Atewa Forest, the source of the Densu River. Both the Commission and non-governmental organisations, such as A Rocha Ghana, have been advocating for the Atewa Forest Reserve to be upgraded to a national park and tourist destination. This is because of its rich biodiversity, including flora and fauna with medicinal properties, as well as its vital water resources.

Discussions with the Densu Secretariat and Board revealed that the Forestry Commission manages the Densu Delta and its wetlands, which originate from the Densu River. The Densu Delta, designated as a Ramsar site in 1992, is recognised as an area of international importance under the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands, which Ghana ratified in 1988 (PAC, 2010). The Commission actively engages in planting and replanting mangroves in the Densu Delta, as mangroves have been found to strengthen coastlines against climate change impacts.

The Ministry of Food and Agriculture oversees sustainable agriculture and enhances agricultural practices in the Densu Basin. Agriculture, the most significant land use in the basin, plays a major role in the local economy, employing many residents (Ofosu et al., 2020). Local farmers rely on the Densu River and its tributaries for crop irrigation, while communities near the river practice flood-recession agriculture.

Officials from the Department of Agriculture in Abuakwa South Municipality explained that the Ministry supports responsible water management. Agricultural extension officers actively educate farmers on sustainable practices that protect water bodies, such as promoting continuous land use and discouraging illegal mining that could pollute water sources. The Ministry operates through decentralised regional and district directorates, working together to achieve these goals.

The Ministry of Health improves the health of all people in the country, focusing on the well-being of human capital, from farmers to fishermen, under the slogan ‘creating wealth through health’. It ensures the health of communities in the Densu Basin, particularly those who depend on the river and its tributaries, by preventing water resources from negatively impacting public health. Through regional and local offices, the Ministry, along with its partners, implements government policies that promote healthy living and vitality (Ministry of Health, 2023).

GHANA WATER COMPANY LIMITED

Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL) used to be known as Ghana Water and Sewerage Corporation until July 1999, when it was converted into a limited liability company owned by

the State. Ghana Water Company Limited oversees the country's urban water supply. Discussions with the Nsawam and Kyebi headworks of the GWCL revealed that the Company abstracts groundwater and also water from rivers and streams, treats the water, and distributes the treated water to citizens who are customers. The Ashanti regional office of the GWCL confirms that the GWCL ensures that the water supplied to customers is safe for different uses. Their responsibility is particularly toward drinking water and its safety. The Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL) manages several water treatment plants in the country, including the Weija water treatment plant. This treatment plant was the first constructed in Ghana in 1914 and is a significant raw water source for the GWCL. The Weija treatment plant has the largest water treatment capacity in the Densu basin, which the GWCL uses to supply safe drinking water to the western part of the Greater Accra region and some parts of the Central region of Ghana. Additionally, other water treatment plants managed by the GWCL take raw water from the Densu, Birim, Offin, and Pra rivers.

The National Commission on Culture, an agency under the Ministry of Tourism, Arts, and Culture, manages Ghana's cultural life (NCC, 2023). The Commission operates regional centres and district offices in all Metropolitan, Municipal, and District Assemblies. Recognising the vital role of culture in developing Ghana's human capital, the National Commission on Culture aims to ensure that the behaviour of Ghanaians aligns with the country's traditions. Reports from the Commission and interviews with board members of the Densu basin show that the National Commission on Culture actively involves citizens in programmes aimed at protecting water resources. By promoting values of discipline and morality, the Commission not only influences social behaviour but also fosters a sense of environmental responsibility among citizens. This approach empowers residents of the Densu basin and beyond to take personal ownership of safeguarding their environment, particularly water resources, which are vital for sustainable development.

Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection

The Ministry of Gender, Children, and Social Protection empowers women and vulnerable groups to assert their rights and actively participate in the country's development. The Ministry ensures that gender equality is integrated into decision-making in the Densu basin. Within the Ministry, the Department of Gender focuses on promoting the welfare of women in the basin and empowering them. The department particularly represents the views and concerns of women, ensuring their interests are considered in decision-making processes (MoGCSP, 2023)

5.5.1.3 Statutory organ of government

The Eastern Regional Coordinating Council

The Eastern Regional Coordinating Council (ERCC), established under the Local Governance Act 936 of 2016, serves as one of Ghana's 16 regional coordinating councils. The ERCC, along with other regional coordinating councils, derives its authority from Article 255 of the Ghanaian Constitution. As the highest decision-making body at the regional level, the ERCC represents the central government. In discussions with stakeholders in the Densu basin, the ERCC demonstrated its commitment to combating water pollution caused by illegal mining. To monitor and control these activities, the ERCC collaborates with national security and conducts surveillance through the Regional Security Council (REGSEC).

5.5.1.4 Non-Governmental Organisation

Earth Service/GAPVOD

Interviews with the Densu Basin secretariat revealed that Earth Service is a member of the Coalition of Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) in Water and Sanitation (CONIWAS). With offices in Accra and Nsawam, Earth Service supports water resources management and the sustainable water supply to Ghanaians. It partners with state actors such as the Water Resources Commission by engaging in advocacy and raising public awareness about water resource pollution.

5.5.1.5 Traditional Authority

Akyem Abuakwa Traditional Council

According to data provided by the Densu basin secretariat and other stakeholders, the Akyem Abuakwa Traditional Council, located centrally in Kyebi within the Eastern Region of Ghana, plays a crucial and significant role in the region. The council is responsible for various aspects of the region's social, cultural, and economic development. From promoting traditional values and customs to overseeing land management and settling disputes, the Akyem Abuakwa Traditional Council is a vital institution that has a profound impact on the lives of the people in the region. As one of the 11 paramountcies within the Eastern Region, presided over by the Okenhene as its paramount ruler, the Akyem Abuakwa Traditional Council serves as the representative of the Eastern Regional House of Chiefs on the Densu River Basin Board. Engagements with traditional authorities and the Assemblymember of Kyebi reveal the traditional council's active engagement in advocating for preserving water resources, notably the Densu and Birim rivers, against pollution and desiccation. The Akyem Abuakwa Traditional Council upholds specific cultural prohibitions (taboos) aimed at nurturing the vitality of river ecosystems and safeguarding the associated deities. Notably, under the leadership of the Paramount Chief, also known as the Okyenhene, initiatives such as the Okyenhene Environmental Taskforce have been instituted to help combat illegal mining activities. This task force collaborates with the Municipal Assembly and law enforcement agencies to enforce regulations on illegal mining operations within Kyebi and adjoining localities within the traditional domain of Akyem Abuakwa.

5.5.2 Interests and motivation of stakeholders in the Pra basin

The study revealed that the interests of all ministries, departments, agencies, and state organs involved in water resources management in the Pra River basin are the same as those of the Densu basin in the preceding sections. Since the interests of the following institutions: EPA, GWCL, Forestry Commission, Ministry of Food and Agriculture, Ministry of Children and Social Protection, and the Regional Co-ordinating Council have been adequately described previously for the Densu basin, to avoid repetition, this section covers the interests and motivations of the Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies that are part of the Pra river basin board as well as the Minerals Commission, the Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority, Friends of Rivers and Water Bodies and the Kumasi Traditional Council.

5.5.2.1 Metropolitan/Municipal/District Assemblies

Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly (KMA)

The Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly (KMA), established by Legislative Instrument 1614 in 1995, is one of the 73 administrative districts and the only Metropolitan Assembly in the Pra basin, making it a key stakeholder in the region. To ensure effective administration, the KMA is divided into five sub-metropolitan councils: Bantama, Manhyia, Nhyiayeso, Subin, and Tafo. The Assembly is mandated by the Local Governance Act 936 of 2016 to oversee the metropolitan area's development.

According to discussions with KMA officials, the Assembly's vision is to transform Kumasi into a safe and vibrant city by improving development across all sectors, including the environment. The KMA is responsible for ensuring environmental sanitation by enforcing proper waste management practices. It works to prevent residents from connecting domestic effluent to public drains, which often flow into water bodies, helping to protect water resources from pollution caused by indiscriminate waste dumping. The Assembly enforces sanitation by-laws enacted in 1998 to maintain a clean and safe environment.

Kumasi, the capital of the Ashanti Region and Ghana's second-largest city, is governed at two complementary levels: political and traditional. Politically, the KMA manages the Kumasi Metropolis, while the Kumasi Traditional Council oversees cultural affairs, focusing on customs and land administration. The main river draining the Metropolis is the Owabi River, a tributary of the Offin River, which eventually flows into the Pra River. Other streams in the area include Subin, Sisai, Wiwi, Aboabo, and Nsuben. Kumasi is also served by two major water treatment plants, Owabi and Barekese, which supply treated water to the city and nearby districts.

Asante Akim South Municipal Assembly

The Asante Akim South Municipal Assembly is a key stakeholder in the Pra basin and the highest political and administrative authority at the local level. Under the Local Governance Act 936 of 2016, the Assembly implements the national environmental sanitation policy within the Municipality and supports the national water policy. The Act also requires all Metropolitan, Municipal, and District Assemblies to design and implement environmental management projects tailored to their unique districts.

Originally established as the Asante Akim South District by Legislative Instrument 1409 in 1988, with Juaso as its administrative capital, the Assembly gained municipal status in 2015. The municipality is drained by three major rivers: the Pra, Kume, and Subin, which provide drinking water and, to a lesser extent, serve as transportation routes for residents (Ghana Statistical Service, 2014).

The municipality covers approximately 1,217.7 square kilometres and has about 1,151.72 square kilometres within the Pra basin, meaning that around 95 percent of its land area lies in this basin. The Pra River basin in the municipality is known for significant gold deposits but these resources are currently being exploited through illegal mining operations. Such activities are causing substantial environmental damage, including the pollution of water sources and the destruction of natural habitats.

Obuasi Municipal Assembly

The Obuasi Municipal Assembly plays a vital role as a stakeholder in the Pra basin at the local level. Established by Legislative Instrument (L.I.) 1795 on March 17, 2004, the Assembly was created from the former Adansi West District, with Obuasi serving as its capital (Ghana Statistical Service, 2014). Mining and related activities form the backbone of the municipal

economy, employing many residents. The municipality is home to AngloGold Ashanti Gold Mines, one of the largest gold mines in Africa, which is also one of the major water users in the Pra basin. The company extracts water from rivers and groundwater for both mining and gold processing.

In an interview, officials from the Municipal Assembly emphasised that their primary mandate is to enhance the quality of life for people within their jurisdiction. According to the Local Government Act 936 of 2016, the Assembly is responsible for making development decisions across all sectors at the local level, including environmental matters. The officials also noted that the Assembly collaborates with various state institutions to manage environmental concerns, adhering to national environmental sanitation and water policies to ensure that development plans align with sound environmental management principles.

Streams serve as a significant source of water for households in communities surrounding Obuasi. However, contamination from mining activities has rendered these streams unsafe for drinking. In response, the Municipal Assembly is constructing mechanised boreholes in several communities to improve access to potable water.

Atwima Nwabiagya North District Assembly

The Atwima Nwabiagya North District Assembly was established in 2018 by Legislative Instrument L.I. 2327, created from the former Atwima Nwabiagya District Assembly, with Barekese as its capital. According to officers of the Assembly, the Rivers Offin and Owabi are the major rivers that drain the area, supplemented by several streams, including Dwahyen and Kobi. Fishing in the Offin River and its streams serves as a significant livelihood for many residents. The Assembly has constructed two dams—Owabi and Barekese—on the Owabi and Offin rivers, which supply potable water to major parts of the Ashanti region, including the Kumasi metropolitan area and its surroundings. Notably, the Barekese dam has the largest capacity of all water supply systems in the Pra basin (Water Resources Commission, 2012b).

Observations reveal that the Barekese and Owabi dams have also become tourist attractions, drawing both local and international visitors year-round. Discussions with the Pra Basin secretariat and District Assembly officials indicate that the Assembly has established by-laws, with assistance from the Water Resources Commission and the Pra Basin secretariat, to enhance sanitation practices and protect water resources within the district.

Bosomtwe District Assembly

Bosomtwe District was carved out of the former Bosomtwe Atwima Kwanwoma District and established by Legislative Instrument (LI) 1922 of 2008 with Kuntense as its district capital. A high-profile officer of the District Assembly in an interview explained that the work of the District Assembly is to prepare and implement programmes and projects geared towards sustainable development to improve the quality of life of the people in the district. The Assembly is guided by national policies such as environmental sanitation and water policies to ensure that its programmes and projects follow sound environmental management.

The primary sources of water for the district's residents include rivers, streams, and Lake Bosomtwe (Ghana Statistical Service, 2014). The district's rivers either flow into major rivers or feed into Lake Bosomtwe. This lake, located within the district, is the largest natural lake in West Africa and one of the six meteorite lakes in the world. Additionally, it is designated as a UNESCO World Biosphere Reserve (UNESCO, 2022).

Discussions with District Assembly officials and focus groups, supported by observations, reveal that Lake Bosomtwe is a popular tourist destination, attracting visitors year-round and generating significant income for the District Assembly. Furthermore, investigations have indicated that parts of the lake basin contain gold deposits.

Plate 10: Lake Bosomtwe

Source: UNESCO, 2022

Upper Denkyira East Municipal Assembly

The Upper Denkyira East Municipal Assembly (UDEMA) stands as the only administrative district from the Central Region that is part of the Pra basin board. Established in 2007 by Legislative Instrument (LI 1877) from the former Upper Denkyira District Assembly, UDEMA serves as the highest political and administrative authority in the municipality, with Dunkwa-On-Offin as its administrative capital. The municipality features the Pra-Offin confluence, where the Offin River joins the Pra River, marking the boundary between the Ashanti and Central regions of Ghana.

According to UDEMA officials, the Assembly aims to enhance the quality of life for residents by implementing programs that foster economic development, environmental sanitation, good health, and education. Under the Local Government Act 936, UDEMA is responsible for managing the environment within the municipality. The River Offin is the primary river draining the municipality, fed by numerous tributary streams such as Aponapon, Subin Ninta, Tuatin, Afiefi, and Subin. The River Offin serves as a key source of water for domestic use in the area. Further discussions with Assembly officials and focus groups revealed that the

municipality is rich in mineral deposits, particularly gold, located along the valleys of the Offin River and its tributaries.

Figure 5.6 below shows all six municipalities represented on the Pra basin board.

Figure 5.6 Municipal Assemblies on the Pra basin board

Source: Derived from SRTM data and Ghana Statistical Service, 2021

5.5.2.2 Ministries, Departments and Agencies

Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority

The Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority (LUSPA) was established in 2016 to replace the former Town and Country Planning Department, which had operated since 1945. Created under

the Land Use and Spatial Planning Act (Act 925), LUSPA's mission is to ensure that human settlements across the country are developed sustainably, harmoniously, and cost-effectively while adhering to sound environmental principles. According to officials at the Ashanti regional LUSPA office, the Authority achieves these objectives by providing comprehensive guidelines for physical development, including establishing buffers around water bodies and creating spatial plans prohibiting construction in wetlands.

Moreover, LUSPA regulates development activities in forests, nature reserves, wetlands, and open spaces. Operating at national and regional levels, LUSPA oversees the physical planning departments within metropolitan, municipal, and district assemblies, where officials are responsible for issuing building permits for all types of physical development. Interviews with LUSPA officials in the Ashanti region underscore the Authority's vital role in ensuring compliance with development guidelines at the local level, further reinforcing its commitment to sustainable land use and effective spatial planning.

Minerals Commission of Ghana

The Minerals Commission of Ghana is a central government agency established by the 1992 Constitution and is responsible for regulating and managing the utilization of Ghana's mineral resources (Minerals Commission, 2021). As the primary implementing agency for the country's mineral and mining policy, the Commission issues mining licenses for both large-scale and small-scale mineral extraction. In discussions with board members of the Pra basin, they revealed that the Minerals Commission actively monitors exploration and mining operations across the country. By collaborating with other state agencies, the Commission ensures that mining companies comply with the requirements of their licenses. Additionally, the Commission maintains regional and district offices nationwide to effectively carry out this critical oversight role

Stakeholders in the Pra basin stated during interviews that mining in rivers is prohibited under the Minerals and Mining Act. The Act also ensures that legal mining activities do not cause water pollution. As per the Minerals and Mining Act of 2006 (Act 703), any individual or company with a mineral right and wishes to use water for mining operations must obtain a

license from the Water Resources Commission. Essentially, this means that the mining company must seek permission from the WRC to use any water resources, whether surface or groundwater, in the specified area during the mining process.

5.5.2.3 Non-Governmental Organisation

Friends of Rivers and Water Bodies

An interview with the Friends of Rivers and Water Bodies representative indicates that it is an environmental Non-Governmental Organisation that started in 1985 as a pressure group made up of mostly civil servants. The group came together in Kumasi, the capital of the Ashanti Region, to advocate for protecting and conserving surface water resources. The group focused on cleaning the country's natural rivers, lakes and streams. As a result, they engaged in tree planting, especially around water bodies. Further discussions with the Friends of Rivers and Water Bodies representative revealed that their organisation played a significant role in creating a separate ministry for water resources in Ghana. While their primary focus is water, they recognise that environmental issues are interconnected and cannot be addressed in isolation. As such, they devote resources to educating people on the importance of not farming near water bodies and avoiding the use of harmful agrochemicals in those areas. Additionally, they work closely with various stakeholders, including the Water Resources Commission, District Assemblies, schools, the police, market women, and other state institutions, to protect and preserve water resources.

5.5.2.4 Traditional Authority

Kumasi Traditional Council

The Kumasi Traditional Council serves as a branch of the Chieftaincy institution, representing the Ashanti Regional House of Chiefs on the Pra basin board. Composed of chiefs with authority in their respective traditional areas, the Council plays a crucial role in upholding customary laws and managing Kumasi stool lands. During the study, the traditional leader from the Adum Traditional Area emphasised the Council's dedication to these responsibilities, underscoring its importance in preserving cultural heritage and ensuring effective governance within the community. He noted that the Council's jurisdiction spans the Kumasi Metropolitan

Area and parts of the Bono, Bono East, and Ashanti regions. In partnership with the government, the Council actively fosters peace and unity among the populace.

The Asantehene, who presides over the Kumasi Traditional Council, serves as the supreme ruler of the Ashanti Kingdom and has shown a strong commitment to environmental preservation, particularly concerning water bodies. To address the challenges posed by illegal mining and to protect the region's water resources, he has collaborated with various stakeholders to establish the Asanteman Task Force.

This task force, identifiable by their branded vehicles (see Plate 11), monitors mining activities throughout the Ashanti Region, gathering intelligence on illegal operations and identifying offenders. At a significant gathering of the Ashanti Regional House of Chiefs in 2022, the Asantehene launched a new initiative aimed at tackling illegal mining in traditional areas. He called upon all chiefs in the Ashanti region to take accountability for these actions. Each chief will oversee mineral rights holders in their territories, ensuring compliance with license requirements and promptly reporting any illegal mining activities to the appropriate authorities for swift action.

Plate 11: Vehicles for Asanteman task force against illegal mining

Source: <https://myjoyonline.com/>

5.5.3 Stakeholders not involved in decision-making in the Densu basin

After identifying stakeholders involved in decision-making in the Densu basin, the study also considered if some relevant stakeholders were missing in the decision-making process. The majority of interviewees agreed that the composition of the basin board had a broad range of actors thus stakeholders from diverse institutional settings who can contribute to efficient and effective water resources management. However, from the point of view of some participants

who work with non-governmental organisations, the current platform for stakeholder engagement is inadequate and more organisations than those on the board should be engaged in the decision-making process. These participants assert that more NGOs are actively operating in the basin's environmental space which can help support the basin board's activities. One of the participants had this to say:

“The current collaboration platform may not be sufficient for the task. It seems that governmental organisations dominate the discussions, potentially overlooking important viewpoints. It may be necessary to explore alternative collaboration platforms or strategies to ensure that everyone can contribute and be heard.” (High Profile Officer of A ROCHA Ghana, Densu Basin, 2021).

Based on discussions with the WRC and basin secretariats and input from other stakeholders, it seems that the basin boards are intentionally mostly comprised of governmental organisations. These stakeholders noted that Ghana's laws require state institutions to collaborate inter-governmentally and inter-agency at various levels. The Water Resources Commission Act, 1996 (Act 522) outlines the composition of the WRC board at the national level, with 10 of the 15 members representing governmental organisations. This composition is meant to guide the makeup of the basin boards. Additionally, state agencies typically share similar objectives in managing water resources and possess specific legal mandates and authority over water-related issues. This authority allows for effective coordination and swift decision-making that impacts water resources.

Focus group discussions in the Densu basin revealed a significant gap in engaging primary stakeholders, including citizens and local actors, who are crucial water users at the community level in decision-making processes. Among these actors, are farmers, miners, fisherfolk, estate developers, waste disposal entities, and sand miners, whose roles as primary stakeholders in the Densu basin are unmistakable, simultaneously contributing significantly to water resource pollution within the basin. Despite their stake, no structured platform exists for their inclusion in decision-making processes concerning the protection, conservation and utilisation of water resources. According to reports from the WRC, a subset of water users typically participates in IWRM planning sessions, aiding in prioritising water resource challenges. However, in the practical formulation of water protection, conservation, and utilisation strategies, these stakeholders often find themselves merely informed of decisions already made, leaving them with the imperative of compliance. In instances of grievances related to pollution and

contamination, local stakeholders typically resort to the district assembly in hopes of redress and acknowledgement of their concerns.

Another group worth mentioning that is not actively engaged in the Densu basin is the private sector. The private sector mainly consists of drinking water companies and beverage manufacturing companies. The findings revealed that the private sector has a role in water resources management, especially in financing water resources protection and conservation programmes.

5.5.4 Stakeholders not involved in decision-making in the Pra basin

One subject that emerged from all discussions with stakeholders in the Pra basin is the absence of the private sector in the decision-making process at the basin level. Though the private sector has a role in the design and implementation of water management decisions at the basin level, this role has not been fully asserted. An interview with one of the big companies producing potable water in the Pra Basin revealed that these prominent water companies pay yearly water abstraction fees to the Water Resources Commission through the basin office. The water abstraction fees are charged based on the number of boreholes the company uses to abstract water. A top official of the company bemoaned the lack of engagement with the Pra Basin office and the Water Resources Commission. The official confirmed his company's willingness to collaborate with the Water Resources Commission if engaged. He believes that the relationship between the WRC, basin secretariats and the private enterprises should go beyond just the collection of water use fees. He noted:

“We are open to collaborating with the Water Resources Commission and want to engage with state regulators like the WRC, similar to how we engage with the Food and Drugs Authority. It is important for us to understand their work beyond just collecting water use fees from us”
(Top official, Drinking Water Producing Company, Pra Basin, December 2022).

5.6 The stakeholders' selection process

The study finds that the process through which stakeholders are selected to make decisions is the same for both the Densu and Pra River basins. The WRC is responsible for constituting the basin boards for both the Densu and Pra basins. The composition of the basin boards has been specified in the IWRM plans of both basins. Stakeholders are selected by appointment from their respective institutions. The WRC officially writes to the individual institutions that make up the Densu or Pra basins board, requesting that they select a representative to be on the basin

board. These institutions respond with the contact information of their representative. The WRC then acts upon receipt of information from the various institutions by engaging the selected representatives. It is important to note that all members of the basin boards serve a three-year term from when they are appointed after which the board is reconstituted by going through the selection process. Old members of the board may be maintained if their respective institutions re-nominate them. Sometimes the formation of the basin board is affected by the state of affairs of the country when there is a change in government and all public sector boards at the national level have to be dissolved to make way for new boards. When the basin board has not yet fulfilled its three-year tenure and there is a change in government, they will continue their work regardless. However, the chairpersons of the basin boards will automatically be removed from post. This is because chairpersons of the Densu and Pra basin boards are appointed from the WRC board at the national level. Board members of the WRC have been assigned as chairpersons to the various basin boards in the country. The Densu basin officer explains why basin board chairpersons are selected from the national board. He expounds that:

“This arrangement is done to link the national board to the basin boards for the chairpersons to have up -to-date information on each river basin. The information about the river basins is shared with other members of the Water Resources Commission board whenever they meet at the national level” (Densu Basin Officer, July 2023).

According to basin officers, sometimes the reconstitution of the Densu or Pra basin board may be delayed until the government in power has nominated people to the Water Resources Commission board. Once the Water Resources Commission board has been put together, the basin board can also be constituted. The basin officer of Densu explained how the basin boards coped with this situation. He notes:

“Each time, we get someone from the national board to chair the Densu basin. Whenever there is a change of government the chairperson of the Densu basin board will have to be replaced. To ensure that the board's work continues, we elect a vice-chairperson who would in the absence of the chairperson, chair the board meetings and moderate decision-making in the basin” (Densu Basin Officer, July 2023).

Another factor that delays the reconstitution of the basin board is when the individual institutions that make up the board do not respond promptly to the request by the Water Resources Commission to nominate their representative on the basin board. A high profile officer of the Pra basin remarks on the nomination of board members and the delay in forming the basin board:

“District Assemblies and other institutions have the power to nominate their representative on the board. It becomes a challenge when the representative is a political figure because once the party is out of power the person is out and we could have benefitted from some continuity. At the moment we do not have the full complement of the Pra basin board, only 5 members are still at post. We are working on getting the institutions to nominate new representatives which takes some time. This affects the board meetings” (A high profile officer of the Pra Basin Officer, December 2022).

5.7 The scope of decision-making

Discussions with the WRC and basin secretariats reveal that the decision-making scope of the Densu basin board differs from that of the Pra basin board. The WRC had intended to stick to the institutional arrangement outlined in the IWRM plans for the Densu and Pra basins. Based on the nature of both basins, the Densu basin is managed as one whole entity while the Pra basin has a three-tier management structure, where the basin is divided into three sub-basins. However, due to resource constraints, all the sub-basin boards of the Pra basin could not be established. The WRC, therefore, had to resort to increasing the workload of the Densu basin board and secretariat by adding the management of the Birim sub-basin of the Pra to the Densu basin board.

5.7.1 Scope of decision-making in the Densu river basin

The Densu River basin is relatively smaller in terms of size than the Pra basin. The basin covers three administrative regions (see Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.2: The Densu Basin

Source: Derived from SRTM Data, 2020

The Densu River Basin Board was established in March 2004 on World Water Day to oversee the drying up of riverbeds in Ghana. According to interviews with basin board officials, the Densu basin board was the first ever basin board to be established in the country when the country started operationalising the principles of IWRM. The basin officials added that the board's objective is to preserve, maintain, and utilise the water resources and other natural resources in and around the basin to the optimum. In terms of scope, the Densu basin board plans for the Densu basin and two other basins. The board is responsible for protecting, conserving, and efficiently using water resources in the Ayensu, Birim, and Densu basins. The Ayensu River basin is part of the same coastal river system as the Densu but does not have a separate basin secretariat or board. The Birim basin, on the other hand, was originally a part of the Pra river basin and is a sub-basin under the bigger Pra basin. It seems the Birim and Ayensu basins' proximity to the Densu basin is an additional factor that led to their addition to the scope of management of the Densu basin board. A Densu basin officer throws more light on this arrangement. He stated:

“Recently this year, the WRC assigned the Birim and Ayensu basins to the Densu basin board to manage with the same resources we used to manage only the Densu basin. This is because the WRC does not have the resources to establish separate secretariats and boards for all the basins” (Densu Basin Officer, December 2021).

5.7.2 Scope of decision-making in the Pra river basin

The Pra River basin is bigger, about nine times the size of the Densu basin. The basin covers five administrative regions of Ghana (see Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.3: The Pra Basin

Source: Derived from SRTM Data, 2020

Considering the complexity of the basin, which is that stakeholders' interests are linked to the major sub-basins and not the entire basin, the basin was to be governed at the sub-basin level. The Basin was divided into the Upper Pra sub-basin, Birim sub-basin and Lower Pra sub-basin (see Figure 5.4). According to the WRC, it had planned to have three separate boards for the three sub-basins. The Upper Pra sub-basin board was to manage the Offin, Anum, Oda and other sub-basins in the upper part of the basin, including the Bosomtwe Lake. The Birim board was to manage the Birim sub-basin in the Eastern Region of Ghana, and the Lower Pra board was to manage the sub-basin involving the main Pra River, between Twifo Praso and the Coast where the Pra River enters the sea. However, only the upper Pra sub-basin board has been set up due to limited funds. In 2010, the Pra/Offin basin board was established to plan and manage water resources in the upper Pra sub-basin with its secretariat in Kumasi. Therefore, the existing Pra basin board's work relates to only the Upper part of the Pra basin. Since the Birim sub-

basin has been given to the Densu basin board and secretariat to manage, that leaves the Lower part of the Pra basin, which currently does not have a governing body.

Figure 5.4: The sub-basins of the Pra

Source: Based on WRC, 2012

5.8 Conclusion

In this chapter, the nature and scope of decision-making in the Densu and Pra River basins have been analysed. Also, the current decision-making framework, the interests and motivations of stakeholders involved in decision-making and the process through which stakeholders are selected for decision-making in the Densu and Pra River basins have been analysed. It has been demonstrated that though the decision-making processes are similar, the geographical scope of decision-making varies between the Densu and Pra River basins. The Densu basin is managed as one whole basin, while the Pra basin is managed as sub-basins. This indicates the varying levels of IWRM operationalisation in Ghana. It also affirms the flexibility of the IWRM module, where IWRM principles can be adapted to different local contexts. The decision-making framework described in this chapter shows that planned development may still be relevant in planning for the management of water resources in the Densu and Pra basins. The

conventional planning process identified in the basins has been to prepare a long-term plan (National IWRM plan), a medium-term (Basin IWRM plan), and annual plans which are implemented to achieve objectives pertaining to water resources management. The interests of stakeholders on the basin boards, particularly state organisations, reflect their legal mandates, which encompass a spectrum of responsibilities ranging from environmental stewardship and resource management to regulatory oversight and public welfare. For both the Densu and Pra basins, the composition of the basin management boards differ which reflects the unique characteristics of the basins. The selection of stakeholders on the basin boards is to achieve a particular end, in that institutions on both the Densu and Pra basin boards are key groups who can affect the achievement of the basin's objective which is to enhance the management and development of water resources in a way that prioritises access to adequate potable water for people in the country. It is clear from the in-depth interviews and analysis of documents that a section of stakeholders are engaged during decision-making for the Densu and Pra basins. The prevalence of public organisations on basin boards may primarily be attributed to their perceived legitimacy in addressing water-related concerns. Additionally, there is a discernible alignment of state institutions with the goals of the ruling political party, suggesting a political coherence within these entities. Consequently, an environment conducive to collaboration and synergy among state institutions involved in water governance is fostered, thereby solidifying their prominence on basin boards. The study supports the idea that limited resources seem to be working against the possibility of a much broader engagement of stakeholders. In the subsequent chapters, the analysis delves into the dynamics of water resource management in the Densu and Pra basins, scrutinising the ramifications of limited resources and various other factors on the sustainable management of water resources.

CHAPTER SIX

STAKEHOLDER INTERACTIONS IN SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF THE DENSU AND PRA RIVER BASINS

6.1 Introduction

The sustainable management of river basins presents a challenge that requires the collaboration and coordination of various stakeholders. This chapter explores the dynamics of stakeholder interactions within the Densu and Pra River basins, aiming to understand how different actors engage with other stakeholders to pursue sustainable management goals. The chapter also explores the multifaceted environmental problems stakeholders perceive in the Densu and Pra basins. This chapter analyses research question two, which examines how stakeholder dynamics affect water resources management in the Densu and Pra River basins. The chapter covers the responsibilities of the individuals who serve on the basin boards and the interactions between the various stakeholder groups and the basin secretariat. In addition, a comprehensive examination has been conducted on the environmental hurdles faced by each basin. There is a particular emphasis on all stakeholders' distinct demands and worries. These ecological challenges are diverse and impact the amount and quality of water resources present in the basins.

Table 6.1: Summary of interview questions and responses under stakeholder interactions

Theme	Questions	Responses
Duties of stakeholders in the basin	How does your organisation contribute to river basin management or water policy implementation? What key activities have been completed?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The WRC's basin secretariat regulates and manages water resources. - Districts and organisations participate in the Green Ghana Project, planting trees near water bodies and educating communities on responsible mining.
Engagement of stakeholders	Who participated in recent stakeholder meetings? Which stakeholders were more collaborative, and which were in conflict (if any)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Board members, state agencies, NGOs, and chiefs. - Chiefs sometimes don't offer on-the-ground support, but there are no conflicts during meetings. - Strong collaboration with state agencies, NGOs, and the Regional Coordinating Council, which helps resolve conflicts.

Commitment to river basin management	How committed is your organisation to river basin management and policy implementation?	- High commitment from stakeholders, especially EPA and security task forces formed by the District Assembly to tackle illegal mining.
Stakeholder participation	How important is stakeholder collaboration for effective river basin management? How active were stakeholders in the meetings?	- Collaboration is vital, as WRC lacks sufficient resources. - Cooperation with agencies like EPA and Ghana Water is key to tackling pollution. - Meetings have almost 100% participation, at least 90% and all representatives are encouraged to contribute to discussions and decision-making.
Public participation	Do you bring together all stakeholder groups in the same consultation meeting? If so, do you get a high representativeness of all sectors? If not, what do you think can be done to engage them?	The basin board holds separate meetings, along with workshops, community outreach, and campaigns. Outreach is project-based and often tied to external funding, while public campaigns are more intensive around World Water Day in March.
Power relations in water governance	Do some stakeholders have more influence over water governance decisions?	- State agencies, especially environmental protection bodies like the EPA, have more influence and are more vocal. - The WRC has the most control, while private enterprises have the least power due to regulations.

Source: Densu Field Data Collection, December 2021
Pra Field Data Collection, December 2022

6.2 Duties of stakeholders in the basin

In-depth interviews with stakeholders across the Densu and Pra basins reveal that the basin boards' formal duties and activities are similar. These duties are spelt out by the operational guidelines provided by the Water Resources Commission. The study identified five principal duties of the river basin boards: pollution control, water use licensing, planning, implementing activities for water resources conservation, and monitoring and evaluating programmes and activities.

Based on interviews with officials from the Densu and Pra River basins, along with corroborating accounts from some basin board members, it was found that following their selection by respective institutions to join the basin board, an inaugural meeting is convened once the board is fully constituted. This meeting serves to delineate the roles and responsibilities of individuals serving on the basin boards. The first meeting of the basin boards holds significant importance as it sets the tone for the entire operation. At this meeting, all members are provided with a comprehensive orientation session to help them understand their respective roles and responsibilities. All members must grasp the functioning of the basin board, including the decision-making process and protocols. This initial meeting lays the foundation for the successful and efficient functioning of the basin board. Following that, the importance of continuous learning is emphasized as training and support programmes are organised to equip board members with the necessary skills to effectively perform their duties and address concerns related to water resource management in their respective basins.

Further discussions with basin officers and board members suggest that, in addition to developing and implementing the basin IWRM plan, the basin boards also periodically undertake ecological monitoring. This monitoring is to observe the state of water quality, identify trends in water pollution, and assess the impact of climate change on water resources in the basins. One of the Densu basin board members commented on the board's ecological monitoring activities, illustrating its benefits. He indicated:

“At a certain point in time, our diligent ecological monitoring efforts led us to prevent the diverting of septic tanks into the Densu River. This decision was made to avoid further water pollution within the basin”
(Board member, Densu Basin, November 2022).

Although the basin board is supposed to periodically monitor the ecological state of water resources and the performance of the basin officers, the study found that this practice is not as consistent as it should be. This situation was reiterated by the officers in the Densu basin who noted:

“Previously, the basin board was responsible for ecological monitoring and evaluating the performance of the Densu secretariat by visiting project sites. However, this practice has not been implemented for a considerable period. Due to financial constraints, the basin officer is now solely responsible for conducting ecological monitoring without assistance from other board members” (Densu Basin Officer, December 2021).

According to the current operational guidelines provided by the Water Resources Commission, which spells out the mode of operation of the basin board, the duties of stakeholders of the basin include:

- Proposing comprehensive plans for the conservation, development, and utilisation of water resources of the respective basin;
- Initiating, implementing, and coordinating activities connected with the development of water resources of the basin;
- Assisting in the process of registering water users and granting water rights;
- Assisting in monitoring and evaluating programmes for the utilisation and management of the water resources of the basin;
- Advising the Commission on any matter likely to affect the water resources of the basin and
- Collaborating with pollution control agencies in the basin on matters concerning the management and control of pollution of water resources (Water Resources Commission, 2011)

6.3 Engagement of Stakeholders

Based on discussions with basin officers and board members, engagement with stakeholders in the Densu and Pra basins typically involves a range of methods, such as meetings, workshops, ecological monitoring, community outreach, and awareness campaigns. The basin officers use meetings, workshops, and environmental monitoring as established channels to disseminate water-related information to stakeholders. Meetings are primarily intended for basin board members, while workshops are open to a broader group of stakeholders. Through these channels, stakeholders are equipped with more knowledge and are better equipped to respond to water-related issues. They are also encouraged to share their own experiences and insights and provide feedback on relevant water-related problems.

6.3.1 Commitment and participation of stakeholders

According to discussions with the basin officers of both Densu and Pra, stakeholder meetings in the Densu basin are typically held at the basin secretariat located in Koforidua, the capital of Ghana's Eastern region. Meanwhile, meetings for the Pra basin are usually conducted at conference halls outside Kumasi's basin office. Invitations for stakeholders are sent through various channels such as letters, emails, and phone calls. In addition, social media and other Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools are also utilised to ensure effective

communication. Each basin board maintains a dedicated WhatsApp group that includes all members to remind them of upcoming meetings. One of the Pra Basin officers provided an overview of the participation arrangements for the recent board meeting of the Pra Basin board. She emphasized their reliance on the WRC to release funds for the secretariat's operations and organisation of board meetings. The main challenge has been securing the presence of the majority, if not all, of the basin board members at the meetings. She explained:

“The last board meeting was held virtually. This was organised in September 2020. The secretariat proposes a date, and we check with members to ensure they would be available for the meeting before we settle on the date and time. The WRC provides resources when we have the full complement of the board. We send out letters to invite board members. We also call them a month ahead, two weeks before the time, a week before and then two days before the meeting. The board meeting is organised outside the office because we need more space to accommodate board members. We rent a conference centre in a hotel or guest house and pay members allowance for participation” (Pra Basin officer, November 2022).

An officer of the Densu basin also commented on the participation of board members and the payment of allowances. He said:

“For participation, people are enthusiastic. If I should inform our board members this morning that we have visitors and requested them to come and meet them, they would do so with enthusiasm. However, after the meeting, they will find out if you have any transportation allowance for them. They would still be friendly and leave if you do not have any such allowance. But they are older people, and you cannot expect them to continue working without any allowance for their travel and transportation expenses” (Densu basin officer, December 2021).

Interviews with officials from the Densu and Pra basins, along with discussions with board members, and in accordance with the operational guidelines of the basin board, reveal that board meetings are required to be held every quarter, which translates to every three months. Each basin board is supposed to hold four quarterly meetings annually. However, this is subject to the availability of funds. For almost a decade, the Densu Basin Board has been unable to organise four board meetings in a year. An officer of the basin had this to say about the regularity of board meetings:

“The last time we could hold four quarterly meetings in a year was in 2013. After 2013, it came down to 2 board meetings a year, then to 1 meeting, and then there was no meeting at all in 2021” (Densu Basin officer, December 2021).

Regarding why the Densu Basin Board has not been able to meet regularly, the basin officer noted:

“We cannot hold meetings because it is said that before you organise a meeting, check with the WRC whether there is money; do not just organise. Previously, it was not like that. There must be money, and the money available is woefully inadequate. At the end of each board meeting, the expenditure would be around GHc 9000. All this time, activities of the basin board were supported by DANIDA funding, and it was expected that once the DANIDA funding fizzles out, the number of times the board could meet would reduce” (Densu Basin officer, December 2021).

It is important to note that no board meetings took place in 2021 or the subsequent year due to funding constraints. However, in March 2023, the CREAM research project, funded by DANIDA (of which this thesis is a part), provided crucial support, enabling the long-awaited board meeting to finally take place. This funding significantly enhanced its organisation allowing board members to discuss important matters and make informed decisions. During a discussion about the Densu basin, a member of the board expressed his thoughts on the significant impact of board meetings. He said:

“The meetings and workshops are always productive. For instance, most board members are knowledgeable and can appreciate the issues discussed. We share relevant information and make critical decisions each time we meet” (Member of the Densu basin board, December 2021).

For the Pra basin, the basin officers and some board members, during interviews, recount that generally, in the past five years, the basin board met at least once a year before the coming of COVID-19 in 2020. In 2019, the Pra Basin board met two times in person. After COVID-19, there was one virtual meeting in 2020. Subsequently, the board is unable to meet. A member of the Pra basin board spoke about the engagement of stakeholders and the challenges they are facing. He noted:

“The board meetings were successful. If you look at the spectrum of expertise on the board and the deliberations, they are very fruitful. The Secretariat also implements the proposals taken by the board. The only challenge has been with the regularity of board meetings. We cannot meet regularly per the guidelines” (Member of the Pra basin board, November 2022).

The Pra Basin secretariat highlighted that the principal cause for the delay in arranging board meetings in the Pra Basin is the insufficient number of members required to constitute a complete board. Owing to the absence of the requisite number of members, the board has not been able to convene a meeting.

6.4 Level of stakeholder engagement

Engagements with stakeholders in the Densu and Pra basins are generally productive. On average, the level of engagement between the basin secretariat and key stakeholders is high, though there are differing levels among the groups of stakeholders. According to discussions with basin officials and the WRC, board meetings for both the Densu and Pra basins have a minimum percentage attendance rate of 90 percent. For the Densu basin, there are occasional issues with the timing of meeting notices and members arriving on time. A former board member who is also a traditional leader in the basin mentioned this as a concern.

“The river basin secretariat sometimes gives short notice for the board meeting, so some members cannot make it. The meeting notice can come in two days before the meeting. At least a one-week notice should be given to board members. Another problem is that most people report late, so the meeting duration is prolonged. When a meeting is supposed to end at 1 p.m., because of the late start, we can close around 3 p.m.”
(Former member of the Densu Basin board, December 2021).

In spite of occasional late notice for board meetings, attendance remains high. This may be because attendees receive a meeting allowance at the end of each session as an incentive to attend.

During discussions with some members of the Pra Basin Board, they expressed their strong desire to increase the frequency of their meetings. They believe that meeting more frequently can help them stay up to date with important developments, discuss issues in a more timely manner, and make more informed decisions. The board members further pointed out that more frequent meetings can help improve communication and collaboration among the board members, which can ultimately lead to better outcomes for the Pra Basin. The observed stakeholder dynamics for the Densu and Pra River basins are presented in Figures 6.1 and 6.2, respectively. These highlight the level of interactions between the basin secretariat and the different stakeholders and the power and influence of key actors in the basins.

6.5 Relations of power, influence and engagement among stakeholders in the Densu basin

The relations of power, influence and the engagement of various stakeholders in the Densu River basin in Ghana were analysed based on the roles the stakeholders play in the conception, development and execution of water conservation and protection decisions and their interactions with the basin secretariat. Eden and Ackermann's (2011) model of 'power' and 'influence' relationships was used and modified to map the relative degrees of power and influence that actors have in the decision-making process over water resources management, as well as the level of engagement between them and the basin secretariat regarding water resources management in the basin. The results of this analysis are based on data and observations collected during key informant interviews in the Densu basin illustrated in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1: Analysis of level of engagement, power, and influence of key actors in the Densu Basin

Source: Author’s construct, 2023

According to Figure 6.1, the stakeholders with higher power and influence in decision making over water resources management in the Densu basin are those with explicit legal mandate over water-related issues. These are Ministries and Agencies at the national level. There is also the Regional Coordinating Council (RCC), which is a local government institution that has a significant influence on decision-making in the Densu basin. The Ministries, Agencies and RCC all emphasise the need for the protection, conservation and optimum utilisation of the country’s water resources. Relative to central government agencies and ministries, Metropolitan/Municipal/District Assemblies (MMDAs) at the local level have less power and influence in the decision-making process over water resources management in the Densu basin. The MMDAs however play an important role in conveying the complaints and demands of communities relating to water to the government or central government institutions.

All interviewees including traditional leaders agreed that though the Constitution of Ghana recognises traditional institutions, the democratic governance system has significantly reduced the hitherto high power of traditional leaders. Unlike land, where traditional leaders have rights of ownership, for water resources all ownership is vested in the President who holds in trust for the people of the country. One of the traditional leaders interviewed in the Densu basin commented:

“The chiefs we think are custodians do not have that much power now the politicians have overpowered them” (Traditional leader, Effiduase Traditional Council, December 2023).

As Figure 6.1 suggests, the actors can be put into four main categories, I, II, III and IV. In category I, we have actors with relatively low power and influence. They also have a low engagement with the basin secretariat in terms of water resources management. The stakeholders belonging to this category are the traditional authority and private enterprises. Data from interviews in the Densu basin particularly with basin officers indicate that the traditional authorities' minimal engagement with the basin secretariat was because they contributed to the problem of illegal mining. They sometimes champion illegal mining activities and inappropriate land sales, which are challenges confronting water resources management in the Densu basin. In the basin, it was observed that most traditional leaders fail to obtain guidance for the optimal conservation of water resources. During discussions with basin officers, it was revealed that many traditional leaders perceive water resources and land within their jurisdiction as personal property. This observation was corroborated by A ROCHA Ghana, an environmental organisation, and was further supported by the Fisheries Commission. This perception of ownership potentially leads to conflicts over these resources' use and hinders efforts towards sustainable management of water resources in the basin.

Private enterprises are another stakeholder group that engages less with the basin secretariat. Data from the WRC and basin secretariat reveal that when any private enterprise seeks water use permits, they must submit applications to the basin office. The office thoroughly assesses its operational areas to ensure their activities do not harm the surface and groundwater resources. Typically, private enterprises only interact with the basin office when obtaining water use permits. Some of the noteworthy private enterprises in the Densu basin include intravenous infusion companies, beverage and juice producers, drinking water bottling companies, and manufacturers of concrete products.

In Category II of Figure 6.1, there are actors with low power but a high level of engagement. Actors belonging to this category are NGOs and MMDAs. All interviewees in the Densu basin believe that the MMDAs and NGOs are vital in managing water resources. They present complaints to the basin office and work together with them to find solutions, even if the problems were caused by the MMDAs themselves. The basin officers indicated that since the work of the secretariat is within specific districts or municipalities, the MMDAs need to be informed about the actions of the basin office in their jurisdiction. One key challenge affecting engagements with MMDAs according to the basin secretariat was high turnover rates among civil servants of the Assemblies. A basin officer expressed concern about this problem:

“There was one good co-ordinating director at Ngleshie-Amanfro: Ga South Municipal Assembly. He was on the board and our liaison officer for the municipality. He was resourceful and stayed in the Municipality for just two years. He was transferred to another Assembly when we were about to roll out an important project for which his services were needed. Sometimes, we spend much project funds to train these people, and they are transferred from the area shortly, leaving with all the knowledge they have acquired” (Densu Basin officer, August 2023).

On the top right corner of Figure 6.1 appear the category III actors who, because of their mandate have more power to use legal, regulatory, or political mechanisms to enforce compliance with water-related regulations. They also show greater engagement levels with the basin secretariat. Among these are those with an explicit focus on improving the quality and quantity of water resources and wetlands attached to the water resources such as WRC, EPA, and Forestry Commission (FC) These agencies are highly involved and assist the basin secretariat in controlling the encroachment of buffers along the Densu river. For instance, the Forestry Commission is planting trees to protect buffers while the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) participates in activities to monitor the quality of water resources. These agencies also share their resources with the basin secretariat. Some members of the Densu board indicated that the basin secretariat sometimes relies on vehicles from the EPA to monitor water quality across the basin. A director of the EPA within the basin underscored a collaborative partnership with the Densu Basin secretariat, emphasising their joint efforts towards shared objectives and mutual goal attainment.

“Most of the time, the EPA makes its resources available to the basin office. This means that anytime the basin office needs vehicles and they reach out to us, we make ours available for them” (High Profile Officer, EPA, Densu basin, November 2022).

The Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL) is one of the government agencies with an explicit mandate in the water sector. Though it is in category III it is positioned at a lower level of engagement, as depicted in Figure 6.1. An officer of the basin explained why GWCL has a lesser level of engagement than the other central government agencies.

“Ghana Water Company Limited’s level of engagement is reflective of its mandate. This is because their mandate has been reduced to the production of water. They used to do what the WRC and the basin office do now: manage our water resources. Since their mandate has been restricted, we are careful not to engage them too much beyond their order” (Densu Basin officer, December 2021).

Category IV of Figure 6.1 describes stakeholders with relatively high influence but low engagement. The media is found in this category with its position depicting moderate influence and moderate level of engagement. The Densu Basin Secretariat recognises the media as essential to its operations and engages with them sometimes to ensure effective communication and collaboration. The Secretariat uses traditional media platforms such as radio, television, and print media to disseminate information and promote its programmes. This engagement takes place in two ways: first, by inviting media outlets to cover events and programmes organised by the Secretariat, and second, by accepting invitations to speak on water resource management matters in the basin. The secretariat emphasises the importance of this productive engagement, which fosters a better understanding of its activities and promotes greater public awareness and participation in water resource management efforts.

“With the media, they call us, and we call them. When we have programmes which we want them to cover, we invite them. They also call to interview us to discuss some issues concerning the basin. Sometimes, you meet people who have no idea about the work of the WRC; at other times, those we meet have some knowledge about the work of the WRC. With such people, it is easier to interact with them” (Densu basin officer, October 2023).

Basin officers however bemoaned a challenge with their engagement with the media which is that the media sometimes misrepresents the message the basin secretariat intends to convey to the public. In such cases, the secretariat takes the necessary steps to speak on other media stations to clarify the issues and correct the misrepresentation. A basin officer shared his experience:

“Someone came from a newspaper agency to interview me, and they misquoted what I said. The newspaper reported that the WRC is

waiting for citizens to change their attitudes before we can fulfil our mandate of keeping our water bodies clean, which was not what we said” (Densu Basin officer, October 2023).

6.6 Public participation in the Densu basin

Community involvement in water resource management is critical, and it appears that communities are typically engaged to support the implementation of various programmes and decisions established by the basin board. The Densu secretariat takes the lead in coordinating these engagements to raise awareness and educate individuals on water resource management issues. This approach has proven effective in disseminating important information to communities within the Densu basin, particularly on the effects of deforestation, poor sanitation, farming, and mining. Through awareness creation campaigns such as community outreaches, the secretariat has endeavoured to encourage agro-forestry practices among farmers residing in the basin, thus promoting sustainable management of water resources. Basin secretariat officers admit that it is not always possible to organise community durbars and outreaches due to financial constraints. However, they mentioned that many projects which receive external funding often include a component for conducting awareness campaigns in the community. Whenever such projects are implemented in the basin, the officers make it a priority to organise more public awareness campaigns and sensitisation meetings. This is done to create awareness among the residents and sensitise them about the importance of protecting water resources. Through these campaigns, the officers encourage the residents to take an active role in preserving the quality of water resources in the region. In addition to other outreach methods, the basin secretariat utilises media platforms to spread awareness about responsible water resource management in the Densu basin. One such platform is Sunrise FM, a public radio station in Koforidua. While radio appearances are not a regular occurrence, the WRC and the secretariat make a concerted effort to engage with the public on air at least once a year, specifically on World Water Day (observed annually on March 22nd).

6.7 Environmental problems perceived by stakeholders in the Densu basin

The ecological concerns determined to have the highest impact on water resources within the basin have been carefully identified and categorised for each stakeholder group. This analysis focuses on how stakeholders view water resources in the basin and allows for a more targeted approach to addressing these concerns, ensuring that the appropriate measures are taken to preserve and protect Ghana’s water resources for future generations.

6.7.1 Traditional Authority

During interviews with chiefs and traditional leaders, it was discovered that the Densu River faces a significant pollution problem. This pollution is primarily caused by illegal mining activities commonly referred to as galamsey, but traditional leaders also believe that disregard for traditional taboos contributes to the pollution of the river and its tributaries. In Akwadum, in the Eastern region, traditional leaders who were interviewed listed many taboos that were in place to protect the Densu. These include:

- No visit to the Densu River on Thursday
- Do not enter the river or cross it with a black attire
- Do not enter the river with footwear
- No bathing in the river
- Do not enter the river during menstruation (For women)
- No washing of utensils in the river
- No dumping of any waste into the river.

In Akwadum, the traditional leaders explained that when the chief of the town was enthroned in 2007, the Densu River passing through the community was drying up. The river was so shallow people could not swim in it anymore. Together with the traditional leaders and Assemblywoman, the community developed 10 taboos to prevent river pollution. The Chief then met the community and the taboos came into effect in 2008. Anyone who violates any of the taboos except entering the river on Thursday is required to pay a Ghc 30 fine but when you enter the river on Thursday which is supposed to be a day of rest for the river god, you will be required to pay for a bottle of schnapps or a sheep for cleansing and appeasing the god. The people have been made to understand that if you enter the river on Thursday you disturb the river god and make her angry. When this happens the god can plague the community or the river will dry up and the god will relocate no longer serving as a protector for the community. So far, the traditional leaders acknowledge that these taboos have been effective in Akwadum and people still obey them. According to the Chief of the community, in 2009, because of adherence to the taboos, Akwadum did not record any incident of guinea worm infestation though there was an outbreak in the country. Akwadum was rewarded by the President then for this feat. Also, the river did not dry up because of adherence to the taboos but has since recovered.

With the communities visited, it was only in Akwadum that taboos were respected. Other traditional leaders especially those in bigger towns blamed the lack of respect for taboos on the widespread of Christianity. One of the traditional leaders said:

“We are destroying the Densu. There were certain days we were forbidden from entering the river but now because of Christianity, there is no regard for such taboos. People think obeying the taboos is idol worship. That is a major reason for the destruction of the river”
(Traditional leader of Adogyiri, December 2021).

6.7.2 Ministries

According to data from the Ministries, the basin's water resources were in good condition until illegal and small-scale mining activities became widespread. Unfortunately, due to these activities, water quality has suffered, leading to numerous complaints from farmers in the area. It appears that many farmers cannot profit from their production and are instead running at a loss, which has forced them to abandon farming altogether. One of the respondents from the district department of the Ministry of Food and Agriculture reiterated these concerns.

Illegal mining (galamsey) has forced many vegetable farmers along the river to stop farming because they need clean water to irrigate their crops. The muddy water damages their pumps, leading to increased costs for pump maintenance and cleaning chemicals. This has caused some farmers to stop farming altogether.(Agric Officer, Abuakwa South Municipal, December 2021).

6.7.3 Departments and Agencies

Officials from the EPA, GWCL and the CWSA identified several issues, including the encroachment on wetlands and buffer zones and agrochemicals on farms near water bodies. They indicate that to safeguard the Densu River - a major source of water that feeds into the Weija dam - a buffer zone was created. However, due to the rapid expansion of urban areas, the buffer zone has been subjected to encroachment, which poses a significant threat to the river's health and the ecosystem it supports. Despite efforts to enforce protective measures, the unchecked development of nearby settlements has continued encroaching upon the buffer zone, putting the river and the dam at risk of contamination and degradation. This encroachment is believed to contribute to the water crises experienced in some areas of the Greater Accra Region, where consistent access to water from the Weija treatment plant is unavailable. Consequently, many people rely on water tanker services for their daily water needs.

6.7.4 Metropolitan/Municipal/District Assemblies (MMDAs)

Officers of the six Municipal and District Assemblies visited indicate that galamsey poses a significant threat to water resources in the basin, making it a primary concern for the MMDAs. Additional challenges include encroachment on wetlands and buffers, farmers cultivating along riverbanks, waste management companies discharging liquid waste into rivers, and the siting of dumpsites near the waterway. There have been reports of waste collection companies choosing to dump their waste into the river under the cover of night instead of utilising designated landfill sites for responsible waste disposal activities. This behaviour raises serious environmental and ethical concerns as it appears that these companies are prioritising short-term cost savings over implementing proper waste management practices essential for preserving our environment. In the words of one District Assembly representative:

“When you go to the areas where the rivers pass, they mostly dump their waste in the river. The waste collection companies also channel their waste into the river. There have been complaints from the Assembly members in those areas, and they even mentioned that the water was killing their poultry” (Ga West Municipal Assembly Official, December 2021)

Upon further discussions with the Assemblies, it became evident that the Densu River basin is particularly susceptible to inundation during periods of heavy rainfall. These floods not only pose a significant threat to human life but also lead to the displacement of communities residing along the riverbanks.

6.7.5 Eastern Regional Co-ordinating Council (ERCC)

The ERCC mentioned the destruction of water resources caused by illegal mining (Galamsey) as its primary concern. This activity harms water bodies and ruins agricultural land and vegetation. To tackle this issue, the ERCC focuses on controlling illegal mining in the Densu basin, allocating significant resources to the cause.

6.7.6 Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

The NGOs interviewed expressed concern about illegal mining activities by locals and foreigners and the disposal of refuse into water bodies. The respondents noted that such actions harm farming, polluting the rivers farmers rely on to water their crops. It was also discovered that many households in the Densu basin dispose off their refuse into drains and nearby water bodies, leading to the movement of solid waste into the Densu River whenever it rains. This contributes to the perennial flooding of the Densu River in some areas. According to study participants, waste dumping into drains and water bodies has become widespread due to the lack of a central container system for collecting household solid waste.

6.7.7 Private Enterprises

During interviews with private enterprises operating in the basin, it was brought to light that climate change, largely attributable to human activities like deforestation and vegetation removal, is posing a substantial threat to the region. The discussions revealed that the impact of these activities is not only limited to the environment but also to the socio-economic fabric of the region, affecting various sectors like agriculture and industry. The enterprises expressed their concerns about the long-term sustainability of their businesses and the well-being of the local communities, indicating a pressing need for immediate action to mitigate the effects of climate change. The declining groundwater levels were also a significant issue for private enterprises that rely on it for their operations. Water is crucial for many businesses. With the dwindling levels of groundwater, the cost of accessing it has increased. In some cases, private enterprises have had to dig deeper wells or invest in more boreholes to meet their water needs, which has added to their operational costs. The interviewees emphasised that lesser rainfall periods and also the construction of impermeable structures like concrete houses contribute to increased runoff, aggravating the issue of dwindling groundwater levels.

6.7.8 Farmers

During focus group discussions with farmers in the basin, they identified water pollution and the drying up of water bodies as crucial environmental issues. They unanimously agreed that illegal mining and sand-winning practices were responsible for this degradation. One participant's concern over the harmful effects of these activities which was supported by all the others was expressed as follows:

“Initially, we did not transport water sachets to the farm for consumption. We used to collect water from streams that flowed through the farm, but presently, all the water sources are contaminated,

so sending water to the farm for drinking has become necessary”
 (Participant, Focus Group Discussion, Coaltar, December 2021).

Farmers acknowledge that they have been advised against farming so close to water bodies and using agrochemicals on farms near the river due to the risk of pollution. However, they find it challenging to forego the use of agrochemicals as they result in high yields. To address this issue of pollution caused by agrochemicals, farmers agree that participating in a payment for ecosystem services programme that offers incentives in the form of farm inputs to those who opt out of using agrochemicals can be effective.

The team at the basin office works hard to address the environmental concerns raised by stakeholders. Their approach involves actively engaging with key stakeholders, attentively listening to their concerns, and taking necessary actions to mitigate issues. The office ensures that all relevant stakeholders are involved in the process, although some may be more closely engaged than others. This is dependent on the stakeholders' interests and how well they align with the work of the basin secretariat.

6.8 Relations of power, influence and engagement among stakeholders in the Pra basin

Figure 6.2: Analysis of level of engagement, power, and influence of key actors in the Pra Basin

Source: Authors construct, 2023

The power dynamics, influence, and level of engagement among different stakeholders in the Pra Basin were analysed based on the roles of stakeholders in formulating, developing, and implementing decisions related to the conservation and protection of water resources in the Pra Basin. The analysis also included the interactions of the different stakeholders with the basin secretariat in carrying on their roles in water resources management. Eden and Ackermann's (2011) model of 'power' and 'influence' relationships was adopted and modified to map the relative degrees of power and influence that actors have in the decision-making process over conservation and protection activities, as well as their level of engagement with the Pra basin secretariat. As Figure 6.2 suggests, stakeholders can be put into four main categories, I, II, III and IV. In category I, we have stakeholders whose power and influence is low. They also have low engagement levels with the basin secretariat. Such stakeholders are private enterprises, specifically small- and medium-scale, and large-scale private enterprises that use significant amounts of water in their operations. For these businesses, the key times to engage with the basin secretariat are when applying for water use permits or when the basin office monitors their operations. The monitoring process is particularly vital, as it allows the office to identify the water sources utilised by the enterprise, the number and location of boreholes operated, and the overall impact on groundwater. It is important to note that the basin office interacts more with large enterprises than with small and medium-scale enterprises, as they abstract more water and are more likely to significantly impact groundwater. One big private enterprise operating within the Pra basin admitted to having weak interaction with the basin office and the Water Resources Commission. According to the enterprise's manager, they believe that the basin office should provide more education to citizens to understand better why specific fees are required. This weak engagement between private enterprises and the basin office may ultimately hinder their ability to monitor and manage groundwater in the region properly. The enterprise manager mentioned:

“I learned of the activities of the basin office and the WRC when they contacted us. We produced water for about seven years before we heard of the Pra Basin office. We were contacted seven years into our operation, and paying the abstraction fees was difficult. I just learned that you must pay abstraction fees for drilling a borehole for drinking water production. We had to pay the penalty for defaulting” (Manager, Drinking Water Company, Pra Basin, November 2022).

In category I there is also the traditional authority. Many stakeholders interviewed agreed that the political leaders have usurped the authority of the traditional leaders, so they are no longer as powerful. Based on the data presented in Figure 6.2, it seems that there is a moderate level of interaction between the traditional authority and the basin secretariat. The secretariat officers seek support from traditional authorities when they need access to a community for any activity. Traditional leaders are involved in the community entry procedures to ensure that community leaders know the secretariat's planned activities before they are carried out. However, the Pra Basin office reports of instances where there have been conflicts of interest between traditional leaders and other stakeholders over the sale of lands, including wetlands or lands connected to water bodies. Even though the country's laws prohibit the development of wetlands, traditional leaders, who are landowners, sell them to developers. These actions by the traditional authority hinder the achievement of sustainable goals. In cases of conflict of interest, the basin office increases engagement with the traditional leaders. If a consensus cannot be reached, the basin office invokes the powers of higher authorities, such as the Ashanti Regional Co-ordinating Council, headed by the regional minister, to resolve the matter conclusively.

Category II from Figure 6.2 represents the stakeholders with low power and influence but a relatively high level of engagement. MMDAs, NGOs and the Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection (MoGCSP) belong to this category. MoGCSP appears to have a moderate level of engagement with the basin office. Data gathered from key informants indicate that though the basin secretariat may hold meetings and workshops with the MoGCSP, their participation is more critical when executing projects with a gender-focused component. Projects that aim to empower women who play important roles in water management receive special attention from the Ministry of Gender, Children, and Social Protection. As a result, whenever there is a project of that nature, the active participation of the MoGCSP is vital in ensuring that the project meets its objectives and delivers the desired results.

The MMDAs have low power and influence because they are local government agencies. Still, in terms of engagement, it appears there is regular communication between this group and the Pra basin secretariat. In a discussion with the Pra basin officers, they shared insights into the office's interactions with MMDAs.

“Usually, individuals seeking building permits involving water bodies go to the MMDAs. The applications are then referred to the Pra Basin secretariat for advice before the permit is granted or denied” (Pra Basin Officer, September 2023).

Figure 6.2 shows that stakeholders under category III include the WRC, EPA, Forestry Commission (FC), Minerals Commission (MC), LUSPA, MOFA, GWCL and the Ashanti Regional Co-ordinating Council. These stakeholders yield higher power and influence in decision-making over water resources management in the Pra basin, and they have an explicit mandate over water and water-related sectors such as the environment, mining, agriculture, and human settlements. Category III stakeholders also appear to be notable central government agencies. There is also the regional co-ordinating council that has a political mandate over administration and decision-making in the region. The basin secretariat gave details about their ongoing collaboration with these departments and agencies for public sensitisation and to combat wetland encroachment. A basin officer indicated.

“The Basin Office works together with Ghana Water Company Limited to educate the public on responsible water usage and the protection of water resources. Ghana Water Company regularly goes on state-owned radio stations in Kumasi to provide information on water-related topics, and we join them sometimes on this platform to discuss these issues” (Pra basin officer, November 2022).

Further discussions with the basin secretariat, revealed that unlike the other agencies in Category III, the Ashanti Regional Coordinating Council (ARCC) is a local government agency with relatively high influence and engagement with the basin secretariat. The basin office described situations that demand their engagement with the ARCC:

“Whenever we are faced with a critical matter concerning the encroachment of wetlands or flood hotspots, we engage with the Ashanti Regional Co-ordinating Council. They are a higher power and their expertise and experience in dealing with such issues make them invaluable partners in our efforts to address these pressing concerns. The gravity of the situation will prompt us to work with the ARCC towards practical solutions” (Pra basin Officer, September 2023).

Interviews with key informants from the different government agencies suggest that the Ministry of Food and Agriculture (MOFA) is a major water user in the basin because it relies on irrigation for crop production. As a result, the Basin Secretariat interacts more with MOFA to ensure water is used efficiently and sustainably. Agriculture also significantly impacts the state of water bodies in the country, making it essential to collaborate with the Ministry of Food and Agriculture to protect and conserve water resources.

According to officers at the Pra basin secretariat, the media is another stakeholder group that promotes sustainable water resource management. The media is represented in category IV thus stakeholders with high power and influence but low engagement level. In Figure 6.2 the media appear to have a moderate engagement level. The basin secretariat invites the media to cover and share information about workshops and activities, which helps raise public awareness about water resource issues. While radio stations are their primary point of contact, they also interact with television stations and print media, albeit less frequently. A basin officer shared his perspective on their interactions with the media.

“The secretariat used to visit a privately owned radio station in Kumasi. There is a programme called "Environment" aired on the station, where we discuss water-related issues. However, due to other equally important assignments, we are unable to visit the radio station regularly nowadays” (Basin officer, Pra basin, October 2023).

6.9 Public participation in the Pra basin

The basin secretariat facilitates public participation through community engagements that target areas with specific water issues, such as water pollution and flooding. Through education and outreach, the secretariat encourages responsible use of water resources. It is important to note that community engagements are not solely organised by the secretariat, as other organisations partner with them to host these events. For example, in the Bosomtwe District, regular community engagements are held to address concerns related to Lake Bosomtwe. These efforts are led by the Man and Biosphere (MAB) programme, supported by UNESCO. The MAB programme works closely with the local community to identify water-related challenges and develop strategies to address them. The Secretariat mentions that as a result of the MAB project, every year and almost every month, community engagements are organised in the communities around Lake Bosomtwe.

Interviews with the basin secretariat and focus group discussions revealed that the Lake and its environs are under the management of the Lake Bosomtwe Community Resource Management Area (CREMA) and supervised by the Pra Basin Secretariat. The CREMA is a community-based organisation, governed by an executive body and a constitution that outlines their activities and regulations (Dzekoto & Bosu, 2018). According to UNESCO reports, the establishment of the CREMA in 2014 involved transferring management authority to local communities to oversee natural resources on their land for sustainable development. This means that community members are actively involved in the decision-making process to preserve the beauty of the lake and its associated ecosystems, and to safeguard them from harm.

6.10 Environmental problems perceived by stakeholders in the Pra basin

The Pra Basin is known for its remarkable ecological diversity and cultural significance. It is home to forests, expansive wetlands, and vital waterways. However, beneath its scenic beauty lies an array of environmental challenges that deeply resonate with stakeholders across various sectors. From water pollution and encroachment to climate change impacts, human activities and natural forces increasingly threaten the basin's delicate balance. Understanding stakeholders' perceptions is crucial for addressing these environmental issues effectively.

This section examines and brings to light the environmental concerns that have garnered the attention of stakeholders and impacted the diverse stakeholder groups in the basin. The analysis will delve into the complexities of the ecosystem and explore the interconnections between human activities, environmental factors, and the ecological balance in the Pra basin. This segment compares the environmental concerns from the point of view of the experts and the laypeople.

6.10.1 Traditional Authority

According to some traditional leaders, the pollution of pure and secure water sources in the Pra basin caused by illegal mining is a major concern. These leaders believe that the government is not providing enough resources to tackle the issue of illegal mining. The younger generation is increasingly turning to illegal mining as a means of sustaining themselves due to the lack of employment opportunities in the country. This unfortunate trend is exacerbating the depletion of water resources, posing a serious threat to the environment and the well-being of local communities.

6.10.2 Ministry of Food and Agriculture (MOFA)

In their reports, the Ministry of Food and Agriculture (MOFA) raised concerns about water pollution, which has decreased irrigated land. They highlighted that despite being predominantly rainfed, agriculture remains a major water consumer in the nation and the basin. Unfortunately, illegal mining activities have resulted in water contamination from rivers, rendering it unfit for irrigation and necessitating many farmers to switch to non-irrigation-dependent crops. MOFA acknowledges that using agrochemicals near water bodies can lead to pollution of surface water sources through runoff. Therefore, they advise farmers against using agrochemicals on farms near water bodies and the dumping of used agrochemical bottles in water bodies.

6.10.3 Government Departments and Agencies

According to government departments and agencies such as GWCL, LUSPA and the EPA, the issue of water pollution is often exacerbated by illegal and small-scale mining activities. Such practices significantly impact the quality of water resources, leading to serious environmental and health concerns. Measures must, therefore, be taken to address this problem and prevent further damage to the precious water ecosystems. Sand winning, logging, and the use of agrochemicals on farms close to water bodies were also identified as harmful to water resources. An officer from the Ghana Water Company Limited explained:

“Some time ago, we went to a community called Apenteng to monitor activities there, and we realised they were clearing land which was adding much silt into the river. Also, the chemicals used for farming were causing pollution” (Water Quality Officer, Ghana Water Company Limited, Kumasi).

Interviewees from government departments and agencies mentioned a significant obstacle: the public's insufficient knowledge and understanding of water resources management. Participants noted that inadequate education on water-related issues hinders individuals' ability to make informed decisions and take necessary actions to protect and preserve this critical resource. This knowledge gap affects everyday choices and undermines broader efforts to implement effective water conservation policies and practices, ultimately threatening the sustainability of the water supply.

“The problem is, are the people aware of the consequences of what they are doing? Someone should have informed them, but they have not been informed. The Pra Basin Secretariat should inform the public, but they lack the resources” (Member of the Pra Basin Board, November 2022).

6.10.4 Metropolitan/Municipal/District Assemblies

The encroachment upon wetlands and the buffer zones surrounding rivers was identified as a significant concern for MMDAs. Interview participants identified that these vital ecological features serve as essential habitats for many species and play a critical role in regulating the water cycle. The degradation of these areas can lead to significant adverse impacts, including increased flooding and erosion, reduced water quality, and loss of biodiversity. One of the interview participants noted:

“There are numerous locations where MMDAs are unaware of developments and large buildings constructed on reclaimed wetlands. In my case, where I live within the KMA, the Assembly was unaware that the area had been developed for over 11 years. It was only when the landlords, including myself, sought approval for a layout that a

private person had prepared that the KMA became aware of the existence of that community” (High Profile Officer, Asante Akyem Central Municipal Assembly, August 2022).

In certain areas such as the Bosomtwe District and the Atwima Nwabiagya North District, interviewees confirm the existence and enforcement of by-laws to protect water bodies. These by-laws were established by the District Assemblies. In these districts, the Environmental Health Departments of the Assemblies have assigned staff to conduct inspections in various communities. If someone is found guilty of not respecting the buffer zones, they are fined. This has helped reduce the incidence of encroachment. In the case of the Bosomtwe district, the by-laws protect Lake Bosomtwe and the Streams that join the lake. For the Atwima Nwabiagya North District, the by-laws protect the River Offin and the catchment around the Barekese dam which draws raw water from the River Offin for treatment.

It was also revealed that farmers who cultivate in areas near water sources use agro-chemicals that eventually end up in the water. This practice not only harms the environment but also puts the health of those who rely on the water at risk. Others also acquire land near water bodies for purposes other than farming, such as residential. In the Twifo Atti Morkwa district, data from the Assembly's representative corroborated during the focus group discussion revealed that some individuals acquired land near the River Pra in Twifo Praso. Against the advice from the District Assembly, they decided to build residential facilities on those lands, believing the lands were not 'so close' to the river to suffer from floods. However, in the subsequent years, there have been instances where the River Pra overflowed its banks and destroyed houses built in that area. Some people have relocated to other areas, while others are still adamant and would leave only when it is flooded and return later when the waters have subsided.

Representatives from the MMDAs also mentioned the issue of illegal and small-scale mining activities. Additionally, towns near water bodies have been affected by sand winning. Illegal logging and unapproved fishing methods have been ongoing issues, as well as effluent discharge into smaller water bodies. These activities have further deteriorated the condition of water bodies such as streams. In addition, environmental awareness among citizens in the basin is weak.

6.10.5 Ashanti Regional Coordinating Council (ARCC)

According to the ARCC, the prevalent issue of illegal mining has led to the significant pollution of various water bodies. This activity, often unregulated and driven by the pursuit of precious

minerals, involves using harmful chemicals such as mercury and cyanide. The use of these substances results in severe contamination of nearby rivers and streams. The chemicals seep into the groundwater and flow into larger water bodies, creating a toxic environment detrimental to human health and aquatic life. One of the most affected water sources is the Pra River. This river, once a vital source of clean drinking water for numerous communities, has become heavily polluted due to the runoff from illegal mining operations. Heavy metals and other pollutants in the water have reached alarming levels, rendering it unsafe for consumption. People who once relied on the Pra River for their daily water needs now face significant health risks, including skin diseases. The pollution of the Pra River also has severe implications for agriculture because farmers cannot use the water for irrigation due to the contamination. As part of its efforts, the ARCC has provided logistical support to the security services in the fight against galamsey.

6.10.6 Non-Governmental Organisations

Again, activities of illegal and small-scale mining operators in the Pra basin were listed as the most prominent environmental concern for NGOs in the basin. A section of miners who mine along water bodies, and those who do not mine along water bodies end up discharging the residual water from the mining activities into water bodies. One participant explained the prevalence of mining along water bodies. He noted that:

“The sudden surge in river mining is due to the widespread knowledge that gold is typically found in riverbeds and along the banks of rivers. It has become common knowledge amongst prospectors and miners that these areas are more likely to contain valuable deposits, leading to increased activity in these regions. They say for the gold, the nearer you get to the river, the richer you get” (Senior officer of AROCHA Ghana, December 2021).

6.10.7 Private Enterprises

Within the space of private enterprises, it was released that the basin secretariat, and the WRC are not adequately conveying their initiatives regarding water resources management to the enterprises. Furthermore, it was noted that the secretariat has not emphasised citizens' crucial role in water resource management. This lack of effective communication and education hinders progress towards sustainable water management practices.

6.10.8 Farmers

According to the farmers who participated in the focus group discussions there is a gradual decline in the water levels of many water bodies. This phenomenon, known as receding water levels, is becoming a growing concern for many communities.

One of the farmers noted that:

“The level of the lake Bosomtwe keeps reducing because of climate change and evaporation due to the cutting down of trees around the lake. Also, some farms are located on the mountaintop around the lake. When there is rain, it washes down soil into the lake which causes siltation” (Participant, Focus Group Discussion at Abono-Bosomtwe, November 2022).

Pollution of water bodies due to illegal and small-scale mining and waste disposal were identified as environmental concerns by the farmers. Some farmers commented on these issues:

“The galamsey we used to do before the Chinese came did not pollute water resources because we did not have the machines. About 10-12 years ago, when the Chinese came with their machines, they have been able to destroy all water bodies. The machines are in the water directly” (Participant, Focus Group Discussion, Bedieso, December 2022).

“Because most households have directed sewage into the streams, all streams have now turned into gutters” (Participant, Focus Group Discussion, Bedieso, December 2022).

6.10.9 Fishermen

According to fishermen in the Pra basin, pollution of water bodies caused by illegal, small-scale mining and household wastewater has affected their lives. Some fishermen talked about the pollution of the Pra River and its effects:

“At first, if we do not get enough fish from the sea, we go to fish in the Pra River to supplement the little catch from the sea. Now we can wake up at 3 am and go to the Pra Estuary, but you won't get any fish” (Participant, Focus Group Discussion at Kumunumu- Shama, December 2022).

“At first, we used water from the Pra River to bathe, cook and even drink water from the river. We also used water from the Pra to wash the fish we catch from the sea. When the Pra travels and gets to this place, it settles. The pressure with which it flows slows down, so even young children could fetch water from it, but now when you fetch and bathe

with it, you get skin rashes” (Participant, Focus Group Discussion at Kumunumu- Shama, December 2022).

“We used to have fishermen who fish in the Pra River, but because the river is polluted, the fishermen have now joined illegal mining activities. The fishermen who now do galamsey can swim and dive, so when some of the mining materials fall into the river, they are the ones who swim to collect them” (Participant, Focus Group Discussion, Bankyease, December 2022).

It is worth noting that water bodies in the basin, such as rivers, streams and lakes, are particularly susceptible to siltation. This occurs when sediment and other debris settle at the bottom of the body of water, leading to a buildup that can harm aquatic life and affect water quality.

6.11 Conclusion

This chapter examined the stakeholder dynamics within the Densu and Pra River basins, where various stakeholders are involved in making critical water resource management decisions. This overview included an examination of the roles of key stakeholders. The specific roles and responsibilities outlined in the operational guidelines of the basin board were emphasized, as they serve as the core of the board's administration. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of these boards in carrying out their duties is contingent on the resources at their disposal.

Stakeholder engagement was done, which aligns with the study's objective of examining stakeholder dynamics. This analysis dissected the level of engagement, power, and influence wielded by key actors within the Densu and Pra basins, providing an understanding of the dynamics at play. By exploring the relationships, conflicts, and cooperation among stakeholders, the study sought to uncover insights that can inform more effective strategies for preserving the ecological integrity of water resources in these river basins. The study revealed that many stakeholders with high power and influence also had a high stakeholder engagement level. Stakeholder engagement is high among the stakeholders with an explicit mandate to protect and conserve the environment. This promotes collaboration towards achieving optimal water resource management and minimises stakeholder conflicts. The MMDAs, though, have a mandate to protect the environment in their locality and have less power and influence over water management decisions in the basins because they operate at the local level of governance.

The chapter's findings suggest that the involvement of government authorities in the basin offices' engagements has led to significant information gain. This outcome is primarily

attributable to the fact that the stakeholders involved in these engagements are predominantly representatives from various government institutions. These government stakeholders bring a wealth of knowledge, resources, and expertise, enabling a more informed dialogue on water resources management. Their active participation ensures that critical data, policies, and regulatory frameworks are thoroughly discussed and integrated into decision-making processes. Consequently, the enhanced flow of information and the alignment of strategic objectives among government entities have strengthened the overall effectiveness of proposals made by the basin boards regarding water resource management. Stakeholder meetings have proven to be very productive occasions where individual stakeholders introduce one another to new ideas through exchanging knowledge. This exchange of knowledge helps to increase the knowledge level of actors, particularly regarding the sustainable handling of water resources.

Again, engaging the community and media actively empowers people to protect water resources in their locality. Through stakeholder interactions and collaboration, the Secretariat and partners work together to achieve their shared goals of promoting sustainable water management practices that benefit both the environment and those who rely on these resources.

The benefits of stakeholder meetings extend beyond the individual actors involved. They also benefit the Densu and Pra Basin offices, as they provide a platform to receive support from other state agencies to carry out their activities. This further supports the idea in the literature that participation sets the foundation for cooperation between actors in the handling of water resources.

In this chapter, we have learned that the concerns raised by individual stakeholders are mainly directed towards the actions of traditional authorities, small-scale and illegal miners, poor farming and household practices, and uncontrolled development, leading to encroachment. Actors in these spaces tend to prioritise economic gains over environmental conservation, resulting in conflicts of interest with other stakeholders who value the preservation of the environment. It is evident that the pursuit of profit by these mining groups comes at the expense of environmental sustainability, a critical issue that needs to be addressed to ensure a harmonious coexistence between all stakeholders.

All stakeholders unanimously agreed that illegal and small-scale mining activities pose the greatest threat to water resources in both the Pra and Densu basins. These environmental concerns should be addressed promptly to ensure the long-term viability of the basins'

ecosystems and the welfare of the surrounding communities who rely on them. Taking action to mitigate these issues is vital to safeguarding the country's ecological integrity and preserving its natural resources for future generations.

CHAPTER SEVEN

BARRIERS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR EFFECTIVE WATER RESOURCES MANAGEMENT IN THE DENSU AND PRA RIVER BASINS

7.1 Introduction

In this chapter, I present an overview of the significant barriers to effective water resources management in the Densu and Pra River basins, as identified by stakeholders. This detailed analysis of the barriers highlights their impact on managing water resources in the two basins. Furthermore, there is an in-depth examination of the opportunities within each basin for enhancing water resources management. By exploring the multifaceted challenges and promising opportunities surrounding the management of water resources within the Densu and Pra River basins, this chapter aims to develop a comprehensive understanding of the complexities involved in effectively stewarding these vital natural resources. It aims to offer valuable insights on how to improve the situation. The analysis of barriers to and opportunities for effective water resources management is presented for the Densu basin first and then for the Pra basin.

Table 7.1: Summary of interview questions and responses for barriers to effective water resources management

Theme	Questions	Responses
Problems with water policies	What do you see as the largest problem - if any - with Ghana's river basin policies today?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The buffer zone policy needs to be converted into law for effective enforcement. - The current policy creates ambiguity for primary stakeholders due to varying interpretations. - The policy should adapt to environmental and social changes
Constraints	What are the constraints faced by your institution?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Logistical Constraints: Basin officers previously used personal or public transport for monitoring; one vehicle now available for the secretariat. Lack of tools to measure all water quality parameters. - Inadequate Personnel: From 2011 to 2016, only two officers; capacity increased to five in 2017 (three technical staff, a cleaner, and a driver) but still insufficient given the basin's size. - Inadequate Funds: Insufficient funds

		to sustain awareness campaigns on water issues and WRC activities.
Challenges with Policy Implementation	Why are policy instruments not working effectively?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inadequate Awareness: Many target groups are unaware of the policy instruments, leading to low compliance. - Organizational Implementation Issues: WRC needs to be seen and heard more. - Target Group Behavior: Resistance to paying water charges and disregard for farming restrictions near water bodies. - Corruption: Bribery makes it difficult to punish offenders.
Resource Availability for Policy Implementation	Are all necessary resources (financial, human, political) available for implementing water policies?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Logistics and Personnel: WRC-Pra Basin secretariat lacks adequate personnel and logistics. - Financial Constraints: EPA relies on internally generated funds, with no government subvention, limiting its capacity. - Municipal Challenges: Assemblies have sufficient staff and political support, but limited resources for development programmes are limited. - Low Political Support: Chiefs and political leaders show little commitment to halting illegal mining.

Source: Densu Field Data Collection, December 2021
Pra Field Data Collection, December 2022

Table 7.2: Summary of interview questions and responses for opportunities for effective water resources management

Theme	Questions	Responses
Opportunities for Effective Water Resources Management	What opportunities exist to improve the organisation's performance?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration with other organisations to fill resource gaps. - Involvement of police, military, and taskforces in enforcing environmental laws. - Donor support from organizations like DANIDA, UN-Habitat, etc. - Corporate sponsorship (e.g., Guinness Ghana Limited) for

		<p>water management activities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adequate laws, regulations, and policies to support water management efforts. - WRC and basin offices developing basin IWRM plans for water management. - Local Water Committee (LWC) concept to decentralise water resources management. - Research institutions (e.g., universities, CSIR Water Research Institute) support.
<p>Instruments for Improving Water Quality and Avoiding Scarcity</p>	<p>What instrument(s) would work to improve water quality and avoid water scarcity?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - District Assembly stakeholder consultations through town hall meetings. - District Assembly taskforces, like Shama's river guards. - Communities becoming aware of water pollution and climate change and supporting tree maintenance to protect rivers.

Source: Densu Field Data Collection, December 2021
Pra Field Data Collection, December 2022

7.2 Barriers to effective water resources management in the Densu Basin

The Densu Basin, a critical watershed in Ghana, serves as a vital source of water for domestic, agricultural, and industrial purposes for a significant portion of the population. Despite its importance, the basin faces numerous challenges that hinder effective water resources management. This section examines the critical obstacles and highlights the need for coordinated efforts to ensure the long-term viability of this crucial water source. The barriers to effective water resources management include (i) gap in policy implementation, (ii) inadequate funding, (iii) personnel deficit, (iv) logistical constraints, (v) low levels of awareness, (vi) negative behaviour of people and companies, (vii) weak law enforcement, (viii) conflicting interests and priorities, and (ix) low political commitment. The following text elaborates on each of these barriers.

7.2.1 Policy implementation gap

The study discovered that the current buffer zone policy has not been enacted into law, which severely undermines its enforcement and effectiveness. However, the potential of buffer zones to mitigate pollution is significant. Buffer zones are integral to sustainable water management practices. They serve as natural barriers that intercept surface runoff, trap sediments, and absorb nutrients before they reach water bodies. The creation of buffer zones is meant to regulate human activities, preserve vegetation, enhance water quality, and maintain the functionality of water bodies. In the Densu Basin, implementing buffer zones is particularly vital due to the region's susceptibility to pollution from various sources, including agricultural runoff, industrial discharges, and domestic wastewater. Establishing and maintaining effective buffer zones can mitigate these impacts, thereby enhancing the resilience of the basin's water resources. In spite of the recognised benefits of buffer zones the current policy framework lacks the necessary legal backing to ensure its effective enforcement. While well-intentioned, the existing buffer zone policy remains a guideline rather than a legislated mandate. This lack of legal status means there is no binding requirement for stakeholders, including landowners, developers, and traditional authorities, to comply with the buffer zone provisions. The absence of legal enforcement leads to weak compliance because, without the force of law, compliance with buffer zone guidelines is largely voluntary, which often results in inconsistent application and adherence, with many actors neglecting the maintenance of buffer zones due to perceived inconvenience or economic costs. According to the basin secretariat, landowners and developers tend to resist implementing buffer zones due to perceived restrictions on land use and potential financial losses. Without legal obligations, efforts to negotiate and persuade these stakeholders to adopt buffer zone practices often face significant resistance.

In 2014, the country put together a minerals and mining policy to address the challenge of activities of illegal miners, which have added to the environmental and social costs of mining due to the extensive destruction and pollution of water bodies. However, interviews with key informants and focus group discussions reveal that the country has been unsuccessful in implementing this policy against illegal mining activities. Now, illegal, and small-scale mining activities are more widespread. Interviewees and participants attributed the widespread illegal mining activities to the youth's high unemployment rate. Also, there is poor collaboration among stakeholders such as traditional leaders, the Minerals Commission, WRC, EPA, District Assemblies and others. The lack of job opportunities drives many young people to seek alternative means of income, often leading them to engage in illegal mining operations.

Although fraught with dangers and illegality, this sector offers immediate financial benefits that are otherwise unattainable. The allure of quick money becomes a significant pull factor, overshadowing the long-term health risks and environmental consequences associated with these activities. An official from one of the NGOs interviewed commented:

“For the unemployed youth, engaging in illegal mining is a means of survival. So, you can stop them today and they will return tomorrow”
(High profile officer, AROCHA Ghana, December 2021).

Another critical element fuelling illegal and small-scale mining is the financial backing provided by interested parties, including foreigners and politicians. Foreigners bring in capital, expertise, and advanced equipment, which significantly enhance the efficiency and scale of illegal mining operations. Their involvement includes providing machinery which local miners would not have the means to procure on their own. According to one participant,

“The Chinese have introduced an equipment called ‘chanfan’ which the locals are now using and that is what has caused a lot of water pollution. Before the influx of the Chinese, most of the mining we did, did not pollute water resources” (Participant, FGD, Coaltar, December 2021)

This technological edge allows illegal miners to extract resources more rapidly and in greater quantities, exacerbating environmental degradation and making enforcement more challenging. Politicians are frequently implicated in supporting illegal mining activities, driven by various motivations including financial gain, political leverage, and voter support. These individuals may provide direct financial assistance, legal protection, or logistical support to illegal miners. In some cases, politicians exploit their influence to shield illegal mining operations from law enforcement actions, ensuring that these activities continue unabated.

7.2.2 Limited financial resources

The Densu Basin Secretariat manages and protects the Densu River and its surrounding basin. However, it faces significant challenges due to limited financial resources. The primary function of the basin secretariat is to monitor the health of the water bodies within the basin. Regular monitoring is crucial for assessing water quality, identifying pollution sources, and taking corrective actions. However, limited financial resources hinder the Secretariat's ability to conduct frequent and thorough monitoring. This inadequacy results in a lack of up-to-date data, making it challenging to respond promptly to emerging issues. The Densu Basin Board has developed various strategies aimed at achieving water conservation. Programmes such as community education and pollution control measures often stall due to financial limitations.

“The Secretariat faces operational challenges that stem from financial constraints. For example, the maintenance of equipment and the day-to-day administrative costs are all affected” (Officer, Densu Basin Secretariat, December 2021).

Based on documentary evidence, the government has been allocating less than 15 percent of the total annual financial requirements of the Water Resources Commission. Coupled with this, the transfer of funds from the government to the Water Resources Commission is often delayed, further exacerbating the already limited resources available for managing the Densu basin. An officer of the basin remarked:

“The Government of Ghana (GOG) has been releasing its funds later in the year. From what I learnt, this year, the funds were disbursed in November or later. So, the question is, how can a government institution like the basin office function efficiently and effectively without financial resources for almost a year” (High profile officer, Densu basin board, December 2021).

The Water Resources Commission (WRC) has reported that while the government pays staff salaries on time, funds from the central government for WRC operations, including the basin offices, have been arriving late. Between 2019 and 2022, central government funds were received between October and December. An officer from the WRC believes that the country's economic challenges may explain this phenomenon:

“There is no money in the system. The country itself is facing major economic challenges, so we can say this is expected” (High profile officer, Water Resources Commission, December 2022).

Besides central government transfers, the WRC relies on external agencies and Internally Generated Funds (IGFs) to finance its activities. However, there is a need to increase the mobilisation of the internally generated funds. Unfortunately, only a portion of these funds can be retained by the WRC for its operations. Since August 2017, the WRC returns 34 percent of its IGFs to the central government. This means that 34 pesewas are returned to the government for every cedi generated internally, while the remaining 66 percent is still kept with the Bank of Ghana. To access the 66 percent, the Commission has to undergo a rigorous process of demonstrating its ability to spend and provide detailed information on how the funds will be utilised. Therefore, the funds are not readily available, and proper application can take time and effort. An officer of the Densu basin secretariat noted:

“When we generate our Internally Generated Funds (IGF), we do not keep it with us. Instead, we give it to the Bank of Ghana, which deducts their percentage, and we receive the remainder. However, even with the rest, we must go through a bureaucratic process to show evidence of how we intend to spend the funds before we can access them” (Officer Densu Basin Secretariat, December 2021).

It is important to note that funds from external agencies in the form of grants formed the largest Water Resources Commission funding source. However, external transfers to the Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) sector have gradually shifted from external grants to loans, as Ghana has achieved a middle-income status. An officer of the basin commented on the decline in external funds:

“We used to organise community awareness programmes, but unfortunately, we cannot continue with them anymore due to the lack of funding. DANIDA, UN-Habitat, and Switzerland were some organisations that had provided funding for our projects, but their support has ended. We had plans to initiate something in the basin with the grant from Switzerland, but it is also no longer available” (High Profile Officer, Densu Basin Secretariat, December 2021).

The basin secretariat explains that after receiving funding from DANIDA, the secretariat was able to allocate resources to enhance stakeholder collaboration for efficient water resources management within the basin. Unfortunately, with the cessation of funding, the Secretariat's capacity to actively engage stakeholders through regular board meetings, workshops, and collaborative projects has been significantly constrained.

7.2.3 Personnel deficit

The basin secretariat currently operates with only four working staff members. This limited workforce significantly hampers the secretariat's ability to fulfil its duties efficiently and effectively. The scarcity of personnel means that the existing staff members are often overburdened, struggling to manage the various tasks and responsibilities of maintaining the basin's operations. To mitigate this shortfall in human resources, the secretariat usually relies on the support of basin board members. These board members, however, are already committed to their respective roles and responsibilities within their institutions. Their primary duties often consume most of their time and energy, leaving them with limited capacity to assist the secretariat. Despite their willingness to help, the board members' contributions are constrained by their other professional obligations. Also, the secretariat relies on student interns from local universities to fill in as staff members. At other times, the secretariat works with former board members who have gone on retirement. This reliance on external support underscores a critical challenge faced by the basin secretariat: the need for a more robust staffing structure. In addition to the personnel deficit, the Densu basin grapples with a high staff turnover rate, a challenge exacerbated by the unattractive working conditions in the public sector. These conditions often fail to provide the incentives and benefits necessary to retain skilled professionals. As a result, the few qualified and trained staff members that the basin office manages to recruit are swiftly absorbed by the private sector, which offers more competitive salaries and better career advancement opportunities. This constant drain of talent weakens the capacity of the basin office to effectively carry out its responsibilities. The loss of experienced staff disrupts continuity and institutional knowledge. Consequently, the basin office is left in a perpetual state of rebuilding its team, hindering its ability to achieve its objectives and fulfil its mandate. A basin officer stated:

“We are facing human resource challenges. I have hired assistants with the expectation that they will eventually take over the care of the basin because no one can hold on forever. At some point, one may resign, retire or be unable to continue working due to sickness or an accident. However, it is frustrating when new employees join the secretariat and leave shortly afterwards because they have found something more attractive elsewhere” (Basin officer, Densu, December 2021).

7.2.4 Logistical constraints

To ensure the basin secretariat is productive and effectively discharges its duties, acquiring the necessary equipment is imperative, as the current logistics are inadequate. The secretariat faces challenges that hinder its ability to perform optimally, primarily due to insufficient and outdated

equipment. One of the most pressing needs is the acquisition of an additional vehicle. The current car is unreliable, frequently breaking down and causing delays in field operations. A new, dependable vehicle is essential for the secretariat to conduct timely site visits, sample collection, and emergency responses. Ensuring consistent mobility is crucial for effective monitoring and quick intervention in case of any issues affecting water quality and quantity. The secretariat requires modern multi-parameter meters to accurately measure various water quality parameters, such as pH, conductivity, and dissolved oxygen levels. These devices are essential for obtaining precise and reliable data, which is critical for making informed decisions regarding water management. Currently, all staff members are using their personal computers for work-related tasks. This situation is far from ideal, as it can lead to security risks, inefficiency, and inconsistency in data handling. Providing dedicated computers for each staff member would enhance productivity, ensure data security, and improve overall workflow. In addition to technical equipment, the secretariat also needs tools to enhance public engagement and awareness campaigns. A Public Address (PA) system, a projector and a projector screen are vital for conducting educational workshops, community outreaches, and public presentations. These tools will help the secretariat effectively communicate the importance of water conservation and protection.

7.2.5 Low level of awareness of policy instruments

Through interviews conducted in the Densu basin, it has been revealed that residents and private businesses in the area need more knowledge of the various water policy instruments to safeguard and conserve the basin's water resources. These policy instruments are crucial in ensuring the preservation of water resources in the region. For instance, the buffer zone policy requires individuals to maintain a distance between their activities and the water body. Unfortunately, most residents and enterprises are unaware of this requirement, which poses a significant challenge to effectively managing the Densu River basin. A member of the Densu basin board expressed concern about this need for more awareness. He said:

“People are not aware of the things they are doing. For example, people siting buildings and commercial activities close to the Densu at Weija must learn how much their activities pollute the water. Nonetheless, a natural cleaning system enhanced in the Weija Lake supports water treatment in the dam” (Member of Densu Basin Board, December 2021).

Another individual participating in the interviews provided her input on the topic of low levels of environmental consciousness in the basin.

“The environmental awareness among citizens is low. Awareness level could be higher among citizens, even though, nationally, the government is doing something to protect the waterbodies by using security forces, we need more sensitisation and education at the local level” (High Profile Officer, New Juaben South Municipal Assembly, December 2021).

It was discovered that the low level of awareness about environmental issues in the basin can be attributed to the inability of the basin secretariat and other environmental institutions to create and sustain effective awareness campaigns. This failure stems from various factors, including inadequate funding and personnel. Another cause is rapid urbanisation, which disconnects people from nature, reducing their awareness of environmental issues and the impact of their actions on the environment. Also, there is a cultural attitude among Ghanaians where we place low value on environmental stewardship, which hinders the adoption of eco-friendly practices. Furthermore, among citizens, economic development and immediate financial concerns take precedence over environmental conservation, leading to neglect of sustainable practices.

7.2.6 Negative behaviour of people and companies

The success of water resources management decisions relies heavily on the attitude of the individuals and organisations that these decisions target. It was discovered that skill, capacity and will are significant factors that influence the behaviour of the target group in the Densu basin towards water resources management. Some farmers in the basin expressed concerns about the fact that they have less capacity to adopt and sustain specific measures though they have received the skills from the basin secretariat and other stakeholders to help protect water bodies. For instance, farmers close to water bodies have cited agroforestry, which involves planting trees among food crops, as a problematic measure to adopt. These farmers argue that even when they adopt this measure, landowners complain and prevent them from doing so since the farmlands belong to them. If the farmers resist the landowners, they risk losing their land. In light of these challenges, the farmers suggest that the basin secretariat and the Ministry of Food and Agriculture should involve chiefs and landowners who have higher capacity when educating farmers about practices that will preserve the water bodies, such as growing trees around the water bodies. During the focus group discussions in the basin, a participant shared the following comment:

“We, the farmers, intentionally leave the trees around the water bodies. We sometimes plant trees around the water, but the problem is that after

planting, the landowners would come and cut down the trees. The farmers are willing, but the landowners and chiefs are not helping” (Participant FGD, Coaltar, December 2021).

Participants agreed that water resources and the environment are critical components for the survival of every living organism on the planet. However, it is disturbing that many people and companies are unwilling to take the necessary steps to protect them. This unwillingness to comply with environmental laws and regulations remains a significant issue that requires urgent attention. Although the country has good laws and policies to safeguard these resources, recalcitrant citizens and companies who act with impunity often undermine their implementation. This behaviour has far-reaching consequences that affect the environment, human health, and the economy. Some participants shared their thoughts on citizens' attitudes towards environmental protection.

“Also, our attitudes towards waterbodies. Sometimes we do all these sensitisations yet still some have decided that no matter what they will dump refuse into the rivers and at the end of the day when the drains are choked, and it rains the whole place gets flooded so I think we should change our attitude” (High Profile Officer, New Juaben South Municipal Assembly, December 2021)

“If you go and educate them and then you sit back and give yourself a few months, you see them going back and doing the same old thing. Especially in this area where mining has been a critical issue in disturbing our water resources, they are so recalcitrant that if you do not push them, they will always go back” (High Profile Officer of NGO, Kyebi, December 2021).

7.2.7 Political power and citizen influence

In Ghana's political environment, many politicians prioritise retaining power, leading to decisions that prioritise initiatives with high visibility and appeal to the electorate and specific constituencies (Mosello et al., 2017). Recognising the politician's reliance on electoral support, citizens have developed a strategy to hold politicians accountable: they threaten to withhold their votes unless their demands for certain decisions are met. This tactic leverages the politician's primary fear—losing power—and turns it into a driving force for either positive or negative action. Before the 2020 elections, illegal miners threatened to vote against the ruling party in the 2020 elections if there was a continued fight against illegal mining by security forces. This made the country's president reiterate that threats of losing the election will not stop the galamsey fight. (Ansah & Wiafe, 2017). It appears that withholding votes remains a

potent tool for citizens in an attempt to weaken politicians' commitment towards protecting and conserving water resources.

Recently, a case of illegal dumping of refuse into the Nsukwao river led to legal action against the perpetrators. However, despite the evidence, the individuals involved were released without significant consequences because apparently, the people threatened some political leaders. An officer of the Municipal Assembly explains:

“Relatives of the perpetrators gathered, walked into the Municipal Chief Executive’s office and threatened him that if they did not release the culprits, they would demonstrate against him for him to be sacked or vote against the government in power” (High Profile Officer, New Juaben South Municipal Assembly, December 2021).

7.2.8 Weak law enforcement

The study revealed that despite regulations aimed at protecting water quality and controlling pollution, their effectiveness is often undermined by weak enforcement. The study identified instances where high political figures have stopped efforts at protecting the Weija Lake and the Densu Delta. A member of the Densu Basin board recalled one of such experiences in his line of duty:

“Some time ago, during our demolition exercise in Weija, we encountered a situation where we were pulling down structures encroaching on the buffer zone. Then, we received a call indicating that a minister's relative had a building in the same area where we were working. The call asked us to exercise patience and assured us they would investigate the matter. As a result, we could not go ahead with the demolition. Even though we had done our homework and were already working, a call from ‘above’ instructed us to stop” (Member of the Densu Basin Board, December 2021).

Interviewees from various Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies (MMDAs) also expressed concern about their inability to enforce local by-laws in the face of political interference. For instance, participants discussed cases where they would arrest an individual for violating a by-law, only to be forced to release them due to pressure from ‘above’. One participant summed up the frustration felt by many MMDAs in this way:

“In 2016, a court was scheduled to convene in the morning where the judge planned to impose fines on those found guilty of dumping waste into the Nsukwao River. Failure to pay the penalties would result in prosecution. However, the politicians intervened. Consequently, the

judge was transferred, and the court proceedings were suspended”
(High Profile Officer, New Juaben South Municipal Assembly,
December 2021).

Law enforcement is an effective way of holding people accountable for their actions. In Ghana, there are several laws in place to protect water resources. However, enforcing existing regulations has proven ineffective, posing a significant challenge. According to interview participants, Ghana faces a general problem enforcing environmental laws. This issue is primarily caused by political interference and interference from other influential people, such as traditional leaders. While public institutions are willing to do their job and ensure that those who defy the laws are dealt with, politicians often intervene to stop the action. Also, traditional leaders such as chiefs are known to plead for wrongdoers, further hindering the enforcement of regulations.

7.2.9 Conflicting interests and priorities

The Densu basin supports diverse stakeholders, including local communities, farmers, industries, and governmental bodies. Each group relies on the Densu River and its tributaries for livelihoods, economic activities, and sustenance. However, this multiplicity of reliance sometimes leads to conflicting interests and priorities.

According to reports by the Forestry Commission and A ROCHA Ghana, in 2016, the government promised to establish a mining company in Abuakwa South Municipality to mine bauxite in the Atewa forest, a forest reserve in the basin. This caused much concern among environmentalists and stakeholders in the basin since the forest is home to a diverse range of plants and animals and is the source of the Densu, Birim and Ayensu rivers. The Ghana Integrated Aluminum Development Corporation (GIADEC) was later formed in 2017 to manage the bauxite mine operation in the forest. However, many stakeholders in the basin disapproved this arrangement since GIADEC started clearing roads to the forest to make way for the mine in 2019.

Interviews with AROCHA Ghana revealed that environmentalists and non-governmental organisations such as AROCHA Ghana have been vocal and opposing the bauxite mine. They have even taken the government to court over this matter. The government argues that establishing the bauxite mine is necessary to create more jobs for the unemployed youth in the country. However, government agencies responsible for the environment conducted a socio-economic study, which reported that the country would make more money if the Atewa forest

is kept as an ecotourism site rather than mining bauxite. In addition to creating jobs, the government in power said it would leverage Ghana's bauxite resources to build an integrated bauxite-aluminium industry to propel industrialisation. As a result, the government signed the Sinohydro Deal with the People's Republic of China, allowing them to build infrastructure in exchange for refined bauxite. Therefore, the bauxite mine in Atewa forest was part of this deal. Regarding the Sinohydro Deal, reports indicate that it bypassed Ghana's environmental laws (see Purwins, 2024; IUCN, 2023). This suggests that neither an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) nor a Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) was conducted to evaluate the potential environmental impact of the proposed bauxite mine in the Atewa Forest before the agreement was finalised. Purwins (2024) contends that political pressure may have influenced the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) to overlook these critical evaluations, allowing the deal to proceed without considering its environmental consequences. Conflicting interests on the part of the government emerge strongly here, highlighting the economic gains from continuing mining activities in the Atewa Forest clashing with the imperative of environmental sustainability. On the one hand, the government sees the development of the bauxite mine as a significant economic opportunity, promising increased revenue, job creation, and infrastructural improvements that could drive national growth. On the other hand, the environmental costs of such activities are substantial, posing a severe threat to the biodiversity and ecological balance of the Atewa Forest, which is a vital habitat for numerous species and a crucial water source for the country. A member of the Densu Basin Board adds this comment:

“I represent a government institution, and we do not agree with bauxite mining in the Atewa forest. However, as a public servant, I should not be seen as fighting the government too much, which is why those in the government sector have not been vocal about this. But if we allow the mining to go on, we have no business here anymore. The Densu Basin secretariat or board, because the river we are all trying to protect, would be destroyed” (Member, Densu Basin Board, December 2021).

7.2.10 Low political commitment

As has been observed by many stakeholders in the basin, the government lacks the political will to deal drastically with members of the government who are defying the laws and degrading water resources. The pollution of water resources is a menace that the country has been dealing with for decades. Recently, the situation has worsened because of illegal mining, also known as ‘galamsey’. The government declared a fight against illegal mining in 2017 to protect water resources, forests and agricultural land. Apart from illegal mining, some have

also raised concerns that small-scale mining contributes to the pollution of water resources. The fight against illegal mining has been difficult; the Densu River, among others, is still heavily polluted, and all stakeholders interviewed identified it as a significant environmental problem in the basin. The country's president admits the fight against illegal mining has been difficult. In explaining the difficulty, the President stated that in the last elections held in 2020, his declaration to stop illegal mining caused significant losses for his party and himself in terms of votes. Based on the President's statement and assessments by people in the basin, the government's will to protect and conserve our water resources is weak.

To address the challenges associated with water resource management in the Densu basin, it is paramount to promote innovation and collaboration among governments, NGOs, communities, and private sector players. In the subsequent discussion, I delve into the various opportunities available for implementing sustainable water management practices that can help to address the challenges faced in the Densu basin. The opportunities refer to 'economic, social, cultural, demographic, environmental, political, legal, governmental, technological, and competitive trends and events that could significantly benefit the basin secretariat in the future' (David & David, 2015, p. 44). These are largely beyond the control of the basin secretariat but can support water conservation, efficient use of water resources, and sustainable water management practices in the basin.

7.3 Opportunities for effective water resources management in the Densu basin

7.3.1 Holistic planning by the WRC

The WRC strategically plans and executes IWRM to harmonise the management of water, land, and interconnected resources across various sectors and geographical boundaries in the Densu basin. The primary goal is to optimise economic and social well-being while ensuring the long-term sustainability of critical ecosystems. The WRC has developed and is actively implementing an IWRM plan for the Densu Basin. This plan is not static; it is revised occasionally and updated to address new and emerging issues, ensuring that water resources management remains responsive to changing conditions and challenges. The dynamic nature of the IWRM plan allows the WRC to integrate new scientific data, technological advancements, and socio-economic changes into its management strategies. By doing so, the WRC ensures that the IWRM plan remains relevant and effective in the face of evolving environmental and societal conditions. A core principle of IWRM is managing water resources in a holistic and integrated manner, considering the needs of various sectors such as agriculture,

industry, and domestic use. This comprehensive approach helps balance these diverse demands, leading to more sustainable resource utilisation. In the Densu basin, agriculture requires water for irrigation, especially during dry seasons. Industries depend on a reliable water supply for their operations, while communities need clean water for drinking, sanitation, and daily activities. By coordinating these demands, the WRC ensures that no single sector disproportionately impacts the water resources, which is crucial for maintaining the basin's overall health and functionality.

7.3.2 Good collaboration and support from other Institutions/Agencies

Other institutions, especially government institutions and NGOs, have committed to supporting the basin office in delivering on their mandate. Aside from board meetings and ecological monitoring activities that these institutions collaborate on, they also help in other ways. Agencies such as the EPA, Forestry Commission, GWCL, Community Water and Sanitation Agency, Ghana Hydrological Authority, Minerals Commission, Fisheries Commission, Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority (LUSPA), Ghana Meteorological Agency (GMet), Ghana Irrigation Development Authority (GIDA), Volta River Authority (VRA), Ministry of Sanitation and Water Resources, Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation (MESTI), Ministry of Works and Housing, Ministry of Food and Agriculture (MOFA), Ministry of Health, Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection, National Commission on Culture, Regional Co-ordinating Councils, NGOs and all the Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies (MMDAs), collaborate with and support the WRC and basin offices in fulfilling their mandate. For example, the EPA assists the basin office with monitoring activities using vehicles. Though the protection and conservation of water resources lies with the WRC and basin offices, the GWCL and the CWSA, who are in charge of water supply, and the MMDAs seem more visible to citizens and, therefore, receive more reports on water pollution issues. In turn, the GWCL, CWSA, and MMDAs forward such reports to the basin offices for onward address. NGOs such as AROCHA Ghana also support the basin office by partnering with them to organise sensitisation and awareness programmes on water and mining. Sometimes, the basin office reaches out to AROCHA Ghana for information about activities in the communities along the basin. Similarly, AROCHA Ghana consults the basin office in case of any illegal activities in these areas. In an interview, a senior official from AROCHA Ghana discussed this collaborative effort.

“There was a situation in a community where someone was raising pigs at the upper stream of the Densu River. The CREMA committee raised

a complaint, and we visited the site to assess the situation. We recommended that the committee take full responsibility for addressing the issue, so we invited the basin office, the District Assembly, and NADMO to help resolve the matter” (Senior official, AROCHA Ghana, December 2021).

7.3.3 Availability of Corporate Bodies

Industries and corporate entities offer a promising prospect for efficient water resources management in the Densu basin. With a heavy reliance on water for their operations, many businesses in the basin are committed to safeguarding this valuable resource to maintain continued access. For example, Guinness Ghana has taken proactive steps towards water conservation and management as a part of its Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) endeavours. An interview with A ROCHA Ghana revealed that Guinness Ghana has been supporting them for the past years in planting trees along the Densu River, the upper stream of the Densu basin. According to stakeholders in the basin, and corroborated by documentary evidence, other companies operating in the Densu basin have also undertaken environmentally sustainable activities such as minimising their water consumption and reducing waste generation. These companies include Nestle Ghana Limited and Accra Brewery Limited. To achieve their sustainability goals, these companies have implemented water-efficient technologies and practices such as recycling and reuse systems. Blue Skies, Voltic Ghana and Cocoa Processing Company are among the companies in the basin whose CSR projects have involved providing potable water or planting trees to protect water bodies. Corporate organisations can contribute to effective water resources management in the basin by integrating water management into their operations and providing funds to support water protection and conservation.

7.3.4 Increasing awareness of climate change and pollution among the public

Interviews with the WRC, GWCL, and CWSA and corroborated by NGOs in the Densu basin indicate that due to the extensive media coverage in recent times, communities have become increasingly aware of the environmental challenges facing river basins, including climate change impacts and pollution. This offers an opportunity for effective water resources management because the WRC and basin offices can leverage this increased awareness to develop more educational programmes focused on water conservation and the impacts of climate change. Heightened awareness can spur community-led initiatives and grassroots movements focused on protecting and managing local water resources. The increased awareness can lead to behavioural change in citizens and companies. With a better

understanding of the impact of pollution, individuals and communities may engage in practices that reduce water pollution, such as proper waste disposal and minimising the use of harmful chemicals. Also, companies, aware of the public's concern for pollution, may adopt more sustainable practices to align with consumer expectations. This includes minimising pollution, reducing water waste, and investing in sustainable solutions. Increased awareness can also lead to greater international cooperation on water resource management, as countries and bilateral and international organisations recognise the global nature of water issues exacerbated by climate change.

7.3.5 Support from Donor Agencies

Another opportunity is that some donor agencies are willing to provide financial support for addressing urgent environmental challenges, including support in the water and sanitation sector. The WRC has received many external funds from donor agencies such as DANIDA, the World Bank and the Royal Netherlands Embassy. These agencies are still willing to offer financial help for sustainable sanitation and water management. Moreover, other donor agencies may be more inclined to allocate resources to support efforts at combating water resources degradation highlighted in the media due to increased visibility and public pressure. Media coverage brings attention to the severity and urgency of water-related issues, making them more prominent in the public eye and on the global agenda. As a result, donor agencies, motivated by both public concern and the need to address critical environmental challenges, may prioritise funding for projects aimed at mitigating water pollution, improving water conservation, and enhancing sustainable water management practices. This heightened media focus can lead to more significant financial commitments and support from international donors, non-governmental organisations, and philanthropic foundations dedicated to addressing the environmental and socio-economic impacts of water resource degradation. The WRC and basin offices can, therefore, take advantage of this.

7.3.6 Availability of Research Institutions

The existence of the CSIR-Water Research Institute(WRI) and other institutions of higher learning, such as the Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST), is an excellent opportunity for effective water resources management in the Densu basin. The Water Research Institute and other research institutions house scientists, engineers, and experts with specialised knowledge in water resources management, including hydrology, water quality, ecology, climate science and governance. The basin office can tap into this expertise to inform

evidence-based decision-making and help develop innovative solutions to water-related challenges.

Research institutions often conduct field studies, monitor water resources, and collect data on hydrological processes, water quality parameters, and environmental indicators. They also play a vital role in driving technological innovation and developing advanced tools, models, and techniques for water resources assessment, monitoring, and management. As the interviews with the WRC and basin offices revealed, the WRC liaises with the CSIR-Water Research Institute to obtain valuable data for assessing the status of water resources, identifying trends and patterns, and evaluating the effectiveness of management strategies. The WRI is advanced in remote sensing technologies, computer simulations, data analytics, and decision support systems that enhance the efficiency and accuracy of water management practices; therefore they can help build the capacity of staff of the basin offices through training programmes, workshops, and educational initiatives with these skills to better understand and address water challenges in their respective contexts.

7.3.7 Availability of regulations and government policies

There are currently the Ghana water policy, riparian buffer zone policy and regulations on water use, dam safety and drilling license and groundwater development. These are policies and legislative instruments that can be taken advantage of to improve water resources management. The water policy is a crucial element that is pivotal in enabling effective water resources management. It provides a comprehensive and coherent framework encompassing guiding principles and actionable strategies to address various water challenges and promote sustainable development. With the help of a well-crafted water policy, the WRC and basin secretariat can make informed and evidence-based decisions to ensure the optimal use of this scarce resource while balancing various competing demands. The availability of the buffer zone policy proves to be a crucial step towards efficient water resources management. The buffer zone policy addresses many factors such as water quality, erosion control, flood mitigation, habitat conservation, and climate change adaptation. By implementing and enforcing the buffer zone policy, various stakeholders, including government agencies and landowners, can safeguard and enhance the ecological, economic, and social value of rivers and wetlands. This, in turn, ensures the sustainable use and conservation of water resources for generations to come.

The water use regulations, Legislative Instrument (L.I.) 1692 (2001), include measures to promote sustainable water use and conservation and govern the allocation and use of water resources among different users and sectors, including agriculture, industry, and municipalities. Enforcing these regulations by establishing water rights systems, water pricing mechanisms, and allocation frameworks can ensure equitable access to water resources, resolve conflicts over water allocation, and promote efficient water use. The regulations also help optimise water resource utilisation, reduce wastage, and mitigate water scarcity risks.

The Drilling Licence and Groundwater Development Regulations Legislative Instrument (L.I.) 1827 (2006) address groundwater management issues, including groundwater extraction, recharge, and contamination. By establishing groundwater withdrawal permits, monitoring requirements, and pollution control measures, these regulations will help prevent overexploitation, maintain aquifer sustainability, and protect groundwater quality for drinking, irrigation, and industrial purposes.

7.4 Barriers to effective water resources management in the Pra Basin

Several obstacles hinder effective water resources management in the Pra basin. Interestingly, these barriers resemble those encountered in the Densu basin. In the following section, we will delve into the specific characteristics of these issues as they pertain to the Pra basin.

7.4.1 Inadequate funds to sustain awareness creation

Interviews with the Pra Basin secretariat revealed that despite efforts to raise awareness of the importance of water conservation and management, it has been challenging to maintain a consistent and impactful campaign due to financial limitations. This has resulted in a limited reach and impact of their campaigns, which has affected the effectiveness of the basin's water management efforts.

The Pra Basin Secretariat and the Water Resources Commission are responsible for managing and regulating the use of water resources in the Pra Basin. To fund its operations, the Commission relies on four primary internal revenue sources: administration fees, application fees, raw water abstraction fees, and drillers' licensing fees. These fees are collected from individuals and private businesses that use and extract water from the basin's water sources.

However, the current revenue generated from these sources must be improved to meet the Commission's financial needs. This is because the basin office can only identify large private businesses required to pay the necessary fees. Many individuals and small private companies

that extract water and treat it for sale as drinking water to the public must also pay for the water, they extract per the water use regulations. Unfortunately, only a few companies comply with paying the water abstraction fees, leading to a significant shortfall in revenue.

7.4.2 Personnel deficit

The Pra Basin secretariat currently operates with a staff strength below 50 percent of what they require, a critical understaffing situation. The current staff strength is inadequate to efficiently cover the part of the Pra basin being managed by the secretariat, which is more than One-third of the entire Pra basin, covering 23,200 km². From 2011 to 2016, only two officers worked at the secretariat, making it extremely difficult to manage the area. Even with the increase in staffing capacity in 2017 to five employees, which includes three technical staff, a cleaner, and a driver, the workforce is still insufficient to manage the entire area effectively.

Considering the size of the basin, the current staff strength is inadequate for the workload that the secretariat is supposed to handle. Due to the deficient staff strength, the secretariat faces difficulties monitoring the activities of private enterprises that are supposed to pay water charges, making it challenging to identify defaulters. This goes the long run and affects internally generated funds (IGFs). The Basin officer said:

“The Pra Basin secretariat requires a significant increase in personnel strength to manage the basin effectively. Without adequate staffing, it will be difficult to monitor and manage the entire area efficiently” (Pra Basin Officer, November 2022).

7.4.3 Logistical constraints

Logistical constraints have also hampered water resource management in the Pra basin. The basin secretariat and other state agencies have identified inadequate logistics as a significant obstacle to effectively managing the basin's water resources. For example, one of the critical issues the Ghana Water Company Limited faces is the shortage of dredgers. This has made it difficult for the company to carry out dredging activities to maintain and improve the dams in the basin.

In addition to the dredging challenge, logistical difficulties have hindered monitoring activities. The lack of official means of transportation coupled with the rugged terrain and poor road networks in the basin make it difficult to move around and access various locations. This has made it challenging for the basin secretariat to carry out their monitoring duties effectively. Without access to official vehicles, the secretariat has had to rely on public transportation or

personal vehicles for official duties. This caused delays and made it difficult for the secretariat to carry out their duties efficiently. The basin officer stated:

“For about ten years, basin officers used to take public transport or drive their cars around the basin for monitoring. Now, we have a vehicle for the secretariat” (Pra Basin Officer, December 2022).

7.4.4 Low level of awareness of the WRC and water policy instruments

Based on the interviews, it was found that most citizens were either unaware of or did not understand the various rules and regulations in place for protecting the environment. One particular area of concern was the lack of knowledge about the Water Resources Commission (WRC) and the laws and regulations related to water management. This lack of understanding has led to non-compliance with these regulations. Additionally, many individuals are unaware of the consequences of their actions when they fail to follow these laws. This was particularly evident among private enterprises that do not pay for the water they use for their activities because they are not aware of the water use regulations. The basin officer confirmed this information.

“The importance of the work done by the WRC is not widely understood, resulting in a generally low level of awareness about the Commission’s importance. Additionally, many people are unfamiliar with the laws and regulations established by the commission and, as a result, fail to comply with them” (Pra Basin Officer, November 2022).

7.4.5 Weak law enforcement and compliance

The interviews revealed that many participants, especially those from government institutions, believed that the country already possesses all the necessary policy instruments to improve water quality and prevent water scarcity. These instruments include a range of regulations and economic and financial tools. However, it also came to light that enforcing environmental laws is a significant challenge in the country, primarily due to the prevalence of bribery and interference by influential people, especially politicians. Bribery is a major obstacle to the enforcement of water regulations. Bribery enables individuals and companies to evade water regulations, leading to pollution, over-extraction, and misuse of water resources. The stakeholders noted that these bribery and interferences often prevent the perpetrators from being held accountable. When officials accept bribes, they are less likely to hold violators accountable. This creates an environment where illegal activities go unchecked, further degrading water resources and this is partly responsible for the widespread of illegal mining activities in the basin. A participant commented on this issue.

“It appears that the only motivation for anyone to do anything in this country is money. A lot of us worship money. Once you are tempted with some money, it is difficult to refuse, so many of those who are to enforce the laws are bribed to keep quiet and overlook the wrongdoing” (Participant Focus Group Discussion, Amakye-Bare- Atwima Nwabiagya North, December 2022).

One of the study participants also raised concerns about the lack of strict enforcement and suggested a way forward.

“You see, the laws and other instruments are all available; enforcement and compliance is the challenge. We need more public education and sensitisation to get people to know the laws, rules, regulations and penalties and their duty as citizens to obey them. Concerning enforcement, if we can have some examples of punishment, people would advise themselves” (High-ranking official, Shama District Assembly, December 2022).

Enforcement faces a significant issue in Ghana due to the interference of influential individuals in society. It is a common practice for offenders to seek help from influential people to avoid punishment for their actions. A recent conversation with an official from one of the Municipal Assemblies confirmed this practice is widespread. Offenders who have connections with influential individuals in society often rely on these relationships to help them evade punishment. The officer added this comment:

“In Ghana, our development has become focused on individual interests, promoting nepotism. Anytime someone is on the wrong side of the law, we want to find ways and means and usually rely on the influence of people in authority to free the person. The security forces can do their job to arrest offenders, but most of the time, strings are pulled, and when that happens, they are helpless” (High Profile Officer, Obuasi Municipal Assembly, December 2022).

In discussions with citizens in the Pra basin, concerns were raised about the challenges citizens face in complying with laws to protect water resources in the area. One of the critical issues mentioned was the high level of poverty and unemployment, which has led to a proliferation of illegal mining activities that are known to pollute water bodies. According to the citizens, many young people who engage in illegal mining are forced to do so due to a lack of alternative sources of employment. They argued that if there were more job opportunities that did not involve getting dirty all the time, like in illegal mining, illegal mining would not be as attractive to the youth, and illegal mining activities would significantly reduce. The citizens, therefore,

appealed to the government and other stakeholders to prioritise creating more job opportunities in the Pra basin and other areas affected by illegal mining. One of the participants made a comment stating that:

“Compliance with the rules and regulations is difficult because of poverty and unemployment. There are no jobs in the rural areas for the youth except farming, so many are pushed into illegal mining, which pollutes our water bodies” (Participant, Focus Group Discussion, Amakye-Bare- Atwima Nwabiagya North, December 2022).

7.4.6 The behaviour of people and companies in the area

The study discovered a widely held belief that our water resources are a public and free resource. Also, water is a natural cleanser that carries all our dirt or waste away. Since water resources are public property owned by no individual, this belief has created an environment where some individuals exploit water resources for their gain. Unfortunately, many citizens and businesses prioritise their interests in making money over the degradation of the environment and even over their health. Even though illegal mining has been identified to lead to health complications in the long term, people, especially the youth, are so caught up in the pursuit of money that they pay little attention to the environment around them. Some participants shared their opinions:

“Over the years, we have had free access to all of our water resources, including the sea, so anyone who has money to construct a canoe can go there and start fishing, and with time, we are experiencing overfishing. I think it applies to all of our water bodies. People go there and do things with impunity, such as washing cars by the water body. People believe that once it is a water body, water is a natural cleanser, and we start pushing all our waste into it” (High profile officer, Fisheries Commission, August 2021).

“People must come to accept that we cannot just abuse the environment in our bid to make enough money for our families. We, as Ghanaians, need to change our mindset and be responsible towards the environment” (Participant, FGD at Kumunumu- Shama, December 2022).

“About target group behaviour, all that the citizens, especially the youth, think about is our pockets, getting rich quickly, so we mine destroying our land and water, but I believe if we only think about our pockets, our children will suffer in future” (Participant, FGD, Presentase, December 2022).

The behaviour of people towards water resources is also heavily influenced by their readiness to report any misdeeds and allow the culprits to face the consequences of their actions. The

available data suggests that some rural communities are more prone to shielding those who cause harm to water bodies. In contrast, others are more proactive in safeguarding water resources and acting against wrongdoers. This highlights the importance of creating awareness and promoting a culture of accountability and responsibility towards water resources. An officer of the Obuasi municipality explained:

“Sometimes, the community itself is the problem. The communities shield the illegal miners. The security forces can go to a community to make arrests, but the community will not give the people up” (High Profile Officer, Obuasi Municipal Assembly, December 2022).

During the community focus group discussions, one of the participants highlighted that community members are hesitant to report incidents of water pollution due to concerns about their reputation being tarnished. The participant explained that in rural communities, there is the fear of being ostracised by other community members, which prevents many individuals from reporting water pollution incidents. The participant recounted an incident:

“A task force was formed in this community some time back to ensure the buffer zone was respected. Also, farmers do not dump their empty agrochemical bottles in the river. Still, when the task force identifies any wrongdoing, they cannot report it to the authorities because we feel we are a family in the community. If you report your family member of misconduct, you might get a bad name in the community. People will shun your company” (Participant, Focus Group Discussion at Amakye-Bare, Atwima Nwabiagya North District, December 2022).

The study discovered that the behaviour and attitudes of many local chiefs are hindering the effective management of water resources in the area. These chiefs allow illegal mining activities to take place on their land without any consideration for the environment and river bodies. The participants of the study explained that the leaders themselves own the land where these illegal mining activities are carried out, and their interests often come in the way of adequate water resources management.

7.4.7 Political challenges

During the interviews, participants shared their opinions on the government's commitment to combatting illegal mining which has severely polluted the Pra River and its tributaries. The consensus among participants was that the government's efforts had not been enough to address the issue. They pointed out that government officials tend to make promises and speeches but often fail to deliver actual results. This is how one of the participants explained it:

“Some time ago, river guards were inaugurated to go for patrols on the Pra River with speed boats. I believe this inauguration was done for applause, for people to see that the government is doing something. But the speed boats were only available during the inauguration of the river guards. After that, they all disappeared from the river” (Participant of Focus Group Discussion at Kumunumu- Shama, December 2022).

Participants observed that in recent times, there have been concerns about the government's commitment to ending illegal mining activities in the country, popularly known as 'galamsey'. Many have accused the government of failing to prosecute the big men behind these activities despite evidence of their involvement. There is a growing suspicion that these individuals have connections in high places, and as a result, they are shielded from facing the full force of the law. This has led to a widespread perception that the government is not doing enough to tackle the issue of illegal mining and that the fight against galamsey is being compromised by corruption.

7.4.8 Institutional challenges

Small-scale mining contributes immensely to the degradation of water resources in the Pra basin. Meanwhile, government officials have granted small-scale mining leases without ensuring the companies have the requisite capacity and are mining sustainably. Interview participants expressed disappointment at the government institutions' lack of action to combat this issue and called for more decisive action. One of the participants highlighted this issue. He said:

“You only find people come with some papers to say that Accra has given them the permit to mine or do sand winning. We cannot question them when they come like that since the chiefs support them. They mine, cause pollution and promise to reclaim the mined land, but they never do it, and nothing happens to them” (Participant, Asante Akyem Central Municipal Assembly, August 2022).

The study highlighted a significant institutional challenge in the form of weak collaboration between major stakeholders. During the discussions, the participants emphasised that the current level of cooperation among the major stakeholders involved in the mining sector, including the Minerals Commission, District Assemblies, traditional authorities, Water Resources Commission, and Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), is inadequate, with some conflicting interests. This has led to mining being one of the chief contributors to water resources degradation. The traditional leaders were particularly criticised for their lack of

cooperation in preserving water resources in the basin. Participants described traditional leaders as more interested in making money from selling lands to illegal miners than in safeguarding water resources. The lack of cooperation from traditional leaders is a significant concern, as they play a vital role in enforcing laws and regulations related to water resources. A participant summed up what many referred to as the weak collaboration between stakeholders. He noted:

“The Minerals Commission issues mining permits in Accra, which the Municipal Assembly supports. When the miners arrive, they seek the approval of local Chiefs who support the mining activities. However, none of these actors conduct background checks with the Minerals Commission to authenticate the permit. Consequently, their actions undermine efforts to address the problems associated with mining” (Participant, Focus Group Discussion, Okyinso, August 2022).

The process of obtaining permits for operating within the legal framework is often hindered by excessive bureaucracy, which has been identified as a significant obstacle to effective water resources management. Many interview participants have pointed out that reducing bureaucracy can encourage private enterprises to follow the proper process instead of resorting to illegal operations. The public sector, including institutions that oversee the environment, is rife with bureaucracy, which makes the permitting system take a longer time to complete. For instance, the Fisheries Commission grants aquaculture permits, but these permits depend on getting an environmental permit from the EPA and a water use permit from the WRC. An official from the Fisheries Commission spoke about this issue:

“It would be best to have a water permit to use water, but the process and the time spent acquiring the permit itself become a disincentive. While it is good to regulate water use to avoid conflict among water users, obtaining those permits becomes inimical, leading people to flout the laws and do anything they want” (Officer of the Fisheries Commission, August 2021).

The Pra Basin secretariat also faces the challenge of organising board meetings that all board members can attend. As the meetings are held outside the office, additional expenses are incurred in terms of transportation, accommodation, and refreshments, among others. Therefore, the secretariat always strives to select a convenient meeting date for almost all board members. However, this is not always an easy task as most board members are usually occupied with other equally important assignments in their respective institutions. Consequently,

scheduling board meetings that align with the availability of all board members can be quite challenging for the secretariat.

7.4.9 Policy implementation gap

Stakeholders in the Pra basin expressed concerns about the current buffer zone policy, stating the policy's lack of more specific distances that should be kept as a buffer to protect water bodies. Stakeholders stressed the need for a revision of the policy and for the policy to be transformed into a legislative instrument. They believe this will help improve compliance and accountability for those who violate the policy. By doing so, they hope to ensure that the buffer zone policy is adhered to and that the Pra basin's ecosystem is safeguarded from further degradation. An Official from the EPA noted:

“As the Environmental Protection Agency, we rely on the WRC buffer zone policy as a guide when we encounter construction activities on waterways. However, this policy is not a law. The buffer zone policy also gives officers discretion to set the buffer at different distances, which can be problematic and create confusion. Due to the buffer zone policy's lack of legal standing, it creates uncertainty in legal proceedings” (High Profile Officer of the Environmental Protection Agency, December 2022).

“Under the rule of law, when something is not explicitly written or established as law, it can become difficult to enforce. In such cases, a judge may decide to release an offender, especially if the offense is not clearly defined by law” (High Profile Officer of the Environmental Protection Agency, December 2022).

7.5 Opportunities for effective water resources management in the Pra basin

7.5.1 Availability of the media including social media to support water resources management

According to stakeholders in the Pra basin, over the past few years, public awareness of the negative impact of mining activities on water bodies has significantly increased over the past few years. Stakeholders across various sectors, including environmental groups, government agencies, and local communities, have observed a heightened concern about the degradation of rivers due to mining. Media reports and direct observations of the adverse effects of mining, such as water pollution and the depletion of local water resources, have fuelled this awareness. The current momentum presents a valuable opportunity for the Water Resources Commission (WRC) to interact more proactively with the public. By capitalising on this heightened awareness and support, the basin secretariat and the WRC can enhance their efforts in water

resource management. To take advantage of this opportunity, the WRC can ensure that public education campaigns in the basin are comprehensive to inform citizens about water resource management, the impacts of mining on water bodies, and the importance of sustainable practices. These campaigns can utilise various media, including television, radio, and social media platforms. Social media can be used to host and promote educational campaigns on topics such as water conservation, pollution prevention, and sustainable water practices. These campaigns can reach a broad and diverse audience quickly and efficiently, enhancing public knowledge and awareness. Again, in addition to annual reports, the WRC can provide newsletters on the state of water resources, the impacts of mining, and the outcomes of regulatory actions in the basin to help build trust and keep the public informed about ongoing efforts to protect water bodies. The Water Resources Commission (WRC) can also leverage the current wave of public support to lobby for increased resources and funding. This public backing can be channelled to influence policymakers, and private sector stakeholders by highlighting the widespread concern and collective will to address water management issues. Engaging the media to amplify these messages and mobilising public campaigns can create further pressure on decision-makers to allocate more funds for crucial water management projects. In essence, the WRC can turn public support into a powerful advocacy tool, ensuring that water resource management remains a priority on the national agenda and receives the financial backing necessary for long-term success.

7.5.2 The introduction of anti-galamsey taskforces for water resources management

In response to the rampant destruction of water sources caused by illegal mining activities in Ghana, many municipalities with high illegal mining occurrences have taken proactive measures. These local authorities have formed anti-galamsey task forces to bolster the central government's efforts in combating illegal mining. This collaborative approach presents a significant opportunity for the WRC and basin secretariats to work in tandem with these task forces to help address the pollution of water sources in the basins. Anti-galamsey task forces provide additional resources for the WRC and basin secretariats regarding monitoring and enforcement. These task forces can offer on-the-ground surveillance and rapid response capabilities to address illegal mining activities as they occur. This enhanced capacity allows for more effective enforcement of environmental regulations and quicker mitigation of any environmental damage caused by illicit mining. Anti-galamsey task forces can aid in collecting valuable data regarding the state of water resources and the extent and impact of illegal mining activities. This information is crucial for the WRC and basin secretariats to develop informed

and effective management strategies and to regularly report to the public through newsletters. The basin office can also rely on detailed reports from task forces to highlight illegal activity hotspots and track progress over time, guiding future interventions and resource allocation.

Plate 12: Anti-galamsey taskforce operations

Plate 13: Anti-galamsey taskforce

7.5.3 Availability of assessments as a means of motivation

During interviews conducted in the Pra basin, it was found that the performance assessments of local government authorities serve as a strong motivator for improved performance. District assemblies demonstrating good governance are rewarded with additional funds to support development projects. An opportunity lies in including sustainability as a key criterion for evaluating district assemblies. This could encompass initiatives for conservation and community engagement. Establishing a regular system to assess the performance of district assemblies in conserving and safeguarding water resources annually or biennially could significantly aid in garnering support for effective water management in the Pra basin. Results from the assessment can be published similarly to other assessments, with incentives for high-performing district assemblies, such as financial rewards, public recognition, or additional support for water management projects. Implementing these incentives can serve as a catalyst for local assemblies to prioritise water resource management within their respective areas. This methodical approach can promote accountability, stimulate healthy competition, promote best practices, and ensure the sustainable management of water resources throughout the basin. Furthermore, these assessments will yield crucial data on the condition of water resources and management techniques within the Pra basin. The Water WRC and basin secretariats can utilise

this information to spot trends and devise strategies to tackle specific challenges highlighted during the assessments.

7.5.4 Availability of basin IWRM plan and the concept of Local Water Committee (LWC)

The Pra River basin secretariat is currently dedicated to the sustainable management of the upper part of the Pra basin. To strengthen their efforts, there is a proposal to set up two new sub-basin offices that would function as committees under the WRC. This idea was put forward due to the size of the Pra basin, which requires more localised management. Although establishing sub-basin offices has been included in the IWRM plan, it has not been fully implemented. If implemented, it would ensure that every part of the basin is covered and managed effectively. The WRC should, therefore, guarantee the establishment of the Birim and Lower Pra sub-basin secretariats so that the management of the Pra basin would be more decentralised and the resources in the basin would be utilised more efficiently. Also, the WRC introduced the Local Water Committee (LWC) concept, which is currently being piloted in the Lower Volta Basin. This concept aligns with the decentralisation of water resource management at the local level. Once the pilot is successful and funding is secured, there is potential for the LWC to be expanded to other basins, such as the Pra Basin, bringing water resource management closer to local communities.

7.5.5 Proliferation of drinking water-producing enterprises

One of the most effective methods for the WRC to increase its revenue is by collecting licensing, permit and water abstraction fees from water-producing businesses. During interviews with stakeholders in the basin, it came to light that there are many water-producing enterprises in the basin that are supposed to pay fees to the WRC. Some interviewees believe that the WRC primarily target large companies for fees, overlooking the numerous small and medium-scale operations. Expanding its Internally Generated Funds (IGF) is seen as a key opportunity for the Water Resources Commission (WRC) to improve its financial position. By increasing its IGF, the WRC can ensure a more stable and self-sufficient financial base, reducing reliance on external funding and enabling more consistent and sustainable management of water resources. To achieve this, there is a need for enhanced monitoring efforts. Currently, there may be numerous private enterprises that are legally obligated to pay fees to the WRC but remain unregistered or underreported. The WRC needs to maintain an up-to-date database of all private enterprises operating within the basin that are required to pay

fees. This can be achieved through collaboration with the Registrar General's department, District Assemblies, and other relevant agencies.

7.5.6 Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Contributions

Water and beverage-producing enterprises often engage in corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives to demonstrate their commitment to sustainable practices and community welfare. The WRC can encourage these enterprises to contribute a portion of their profits to water resources management projects. These contributions can fund conservation programmes, community education initiatives and infrastructure improvements.

7.6 Conclusion

Based on the findings of several interviews, focus group discussions and documentary evidence, this chapter has highlighted the challenges that seriously affect the efficient management of water resources in the Densu and Pra basins. The first challenge is the gap in implementing policies to manage water resources in the two basins. This gap reflects the insufficiency of the buffer zone policy and, to some extent, the ineffectiveness of the minerals and mining policy in achieving its intended goals. These policies will need to be reviewed. The buffer zone policy also needs to be transformed into a legislative instrument. The second challenge is the limited financial, logistics and personnel available to carry out necessary tasks. This has resulted in the inadequate monitoring and enforcement of water resource regulations and insufficient investment in developing infrastructure and technology to produce reliable, accurate, continuous, and systematic data on the quality and quantity of surface and groundwater resources. The third challenge is the weak law enforcement mechanisms that lead to non-compliance with regulations. This is mainly due to a need for more capacity and political will to enforce existing regulations and hold those violating them accountable. The fourth challenge is the low levels of awareness about the importance of water resource management. This results from inadequate education and outreach programmes that can effectively communicate the importance of the WRC, water conservation and sustainable water management practices to the public. The fifth challenge is the negative attitudes of citizens towards water conservation efforts. This is mainly due to a need for more trust in the government and an understanding of the importance of water conservation efforts in ensuring the sustainability of the basins' water resources. Finally, political and institutional factors also hamper progress in managing water resources in the Densu and Pra basins. These factors

include conflicting interests among different stakeholders and the influence of powerful actors who may not prioritise sustainable water resource management.

Conditions in the Densu and Pra basins also present some opportunities for enhancing water resources management in the two basins as discussed in this chapter. One of the opportunities identified is the collaborative efforts of various institutions and agencies. Government bodies, NGOs, and corporate entities are pivotal in supporting the WRC and basin offices, contributing resources, expertise, and funding. This collaboration extends to ecological monitoring, awareness programmes, and implementing sustainable practices. The increasing public awareness of environmental issues, driven by extensive media coverage also provides a valuable opportunity for enhancing community engagement in water conservation efforts. Moreover, support from donor agencies, including DANIDA and the World Bank, offers financial backing that is essential for addressing pressing environmental challenges. Research institutions like the CSIR-Water Research Institute and KNUST also exist to provide the scientific expertise necessary for informed decision-making and innovative solutions in water management.

The introduction of anti-galamsey task forces represents a vital step forward in addressing the rampant destruction of water sources caused by illegal mining activities, particularly in regions heavily affected by "galamsey." These task forces can work with the WRC to monitor and prevent illegal mining activities that harm the water sources. The structured approach to assessing the performance of district assemblies in the Pra basin holds immense potential to motivate local government authorities through well-designed incentives. The dissemination of assessment results and providing financial rewards, public recognition, and additional project support can further incentivise these efforts, ensuring sustainable water resource management across the basin. The data obtained from these evaluations will be instrumental in identifying trends and developing targeted strategies to address specific challenges for the Water Resources Commission (WRC) and basin secretariats.

Furthermore, implementing sub-basin offices under the WRC, as the IWRM plan outlines, can enhance localised management within the basins. Establishing the Birim and Lower Pra sub-basin secretariats would decentralise water management, ensuring more efficient utilisation of resources. The concept of Local Water Committees (LWCs), currently piloted in the Lower Volta Basin, also shows promise for decentralising water management and bringing it closer to local communities in other basins, such as the Pra. Additionally, the proliferation of drinking

water-producing enterprises presents an opportunity for the WRC to increase its internally generated funds through licensing and permit fees. Expanding the monitoring scope to include more private enterprises will enable better revenue collection and support sustainable water resource management. The corporate social responsibility (CSR) contributions from water and beverage-producing enterprises can also be a good opportunity for the basin secretariat and the WRC to fund conservation programs, community education initiatives, and infrastructure improvements, reinforcing the commitment to sustainable practices and community welfare.

CHAPTER EIGHT

DISCUSSION

8.1 Introduction

This chapter analyses the research findings, contextualising them within the existing literature to offer a comprehensive understanding of the complexities in water governance within Ghana's Densu and Pra River Basins. Comparing the study's results with established research sheds light on the multifaceted dynamics at play, enhancing our understanding of the governance issues and proposing insights for more effective management strategies. The chapter explores the country's journey in adopting IWRM principles, highlighting progress and persistent challenges. Since Ghana's water governance framework does not exist in a vacuum, there is a discussion on how political and social dynamics shape the country's water governance framework. Based on the analysis of the composition and functioning of river basin boards, the chapter highlights the significant potential for regulatory capture in basin water management. It also examines navigating overlapping and conflicting roles in water governance, stakeholder inclusion and adaptability in basin water management; the hierarchical nature of governance and the centralised regulatory framework that limits local autonomy. Furthermore, this chapter addresses the prevalent issue of tokenism, the paradox of decentralised management with centralised financial control and governance challenges and the water pollution crisis. The study also highlights the weak enforcement of regulations on water management and the overreliance on foreign donors and its implications for the sustainability of water management institutions, aligning with existing literature on the vulnerabilities created by such dependencies.

8.2 Ghana's Journey with Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM)

Ghana's water governance and decision-making processes are rooted in the principles of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM), which was first introduced during the 1992 Rio UN Conference on Environment and Development. IWRM promotes a holistic approach to managing water resources, focusing on sustainable usage, equitable access, and cross-sectoral collaboration. In Ghana, the adoption of IWRM has been gradual, evolving through a series of institutional reforms aimed at improving the management of the country's water resources.

The pivotal moment in Ghana's journey toward IWRM occurred in 1996 when the government made the strategic decision to separate water resources management from water supply

functions. This decision led to the creation of the Water Resources Commission (WRC), a regulatory body responsible for overseeing the country's water resources. Another milestone was the Water Resources Management Study (WARM), a critical study that laid the foundation for the implementation of IWRM in Ghana. With the WRC in place, Ghana began the process of embedding IWRM principles into its water management framework, fully committing to IWRM by 2007.

A key element of IWRM in Ghana is the management of water resources at the basin level. This approach decentralises water management, empowering basin boards to make decisions tailored to their local environments' specific needs and challenges. Basin-level management encourages stakeholder participation, integrates different sectors, and fosters a more collaborative approach to addressing water-related issues such as pollution. The basin management system is a practical application of the IWRM principle of managing water resources within natural hydrological boundaries, rather than administrative or political ones.

Despite these significant strides, some scholars have pointed to certain challenges in the implementation of IWRM in developing countries, including Ghana. One of the most commonly cited challenges is the lack of institutional capital. Scholars such as Mizutani (2011) and Saravanan et al. (2009) argue that many developing countries lack the institutional capacity required to implement IWRM effectively, particularly in managing water resources based on a River Basin Unit. Institutional capital encompasses a range of factors, including governance frameworks, organisational capacity, and the ability to enforce regulations. A lack of these elements can severely hinder the successful adoption of IWRM. However, Ghana presents a somewhat different case. Contrary to the notion that developing countries inherently lack institutional capital, Ghana has made notable progress in building the necessary institutional framework to support IWRM. The country has developed a strong set of policies and regulations that guide water management and decision-making. Additionally, Ghana's institutions have demonstrated significant organisational capacity, with the ability to implement and enforce water management policies.

Moreover, collaborative networks between various institutions and stakeholders are a key component of Ghana's institutional capital. The WRC, for example, works closely with other central government agencies, local governments, non-governmental organisations, private sector actors, and local communities to coordinate water management efforts. Nevertheless, despite Ghana's relative strength in institutional capital, financial constraints and a lack of

political will remain significant barriers to the effective implementation of IWRM. The availability of funds is crucial for the functioning of basin boards and for the broader decision-making processes involved in water governance. Many basin boards in Ghana face challenges in making informed decisions due to limited financial resources. This financial shortfall also impacts the ability to conduct stakeholder consultations, which are a key component of IWRM. Engaging all relevant stakeholders—such as local communities, farmers, businesses, and environmental groups—is essential for ensuring that water management decisions are equitable and sustainable. However, these consultations require funding for logistics, facilitation, and follow-up actions.

The lack of financial resources also hinders the coordination of efforts among stakeholders. For instance, when the WRC seeks to enforce water regulations, such as in cases of illegal water use or pollution, it often needs to collaborate with security services, including the military. However, the WRC is required to cover the costs of transporting and feeding these personnel during enforcement activities. Without sufficient funding, enforcement actions are delayed or scaled back, undermining the effectiveness of water management policies. The absence of strong political backing also leads to weak enforcement of water regulations and environmental laws to protect and conserve water resources.

The basin secretariats have highlighted that even when enforcement mechanisms are in place, the lack of financial and political support creates gaps in implementation. Without adequate funding and political support, these institutions struggle to carry out their mandates, which include monitoring water quality, regulating water usage, and protecting water resources.

8.3 The context of political, socio-cultural dynamics in modern water governance framework

The study's conceptual framework highlights the intricate relationship between Ghana's political and socio-cultural context and its water governance structures. Traditional leaders, recognised as custodians of land, including the water bodies situated within their territories, play a crucial role in these governance frameworks, as evidenced by their representation on basin boards and the board for the WRC. Scholars like Adjakloe (2021) argue that traditional leaders in Ghana historically governed customary water management systems, actively protecting and conserving water resources within their jurisdictions.

With the advent of statutory laws, the responsibility for water governance has increasingly shifted to formal institutions. Despite this transition, traditional leaders continue to hold significant influence in Ghana's water management landscape. Their involvement is not merely ceremonial; it reflects the enduring power dynamics and cultural importance of traditional authority in decision-making processes related to water resources.

This dual system of governance, where statutory frameworks coexist alongside traditional practices, highlights the complexity of water management in Ghana. While formal institutions may provide the regulatory framework for water governance, recognising traditional leaders highlights the necessity for inclusive approaches integrating local knowledge and customs. Engaging traditional leaders in decision-making ensures that water governance not only complies with legal frameworks but also respects the cultural and historical contexts that influence community relationships with water resources.

Traditional leaders' involvement in water governance is essential for gaining community support and advancing sustainable practices. Their historical role as protectors of water resources equips them with unique insights and a deep understanding of local ecosystems. Therefore, leveraging their authority can enhance collaborative efforts between formal institutions and local communities, ultimately leading to more effective and culturally relevant water management strategies.

8.4 Regulatory Capture in Basin Water Management.

The study's findings indicate that the Densu and Pra Basin boards are predominantly composed of government agencies acting as regulators. This composition raises concerns about the potential for regulatory capture in decision-making (Prihandono & Widiati, 2023; K'Akumu, 2022). When regulatory bodies are primarily filled with representatives from government institutions, there is a risk that the interests of these agencies will take precedence over the needs and concerns of other stakeholders involved in water management.

Limited public participation exacerbates this issue, as relevant stakeholders, including miners, waste collection companies, developers, farmers, and significant water users like beverage producers, are often excluded from the decision-making process. This exclusion leads to decisions being made from a top-down perspective, primarily to satisfy the regulators while neglecting the input and experiences of those directly affected by water management policies. Consequently, the main regulatory agency, the Water Resources Commission (WRC), and the

basin secretariats tend to prioritise the interests of government agencies in their decision-making frameworks.

This focus on government priorities can result in regulatory frameworks that fail to consider the practical needs and concerns of diverse stakeholders. By concentrating solely on meeting regulators' requirements, the decision-making process risks becoming inward-looking. This narrow perspective can overlook the broader, multifaceted implications of water resources management, particularly regarding environmental sustainability and community well-being.

When stakeholders feel sidelined, it can lead to a lack of ownership and commitment to water management initiatives. Moreover, excluding various stakeholders from the decision-making process can undermine public trust in regulatory bodies and diminish the overall effectiveness of water management strategies. When communities and other interest groups perceive that their voices are not being heard or valued, their willingness to cooperate with regulatory efforts diminishes, further complicating the governance of water resources.

To address these issues, a more balanced approach that recognizes the importance of incorporating the interests of all stakeholders, not just government agencies, is essential. Encouraging inclusive participation can lead to more equitable and effective decision-making, ensuring that water management strategies are not only aligned with regulatory requirements but also reflect the realities faced by local communities and industries.

Ultimately, fostering a collaborative environment where diverse stakeholders can engage in meaningful dialogue is crucial for developing water governance frameworks that are both effective and sustainable. By bridging the gap between regulators and stakeholders, it is possible to create a more holistic approach to water resources management that supports environmental sustainability while also addressing the economic and social needs of all parties involved.

8.5 Navigating overlapping and conflicting roles in water governance

The analysis of stakeholder interests revealed that the roles of the Water Resources Commission (WRC) and the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) often overlap, particularly with water pollution control. Both institutions are responsible for safeguarding water resources and preventing pollution, reflecting the stakeholder theory proposed by Freeman (1984), which suggests that the interests of different stakeholders can sometimes overlap or conflict. This overlap is further complicated by the presence of private enterprises,

including small-scale and illegal miners, and traditional leaders whose economic interests often conflict with the conservation efforts led by the WRC and basin secretariats.

Effectively navigating these relationships requires the regulatory bodies to skillfully manage conflicts of interest and sometimes make trade-offs (Freeman, 1984). This means regulators may need to adjust their objectives to find a compromise that aligns with the interests of other stakeholders, such as miners and traditional leaders, who are primarily driven by financial considerations. Rather than expecting these groups to entirely give up their financial interests for conservation, a more balanced approach should be taken. Engaging them in the decision-making process, particularly in addressing issues like illegal mining, which is a major contributor to water pollution, requires finding common ground between economic and environmental goals.

To ensure effective collaboration between the WRC and EPA in pollution control, each institution must clearly understand its specific duties, limits, and contributions to the shared goal of protecting water resources. By highlighting the mutual benefits of collaboration, both the WRC and EPA can understand how working together advances their interests, fostering a sense of ownership and commitment. This approach not only helps prevent duplication of efforts but also enhances the overall impact of their work.

Consequently, fostering collaboration and compromise between these stakeholders allows them to gain broader support for conservation initiatives and work more effectively to combat activities threatening water quality. Balancing environmental conservation with economic realities is key to securing the cooperation of various stakeholders and ensuring the sustainability of Ghana's water resources.

8.6 Stakeholder inclusion and adaptability in basin water governance structure

The results of this study indicate that the composition of stakeholders on the basin boards seems to remain static despite the potential for changes in stakeholder salience, as proposed by Mitchell et al. (1997). The composition of the basin boards seems to reflect that of the national-level WRC board, which sometimes creates an exclusive environment for new stakeholders. At the national level, governance structures are well-established, with long-standing relationships and networks. These structures are often dominated by 'traditional' stakeholders involved in the decision-making process. As a result, these groups wield considerable influence and control over the decision-making process. Since basin boards are modelled after the

national-level WRC board, they inherit many of the same characteristics. This includes the presence of ‘traditional’ established stakeholders on these boards. Their established relationships and influence can make it challenging for new stakeholders to integrate themselves into the decision-making process. For a new stakeholder, breaking into this established network can be daunting. They may find it difficult to have their voices heard or to effect change, as the existing stakeholders may prioritise maintaining the status quo or following an established agenda. An example of the difficulty in including new stakeholders is that when the Densu basin board was formed in 2004, the then Ga South Municipal Assembly was included on the basin board because of the Weija dam, a significant water feature in the basin. However, in 2018, the Ga South Municipality split into two, creating the Weija-Gbawe municipality. After this split, the Weija dam was no longer located in the Ga South municipality but in the Weija-Gbawe municipality. In spite of this change, the Weija-Gbawe Municipal Assembly was not added to the basin board. This situation highlights the challenge of making changes to the already existing basin boards. One way to address this issue is to propose additional engagement mechanisms and establish a lower-level governance structure to involve more stakeholders. From the above narrative, it is evident that stakeholder salience is not static and can change over time (Mitchell et al., 1998). New actors can emerge and influence decision-making processes. Therefore, board membership must be adaptable, evolving to incorporate these newcomers and effectively respond to the shifting landscape of stakeholder interests. The WRC can evaluate the board composition after the board has served its three-year term to determine if there are newcomers who should be included in the decision-making process.

8.7 Hierarchical governance and challenge of local actors in basin water management

Chapter five of this study highlights a critical observation regarding the dynamics of decision-making in basin water management. It reveals that organisations operating outside the central and regional government—particularly those without explicit environmental protection responsibilities—tend to wield significantly less power and influence in shaping water management decisions. This finding aligns with previous research conducted by Mosello et al. (2017), which identified that local-level actors often struggle to gain a foothold in the decision-making processes related to water resources management and development in Ghana.

The diminished authority of these organizations places them in a peripheral role, making it challenging for them to contribute meaningfully to the formulation of policies and strategies

aimed at water resource conservation and protection. This situation emphasizes the hierarchical nature of governance within the sector, where central and regional agencies dominate decision-making, often sidelining voices from local entities. Such a structure fosters a concentration of power at the upper echelons of governance, leading to potential oversight of the valuable insights and needs of smaller, localised stakeholders.

As a result, the experiences and perspectives of community members, small businesses, and non-governmental organisations, who are directly impacted by water management policies, may be inadequately represented. This oversight can perpetuate a cycle of disenfranchisement, where those most affected by water-related decisions are excluded from critical discussions that directly influence their livelihoods and environments. The lack of involvement of these stakeholders not only stifles local knowledge and expertise but also diminishes the potential for crafting well-rounded, effective water management strategies.

Moreover, this imbalance of power can hinder the development of adaptive and resilient water governance frameworks. When decision-making is concentrated within a few central agencies, there is a risk of overlooking unique local challenges and opportunities that could be addressed through collaborative efforts.

To mitigate these issues, it is crucial to decentralise further the decision-making processes in water governance to the local level. Encouraging greater participation from local organisations and actors can enhance the inclusivity and effectiveness of water management strategies. By recognising and integrating the voices of those at the local level, governance structures can be more representative and responsive to the complexities of water resource management. This shift not only empowers marginalised stakeholders but also enriches the decision-making process with diverse perspectives, ultimately leading to more sustainable and equitable outcomes for all involved.

8.8 The illusion of inclusiveness: tokenism in public participation for basin water management

One key finding from this study is that public participation in basin water management may be considered as tokenism (Arnstein, 1969). Tokenism, in this context, refers to the minimal involvement of the public, where participation is more about creating an appearance of inclusiveness rather than genuinely considering public input and integrating it into decision-making processes. In a participatory democracy, citizens have the right to participate in the

decision-making process. This means that citizens should not be just passive recipients of decisions made by authorities but active participants who have a say in shaping policies and strategies. The study highlighted instances where public participation was more about the public only receiving information from regulators. Consultation of water user organisations for IWRM planning is often conducted as a formality, with little to no impact on the final decisions. The tokenistic approach to public participation has implications. It can lead to decisions that only partially reflect the needs and concerns of all stakeholders, notably less powerful groups. Also, when the public perceives their participation as meaningless, it can lead to disengagement and a lack of trust in the institutions responsible for water management.

8.9 Decentralised management and centralised financial control in water resource management

A significant finding from this study is that while the operational management of water resources is delegated to basin boards, the financial resources remain centralised. This means every activity undertaken by the basin boards or basin secretariats requires financial clearance from the central Water Resources Commission (WRC). Although decentralisation aims to empower local units and improve responsiveness to local water issues, the lack of financial autonomy undermines this goal. Decentralised units, including basin secretariats, also operate with minimal autonomy and limited capacity. They frequently need more financial, human and material resources to develop and implement localised water management solutions effectively. These findings are consistent with the research conducted by Agyenim & Gupta (2012), which highlighted the centralisation of financial resources in water resource management. Their study found that decentralised units often need more resources to perform their functions effectively under the IWRM framework. Decentralised units may identify critical needs and propose timely interventions, but the need for immediate financial resources hampers their ability to act swiftly. Thereby creating an implementation gap. This bottleneck can exacerbate water-related problems such as pollution. Enhancing the financial autonomy and capacity of decentralised units could be a crucial step towards more effective and timely water resources management, aligning operational control with the financial resources required to address local needs.

8.10 Weak enforcement in regulatory frameworks for water resources management in Ghana

Water resources management in Ghana predominantly relies on regulatory measures to ensure

the sustainable use and conservation of water bodies. This reliance on regulations aligns with Oh & Svendsen's (2015) assertion that regulatory frameworks are countries' most common instruments for environmental governance. However, the effectiveness of these regulations is significantly compromised in the Densu and Pra River basins by weak enforcement. Thereby creating an implementation gap. This weakness is partly attributed to inadequate funding for governmental agencies responsible for overseeing water resources management. Without sufficient financial resources, these agencies struggle to carry out their mandate effectively, leading to lapses in regulatory enforcement. This situation corroborates Carter's (2007) analysis of regulatory regimes, where he highlights that such regimes are often time-consuming and costly to implement. Carter (2007) further argues that the high costs associated with regulatory enforcement can lead to significant problems when governmental budgets are insufficient to support monitoring and ensure compliance. The situation in the Densu and Pra River basins is a case in point. Despite having regulations in place to govern water usage and protect water quality, weak enforcement due to financial constraints has led to ongoing issues such as pollution, illegal water extraction, and encroachment on water bodies. This financial constraint undermines the agencies' ability to perform routine inspections, respond to violations, and implement corrective measures. As a result, regulatory frameworks that are theoretically robust are rendered ineffective in practice.

8.11 Governance challenges and the water pollution crisis

The issue of illegal mining has emerged as a significant threat to Ghana's water resources, leading to alarming levels of water pollution that jeopardise both environmental sustainability and public health. This ongoing crisis is deeply rooted in governance challenges that have hindered effective oversight and management of the sector. The complexities surrounding illegal mining are multifaceted, with several underlying causes intricately linked to governance failures.

One of the primary drivers of illegal mining is high unemployment, particularly in rural areas where economic opportunities are limited. Many young people, desperate for livelihoods, turn to illegal mining as a means of survival, often without fully understanding the environmental consequences of their actions. This desperation is worsened by the absence of investment in alternative economic activities. As such, illegal mining becomes an attractive option, leading to widespread exploitation of the country's natural resources.

In addition to economic factors, the weak enforcement of existing regulations plays a critical role in the proliferation of illegal mining activities. Regulatory bodies, such as the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), the Minerals Commission and the Water Resources Commission (WRC), are often under-resourced to monitor and enforce compliance effectively. This inadequacy creates a vacuum that allows illegal miners to operate with relative impunity. Moreover, the presence of bribery and corruption within regulatory frameworks further undermines enforcement efforts. When regulatory officials accept bribes to overlook violations, it perpetuates illegal mining practices and erodes public trust in governance institutions.

The lack of political will to decisively address illegal mining is a critical factor contributing to its persistence in Ghana. While the government has publicly acknowledged the severe environmental damage and water pollution caused by illegal mining, it has often hesitated to take firm action against influential individuals, particularly those within the political class, who have been implicated in these activities. This unwillingness to confront key political players involved in illegal mining creates a culture of impunity, where those with connections and influence feel protected from legal or regulatory consequences.

A comprehensive approach is necessary to combat the menace of illegal mining and its detrimental effects on water resources. This approach should include strengthening governance frameworks, enhancing regulatory enforcement, and fostering community engagement in sustainable practices. By addressing the root causes of illegal mining, such as unemployment and lack of alternative livelihoods, Ghana can develop targeted interventions that provide viable economic opportunities for affected communities. Moreover, instilling a culture of accountability and transparency within regulatory bodies is essential for curbing corruption and ensuring that enforcement mechanisms are robust and effective.

8.12 Overdependence on foreign donors

In Chapter Two, the study highlights the critical issue of overreliance on foreign donors within the water sector in sub-Saharan Africa. DANIDA, among other foreign donors, has played a pivotal role in shaping water policies, providing not only financial assistance but also technical expertise and capacity building. Building on the discussions in Chapter Two, Chapter Six delves deeper into the consequences of donor exit, mainly focusing on the WRC and the Densu and Pra River basin boards. Chapter six reveals that the reliance on donors like DANIDA extends beyond policy formulation to the actual operational activities of water management

institutions. This support has enabled WRC and basin boards to perform essential functions such as monitoring water quality and developing water management strategies. However, the chapter highlights a critical issue: the exit of these donors has led to substantial challenges. The withdrawal of donor support has resulted in funding gaps, reduced operational capacities, and a slowdown in the progress of water management initiatives. For instance, without continued financial backing from donors like DANIDA, many river basin boards have struggled to sustain their activities, and they are unable to hold regular board meetings. The study suggests that this overreliance on foreign donors has hampered the development of local capacity and financial independence. It points out the need for a strategic shift towards building sustainable, locally funded water management systems that can operate effectively without external assistance. This transition is crucial to ensure the long-term resilience and autonomy of water management institutions in Ghana.

8.13 Conclusion

Ghana's journey with Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) illustrates a strong commitment to sustainable water governance, yet it also uncovers numerous challenges that demand ongoing attention. While significant strides have been made in adopting IWRM principles—such as establishing institutions like the Water Resources Commission (WRC) and decentralising water management to basin levels—implementation remains hindered by complex political and social dynamics. The involvement of traditional leaders alongside formal institutions plays a critical role in shaping water management strategies, highlighting the necessity of a collaborative governance framework.

The governance structures within the Densu and Pra basin boards reveal a tendency towards regulatory capture, where decision-making processes favour government agencies at the expense of vital stakeholders like miners, waste management firms, farmers, and major water users. The overlapping roles of the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the WRC further complicate these dynamics. Additionally, entrenched governance structures often exclude new stakeholders, exemplified by the Weija-Gbawe Municipal Assembly's marginalisation from the Densu basin board, despite its relevance since 2018. Such exclusivity underscores the need for more robust engagement mechanisms and an inclusive governance model.

Public participation in basin water management frequently appears tokenistic, undermining trust and leading to decisions that do not adequately address stakeholder needs. A genuine participatory process is crucial for developing effective and equitable water management strategies. Moreover, a hierarchical governance structure limits local actors' influence, despite their direct impact on water management outcomes. While responsibilities are decentralised, the centralisation of financial control stifles local units' effectiveness, complicating timely responses to water-related issues.

The water pollution crisis exacerbated by illegal mining stems from governance failures, including weak regulatory enforcement, corruption, and a lack of political will to confront influential actors involved in these activities. Moreover, overreliance on foreign donors, such as DANIDA, creates vulnerabilities within water management institutions, leading to operational challenges and funding gaps that impede essential activities. Weak enforcement of regulatory frameworks, primarily due to insufficient funding, further compromises the effectiveness of otherwise robust regulations.

To address these issues, it is essential to improve engagement mechanisms and adopt a more inclusive governance model that integrates diverse stakeholders. Moving beyond tokenistic public participation is vital for rebuilding trust and formulating effective water management strategies. Additionally, enhancing the financial autonomy and capacity of decentralised units is critical to reducing dependency on foreign donors. Strengthening regulatory enforcement and promoting transparency, alongside providing alternative economic opportunities for affected communities, will be crucial for mitigating illegal mining impacts and safeguarding Ghana's water resources for long-term sustainability.

CHAPTER NINE

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

9.1 Introduction

During my research, I have analysed the social, political, and institutional factors that affect water resources management in the Densu and Pra river basins. My goal was to understand the decision-making process in river basin governance, including the actors involved, their motivations, and the mechanisms guiding their actions. By asking the question, how do stakeholder constraints impact effective water governance in the Densu and Pra River Basins in Ghana, and what innovative strategies can be developed to enhance resilience and improve water resources management? I analysed the various challenges stakeholders face that hinder the effective implementation of water governance practices in these regions. I identified opportunities and potential strategies for improving water resource management using this information. Additionally, I analysed the decision-making framework at the basin level and proposed innovative changes to enhance stakeholder engagement and participation.

Since adopting the Ghana national water policy in 2007, the Water Resources Commission has practised the principles of IWRM to manage water resources effectively and ensure the broader participation of stakeholders. One critical aspect of IWRM is the engagement of a wide range of actors from the private and non-profit sectors in decision-making processes. However, my thesis reveals that the private sector is not consulted in the Densu or Pra River basins, and citizens are not directly involved in decision-making. Instead, decision-making processes are such that they are left to experts who consult as necessary with some interest groups representing the aggregated public interest.

The study shows that decision-making in both the Densu and Pra basins occurs at two levels: the national and regional (basin) levels. The Water Resources Commission is responsible for decision-making at the national level, and its decisions have an impact on the Densu and Pra basins. The River Basin Board is in charge of decision-making at the regional level. The level at which decisions are taken, the composition of the basin board, and the discussions during board meetings require the participation of mainly water management experts. It seems that it might be difficult to involve local people as part of the board, as they and local interest groups may feel out of place at that level of decision-making. Going into this study, my anticipation was that many challenges, including those connected to stakeholder engagement, constrain stakeholders' ability to manage water resources effectively in the Densu and Pra basins.

The study concludes that the governance processes of the Densu and Pra River basins appear to be largely technocratic. This means that the basin boards, which serve as technical representatives of selected government ministries, departments, agencies, local government authorities, non-governmental organisations and traditional authorities, tend to approach problem-solving more technically and analytically. Although this technocratic approach to governance is not necessarily problematic, there is consensus among study participants that the decision-making process could benefit from greater consultation and engagement with local communities, private sector entities, and a wider range of interest groups and non-profit organisations. In particular, greater consultation can help ensure these groups' needs and concerns are considered in regional decision-making processes. By doing so, achieving more inclusive and sustainable governance processes that better reflect the diversity of interests and perspectives within the Densu and Pra River basins may be possible.

The following section provides a summary of additional discoveries. These are under the following headings: (a) Decision-making process, stakeholders and interests, (b) Stakeholder dynamics in river basin management and (c) barriers and opportunities for effective river basin management. The third section of this chapter follows the findings and conclusions section and discusses the policy implications of the study findings for river basin governance. The fourth section of this chapter presents the proposed framework for better stakeholder participation in water governance at the basin level. The fifth section highlights areas that require further research, and the last section concludes with general comments.

9.2 General findings and conclusions

9.2.1 Decision-making process, stakeholders and interests

The first question investigated was: what are the decision-making processes, who are the key stakeholders involved in the decision-making processes in the Densu and Pra River basins, and what are their interests in river basin management? My primary focus was to understand the institutional arrangements in place for making water decisions at the basin level and to determine the interests of these stakeholders in river basin management.

The study revealed that the formal decision-making process is quite identical for both the Densu and the Pra basins and describes how decisions are generally made for managing any river basin in Ghana. The decision-making body of the river basin, the basin board, makes the decisions in the form of proposals for the Densu and Pra basins secretariats and other partners to implement. The study again revealed that the composition of the Densu and Pra basin boards

mimics that of the Water Resources Commission board at the national level, which is made of 15 members, out of which about 10 are from state regulatory institutions. As a result, the decision-making processes are mostly controlled by regulatory institutions, which are considered traditional actors with key attributes such as power, legitimacy, and urgency. These attributes were proposed by Mitchell et al. (1997) as important characteristics of stakeholders of salience that water managers should pay attention to. However, there is a lack of representation of regulated entities such as private enterprises and the local people. One of the reasons for the exclusion of these primary stakeholders is that decision-making occurs at the regional (basin) level. At the same time, those affected by the regulators' decisions are mostly at the local level.

Chapter Four of this study observed that the composition of the Densu and Pra basin boards is not uniform. The basin boards comprise various institutions, some common to both boards, while others are unique to the Densu or Pra basin board. For instance, only the Densu board has representation from the Ministry of Health. In contrast, the Pra Basin board has the Minerals Commission and the Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority represented on the board. This arrangement is based on the distinctive characteristics of each basin, which inform the selection of institutions that are best suited to address the specific challenges and needs of that particular basin.

Ideally and at a general level, the state institutions on the boards share a common interest: conserving a healthy environment, particularly water resources. These state institutions include agencies, such as the Environmental Protection Agency and Forestry Commission. They are committed to preserving the environment and ensuring the sustainable use of natural resources for all to benefit. Similarly, the NGOs on the basin boards also share a similar interest in environmental conservation and the well-being of local communities. They work hand in hand with the state institutions to achieve these common goals. Apart from the interest in environmental conservation, the state agencies are also driven by economic interests and gains and by a range of other rationales, but their mandate to protect the environment tends to supersede other interests. For the traditional authority, their interest may be a bit different. While the traditional authority as an institution represents the interest of the local people and deities, individual traditional leaders may be driven by other interests, such as financial gain. This usually leads to conflicts of interest regarding environmental conservation and resource management.

The study shows that in addition to the regional-level representatives, the basin boards also have representatives of local government authorities, known as Metropolitan, Municipal, and District Assemblies (MMDAs). These MMDAs are mandated by the Local Governance Act of 2016, Act 936, and the National Development Planning (System) Regulations LI 1878 to plan, initiate and implement development programs at the local level. They also plan for the physical environment, recognising that the environment plays a vital role in the economic activities and livelihoods of the people in the area.

The nature of decision-making processes in the Densu and Pra basins leads to more communication and cooperation between the river basin offices and other state agencies and departments. The shared interest in protecting water resources is the driving force behind this collaboration, as it aligns with the mandates of these institutions. Environmental concerns are a top priority for these agencies, and there is widespread agreement on the importance of effective water resources management in the basin. Despite having similar goals, each organisation may have its own approach to achieving these goals. This highlights the importance of engagement in minimising conflicts and establishing a common path for managing water resources in the Densu and Pra basins. Therefore, regular basin board meetings are crucial in coordinating and aligning efforts towards this common goal.

9.2.2 Stakeholder dynamics

The second question investigated was: how are stakeholder dynamics affecting water resources management in the Densu and Pra River basins? This investigation focused on analysing the level of engagement between basin offices and stakeholder groups. This also included an examination of the commitment of key stakeholders to river basin management and their participation in decision-making and implementation. The study found a high level of engagement between the basin offices, government departments, and agencies, particularly those on the basin boards. These departments and agencies are involved in various aspects of water resources management in the Densu and Pra basins, including decision-making, implementation, benefits, and monitoring. Despite regular contact and awareness of the issues related to basin protection through meetings and workshops, insufficient resources, capacity, and funding tend to hinder their joint efforts to manage water resources effectively in the two basins.

The study revealed that private enterprises operating within the Densu and Pra River basins have a weak engagement with the basin offices and the Water Resources Commission. These

enterprises report that they are not engaged during decision-making processes related to water resource management activities. This has led to dissatisfaction among private enterprises who feel they could contribute to water resource management if involved in decision-making. Private enterprises have desired more attention from the basin offices and the Water Resources Commission to improve cooperation and collaboration in managing the basins' water resources. They believe this will help them pay their water use fees promptly and support water resource management activities more effectively. By working together, private enterprises and the basin offices can develop a more robust and sustainable approach to water resource management in the Densu and Pra River basin offices, benefitting all stakeholders in the region.

Chapter Five clarified that the selection process for members of the Densu and Pra basin boards is based on their institutional involvement in water resource management, which relates to utilising, conserving and developing water resources. Moreover, the selected individuals on the basin boards possess certain knowledge and expertise in water resource management. This is because managing the Densu and Pra basins seems a complex task requiring technical expertise in basin board work. To further enhance their skills, the selected members must undergo training to comprehend fully the complexities of basin board work. Therefore, it is quite apparent that managing the Densu and Pra basins is a challenging task that may be quite daunting for non-experts.

Furthermore, available data from the study shows that stakeholders can significantly impact the successful management of river basins. Specifically, traditional and political leaders have been identified as key stakeholders whose actions may hinder the effective management of water resources in the Densu and Pra basins. This is a concerning issue, as traditional and political leaders hold significant influence and power over the people and may not prioritise sustainable water management practices. Also, it has been observed that small-scale miners who possess mining licenses are also contributors to water pollution in these basins. This highlights the need for increased awareness and enforcement of regulations on mining activities to protect water resources and promote sustainable development.

In terms of the environmental problems plaguing the Densu and Pra River basins, the study reveals that the experts of the basin board and the local community members, comprising of farmers and fishermen, are on the same page when it comes to identifying the environmental issues that the Densu and Pra basins are currently facing. Both the experts and laypeople have a mutual understanding of the severity of the issues and agree that water pollution is the most

serious problem that must be addressed urgently. For the laypeople, they communicate their concerns about these issues through the MMDAs, and local offices of the GWCL and CWSA, hoping it gets the attention of the central government for onward address. The pollution of the water bodies has been primarily caused by illegal and small-scale mining activities, which release harmful substances into the water, making it unfit for human consumption and aquatic life. Also, improper waste disposal practices have been identified as a significant contributing factor to the worsening water pollution in both basins. Interestingly, the local community members, who are not experts in the field, have provided valuable insights into the environmental issues, their causes and potential solutions. Their viewpoint sheds light on the social and political values of the problems that must be acknowledged and dealt with to find lasting solutions.

9.2.3 Barriers and Opportunities

The third question I investigated was: what are the key barriers and opportunities to effective water resources management in the Densu and Pra River basins? As shown in Chapter Six, the analysis of various barriers to effective water resources management shows how a top-down approach to policy and plan implementation prevails in the water management sector. This approach involves decisions being made by top public servants, such as those in the river basin boards. The study identified that most of the barriers are associated with this approach, including policy implementation gap, insufficient funding, political influences, inadequate logistics and personnel, and low levels of awareness. These barriers highlight the need for a more collaborative and inclusive water resource management approach involving local stakeholders.

The study's findings agree with Winter's (2012) argument that inter-organisational implementation behaviour indicates varying levels of commitment and coordination in policy and plan implementation. In terms of managing water resources, state organisations agree on implementing decisions. This understanding is derived from their mandate and participation in basin decision-making. Some state organisations also rely on the output of others as input for their work. For instance, the basin office and WRC depend on issuing an environmental permit by the EPA before granting a water use permit. Although private enterprises may see this as a bureaucratic process that slows down the water use application process, these organisations can coordinate such that if the proposed activity harms water resources, the EPA will first deny the application. However, mining poses a significant problem. Because of their economic and

political interests, there is less cooperation and commitment from actors like traditional authorities, political leaders, and private enterprises. While state institutions work to prevent water resources from degrading, some traditional leaders, political leaders, and private enterprises work against this objective. These interests led to interference by political leaders with the work of state institutions that would have made decisions favouring the environment and the people they served.

Another conclusion from Chapter Six is the challenges faced by the managers of water resources, particularly the Water Resources Commission and basin offices. These managers are confronted with a multitude of demands, but they have limited resources at their disposal to meet them. The study sheds light on the role of street-level bureaucrats responsible for managing water resources and making discretionary decisions concerning the buffer zone policy designed to protect water resources from pollution and other environmental hazards. Although these street-level bureaucrats are guided by principles when making these decisions, there is room for interpretation, which can lead to biases in delivering their mandates. To address these concerns, some managers and street-level bureaucrats have suggested that the buffer zone policy needs to be reviewed to eliminate all the confusing parts. This will help ensure the policy is implemented fairly and equitably, without any biases or inconsistencies that may undermine its effectiveness. Managers of the environment, including those overseeing water resources, advocate for transforming the buffer zone policy into a legislative instrument to ensure its enforcement and compliance. This policy, which currently serves as a guideline for protecting water bodies and surrounding ecosystems, lacks the legal backing needed to guarantee adherence and accountability.

Addressing the barriers to effective water resources management in the Densu and Pra Basins is imperative for sustainable development and environmental preservation. The challenges of gaps in policy implementation, personnel deficits, logistical constraints, and low levels of awareness highlight the need for robust structural and strategic reforms. The negative behaviour of citizens and stakeholders, weak law enforcement, and conflicting interests and priorities further complicate these efforts. Additionally, the influence of political power and the low political commitment to enforcing regulations exacerbate these issues, making it crucial for a more concerted and unified approach.

Though there are barriers, opportunities do exist, such as the holistic planning and collaborative efforts spearheaded by the WRC, which have laid a strong foundation for effective water

resources management in the Densu and Pra Basins. The basin IWRM plans are dynamic and adaptable, ensuring that strategies remain relevant and responsive to changing environmental and societal conditions. The support from government institutions, NGOs, corporate bodies, and donor agencies to help advance the WRC's mandate. Corporate entities' commitment to environmental sustainability, combined with increased public awareness of climate change and pollution, fosters a conducive environment for proactive water management initiatives. Again, the presence of research institutions that provide valuable data, technological innovations, and expertise enables evidence-based decision-making and the development of advanced management practices. The availability of robust regulations and government policies to strengthen the framework for sustainable water management, promoting best practices.

By harnessing these diverse opportunities, the WRC and basin offices can overcome the barriers and ensure the long-term sustainability and health of the water resources in the Densu and Pra Basins. The holistic planning and collaborative efforts spearheaded by the WRC have already established a solid groundwork that can be built upon to tackle challenges such as resource allocation, stakeholder coordination, and environmental threats. Leveraging the dynamic and adaptable nature of the IWRM plans allows the basin secretariat to stay responsive to evolving environmental and societal conditions, ensuring that their strategies remain relevant and effective. The support from various stakeholders—including government institutions, NGOs, corporate bodies, and donor agencies—provides essential resources and cooperation, enhancing the basin secretariats' capacity to implement solutions. Corporate entities' commitment to environmental sustainability and the growing public awareness of climate change and pollution foster a proactive approach to water management initiatives. Moreover, research institutions that contribute valuable data, technological innovations, and expertise tend to facilitate evidence-based decision-making and the development of advanced management practices. Robust regulations and government policies further solidify the framework for sustainable water management, promoting adherence to best practices.

Also, leveraging the strengths of the media, collaborative anti-galamsey taskforces, performance assessments, and the LWC model can be helpful. The heightened public awareness and support, driven by extensive media coverage, provide a valuable platform for the WRC to engage with communities and stakeholders. By utilising various media channels, including social media, the WRC can educate the public on the importance of water conservation and the detrimental impacts of illegal mining, thereby fostering a more informed

and proactive populace. The introduction of anti-galamsey taskforces marks a crucial step in combating illegal mining activities that threaten the basin's water resources. These task forces enhance the WRC's capacity for monitoring, enforcement, and rapid response, ensuring more effective regulation and mitigation of environmental damage. The concept of Local Water Committees (LWC) provides a solid framework for decentralised and community-focused water management. By fully implementing sub-basin secretariats and expanding the LWC model, the WRC can ensure comprehensive coverage and localised management of the basin, optimising resource utilisation and enhancing community involvement in water conservation efforts. Additionally, the proliferation of drinking water-producing enterprises presents an opportunity for the WRC to increase its internally generated funds through licensing and permit fees. Encouraging corporate social responsibility (CSR) contributions from these enterprises can further support water resource management projects, community education initiatives, and infrastructure improvements. By capitalising on these opportunities, the WRC can turn public support into a powerful advocacy tool.

On the one hand, it appears that without a strong political commitment to protecting the environment, overcoming the identified barriers will not be possible. Political power seems to be the most influential factor in addressing environmental concerns, and it can override any other will and interests. On the other hand, the study indicates that citizens also hold significant power and can push those in authority, including political leaders, to be more accountable and take a stronger stance against environmental degradation. To create a more sustainable environment, it is essential to empower citizens and increase their knowledge about the environment in their locality. This can be achieved by increasing sensitisation efforts, which can help change negative attitudes and enable citizens to demand accountability from duty-bearers. As citizens become more responsive, there will be a more significant commitment to effective law enforcement.

9.3 Policy Recommendations

9.3.1 Increasing public participation

The study has revealed a need for more public engagement and participation in decision-making regarding the management of basin water resources. Without opportunities for public participation, individuals are less likely to engage with environmental issues. Therefore, it is important to find ways to involve the public in decision-making to ensure effective river basin governance. Engaging local people can enhance the situational analysis of problems and issues

carried out by water experts and contribute to achieving practical solutions, resulting in successful implementation. The study has shown that citizens hold significant power, in spite of the challenges of poverty and unemployment, they can support water resources management. Public participation can be enhanced by extending the consultation platform and time. The Water Resources Commission (WRC) and basin offices can incorporate public hearings in their approach, where interested members of the public can listen to the commission's proposals and provide feedback. This can be done while elaborating the basin IWRM plan and engaging other stakeholders. Public hearings will represent community involvement, alert the commission of potential social, political, and legal obstacles, meet legal or procedural requirements, and mitigate opposition. Public hearings are also a way of increasing the visibility of the Water Resources Commission and the basin offices to citizens.

Water resources management is a critical issue in Ghana, and the government is implementing a water policy to address the challenges. One primary policy focus is decentralising decision-making to lower levels, enabling broader stakeholder participation. This approach ensures that most stakeholders are consulted, and their interests and concerns are considered while making decisions about water resources management in the basins. To achieve this, the Water Resources Commission should establish Water Resources User Associations made up of local water users as partnering groups to interact with the river basin secretariats. These associations will report to the basin office and help expand the decision-making platform. The involvement of various stakeholders, such as farmers, fishermen, industry representatives, local government officials, and environmentalists, will ensure that all perspectives are considered while making decisions about water resources management. It will also help build trust and support for water resource management initiatives among the local communities. This approach is crucial for achieving sustainable, equitable, and efficient use of water resources, leading to better outcomes for everyone involved.

9.3.2 Enhancing public participation to raise environmental awareness

Public participation is intrinsically linked to the level of awareness about environmental issues. When the public is actively involved in environmental decision-making processes, their awareness and understanding of these issues naturally increase. This participation fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility towards environmental stewardship. However, in the cases of the Densu and Pra River basins, where public participation is low, the causes of the low level of awareness about environmental concerns need to be addressed. Firstly, increasing

funding for environmental institutions, including the basin secretariat, is crucial. Adequate financial resources will enable these organisations to create more avenues for public involvement, such as community meetings, workshops, and public consultations. Also, hiring and training more personnel dedicated to environmental education and outreach will help reach a broader audience effectively. Again, cultural attitudes towards the environment need to be transformed. This can be achieved through integrating environmental education into school curriculums from an early age, ensuring that children grow up with a strong understanding and appreciation of environmental stewardship. Public campaigns that highlight the cultural heritage of environmental stewardship can also help shift societal values. Additionally, aligning economic development with environmental conservation is important. Promoting green businesses and demonstrating the economic benefits of environmental conservation can encourage individuals and businesses to adopt eco-friendly practices that safeguard water resources.

9.3.3 Harnessing the local government system

An important policy focus for effectively managing water resources is using local governments as rallying points to bring stakeholders together. To achieve this, basin boards can collaborate with the Metropolitan, Municipal, and District Assemblies to establish stakeholder education programmes at the local level. One way to raise awareness of water-related issues among local actors is to use town hall meetings for engagement. Local stakeholders can be educated about the importance of conserving and protecting water resources by bringing basin offices and assemblies together. These meetings can be used to discuss sustainable water use practices, pollution prevention measures, and the role of local communities in water resource management. Additionally, this approach can generate interest among local stakeholders in supporting water conservation efforts. By working together, the local government system and water governance can protect water resources for current and future generations.

9.3.4 Strengthening institutional capacity

The Densu and Pra Basin offices currently require additional staff members. Consequently, it is crucial to ensure enough office space is available to accommodate the new staff members and provide them with a comfortable working environment. Moreover, it is essential to equip the offices with the necessary office equipment to maintain and improve the overall productivity and efficiency of the office. Also, there is a pressing need to invest in better logistical resources to support ecological monitoring and collect more comprehensive data on

water resources to ensure their sustainable management for future generations. To strengthen the capacity of the basin boards, it is imperative to reconstitute them to respond to the issues in the basin. This can be achieved by including some essential stakeholders to help address basin issues. For instance, the Densu basin is currently facing a critical issue of encroachment of wetlands and buffers. It is recommended that the Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority and the Greater Accra Regional House of Chiefs be represented on the Densu board to address this issue. These two institutions have the potential to help deal with the issue of encroachment.

9.3.5 Resolving financial constraints

The government of Ghana can take a bold step by allowing state agencies like the Water Resources Commission to access a greater part of its Internally Generated Funds (IGF) than what is being practised at the moment for water resources management. The WRC should also propose to the Ministry of Sanitation and Water Resources the implementation of 'the polluter pays' principle, which can help raise revenue for water resources management. Under this principle, the government can levy charges on domestic and commercial water users for sewer and sewage treatment costs, which will be included in their water supply bills. These charges will be based on the volumetric water consumption rates, and the revenue raised can be earmarked for managing the country's water resources. Individuals and companies who pollute water sources can also be surcharged. By applying this approach, the government can ensure that the polluters, rather than the general public, bear the water resource management costs while simultaneously generating revenue to maintain and improve the country's water resources. Again, though the WRC must follow the procedures to access its internally generated funds from the Bank of Ghana to ensure accountability and transparency in utilising public funds, the process adds to the delay in releasing funds. It is crucial to, therefore, consider the impact of this delay on the ability of government officials to carry out their duties and the effect on the public who depend on these services.

9.3.6 Strengthening Ghana's Water Policy through WRC and EPA Collaboration

The environmental economic principle "polluter pays" is integrated into Ghana's water policy to deter the uncontrolled discharge of pollutants into the environment, including water bodies (Government of Ghana, 2007). However, despite its potential benefits in combating water pollution, the principle is only being implemented partially. Recognising this gap, the WRC is working to ensure full implementation by developing additional regulations and pushing for the passage of a legislative instrument on Pollution Control and Effluent Discharge.

Meanwhile, the EPA, which also holds responsibility for effluent discharge and pollution control, has expressed its intention to lead this process. It is, therefore, crucial for the Ministry of Sanitation and Water Resources to ensure the WRC and EPA to collaborate and agree on the best path forward to prevent delays or conflicts that could hinder progress. Effective cooperation between these organisations will be essential to achieve comprehensive and enforceable pollution control measures, thereby enhancing the protection and management of Ghana's water resources.

9.3.7 Private sector engagement

Water resources management is a shared duty that requires participation from policymakers and stakeholders. The proper management of water resources requires the involvement of institutions and actors from both the public and private sectors. This study has shown that the private sector is not adequately involved in river basin management. Therefore, engaging the private sector at all levels of water governance is recommended. The WRC should actively involve private sector actors in workshops and stakeholder meetings. Private sector actors, such as industries producing drinking water and beverages, have a significant role to play in designing and implementing plans and policies. Their participation will contribute to having more diversity in the stakeholders engaged. This diversity can provide multiple checks to gauge what works, what does not, and what could work better regarding water governance. It can also enrich the plans of the WRC beyond what a single stakeholder group could achieve. The participation of the private sector actors will also serve as the foundation for cooperation between the WRC and the private sector. This will help private actors adhere to the water use regulations, making the basin offices more effective in managing water resources.

9.3.8 Dealing with water pollution challenges

The problem of illegal mining has been extensively studied, and its adverse impact on water resources has been highlighted. This issue is widespread and requires urgent attention. It is believed that traditional leaders can play an essential role in curbing this menace. This is especially evident from the presence of traditional leaders in the Densu and Pra basin boards, which indicates their crucial role in administering natural resources in the country. To successfully manage natural resources such as land, water, and forests, the cooperation of traditional leaders is necessary. Therefore, they are often included in the decision-making process. In this regard, the government can adopt a hybrid system of granting mining permits, where traditional leaders are consulted before mining permits are granted. This will ensure that

the traditional leaders know the implications of mining activities and can provide their input accordingly. Although some traditional leaders may abuse their power concerning the granting of permits, this can be addressed by making them co-owners. When traditional leaders are made co-owners, they know that their names will be mentioned when there is any illegality. This will put their actions in check and ensure they act responsibly and in the community's best interest.

9.3.9 Active community participation

One of the critical factors in protecting water bodies is ensuring active participation from community members. The government can introduce the payment for ecosystem services as an important water resource management policy instrument. This means that farmers and landowners who live and work around these water bodies must be incentivised to protect them actively. This will ensure they are not compensated with minimal money or other resources in exchange for giving up their lands. Instead, they should be given the tools and resources needed to become active stewards of these critical natural resources to play a meaningful role in their ongoing preservation and maintenance. This can include training and education programs, financial incentives and other resources that can help them take a more proactive role in protecting the health and well-being of these vital ecosystems. WRC, Ghana Water Company and the Ministry of Sanitation and Water Resources should spearhead this recommendation.

9.3.10 Using the gospel to save the environment: The role of churches

In the past, water resources in Ghana were traditionally managed using a system of taboos. These taboos consisted of rules and regulations governing the use of water sources to keep them clean and healthy. The taboos were linked to the river deities, and any actions deemed harmful or disrespectful to the river deities were considered punishable offences. These offences were thought to anger the river gods, and offenders were required to pay a price to appease them. However, in recent times, the traditional water governance system has fallen out of use, largely due to the emergence of statutory laws and Christianity. Ghana has a predominantly Christian population, with approximately 71 percent of citizens practising the religion. Given this, there is an opportunity for the state to collaborate with religious organisations to help protect the environment, including water resources, from further harm. Religious leaders have a significant influence over their followers and can be important advocates for environmental conservation. By engaging pastors and other religious figures, the government can encourage them to preach about the importance of preserving the environment, including the need to protect water resources. With the support of the churches, the government

can potentially influence the behaviour of most Ghanaians and promote a more responsible and sustainable approach to managing the environment.

9.4 Framework for improved stakeholder participation

The final question asked was: how can stakeholder participation in water resource management at the basin level be improved? In response to this question, I make recommendations to the current decision-making framework to improve stakeholder involvement, as shown in Figure 9.1 below.

Figure 9.1: Framework for improved stakeholder participation

Source: Author's construct, 2023, based on Winter 2012

Figure 9.1 actively presents a framework designed to improve stakeholder participation in basin water management in Ghana. The Basin Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) Plan drives annual water management activities, serving as the central guide for the entire process. In addition to these annual activities, basin water resources management also incorporates proposals from the River Basin Board (RBB), which are shaped by monitoring efforts and stakeholder complaints. This approach ensures that the management plan continuously adapts to real-world conditions.

The RBB acts as a crucial platform for decision-making and coordination, bringing together diverse stakeholders, including metropolitan, municipal, and district assemblies, government ministries, traditional authorities, NGOs, and regional coordinating councils. This inclusive board guarantees representation across various sectors, helping to steer water management initiatives effectively.

The Water Resources Commission (WRC) plays a central regulatory role, receiving input from the RBB, funding its activities, and collaborating with other stakeholders to implement water management strategies. Several key bodies are responsible for executing RBB proposals and annual plans:

- The Basin Secretariat handles daily operations and manages the implementation of the basin IWRM plan;
- Regulatory and Information Bodies provide the necessary data and regulatory oversight for informed decision-making;
- Management Bodies manage the operational aspects of water resource management; and
- Institutions for Coordination ensure that all stakeholders are aligned and collaborate efficiently.

A vital group for successful implementation is the Water Users, who not only benefit from the management outcomes but also play an active role in the process. The framework highlights how their engagement and behavior directly affect the success of implementation efforts. Additionally, feedback mechanisms ensure that lessons learned during implementation are communicated back to the RBB and WRC, facilitating continuous adjustments and improvements in water resources management policies and practices.

To further enhance stakeholder participation in decision-making and implementation, the framework suggests addressing gaps in stakeholder participation through these:

- Basin Secretariats should collaborate more with municipalities to increase cooperation on water management and stakeholder education.
- The WRC should establish water resource user associations, involve the private sector in workshops, and provide relevant information to all stakeholders to boost engagement.
- The WRC should strengthen Basin Secretariats by setting up sub-basin offices, creating dedicated funds for basin board meetings, and ensuring the timely selection of board representatives.
- The WRC must ensure that civil servants, not political figures, represent institutions on River Basin Boards, maintaining a focus on technical expertise and neutrality.

This active approach encourages better stakeholder involvement and more effective management of Ghana's water resources.

9.5 Areas of further research

The study's objective was to assess the challenges faced by various stakeholders in implementing effective water governance. The researcher conducted in-depth interviews with various stakeholders to gather relevant data. The study provided valuable insights from formal institutions involved in water governance and the informal sector, including water users such as farmers and fishermen. However, the study could not cover significant water users such as artisanal miners, sand winners, waste disposal companies, developers, and industries, or specific attention to issues of environmental justice and social equity including gender. To establish a more comprehensive and inclusive water governance system, further research is needed to focus on non-traditional actors like those mentioned above and determine their willingness to participate in decision-making processes. Additionally, it would be helpful to explore how these groups prioritise their interests and whether they are open to collaborative approaches that benefit the community.

This study discovered that the Densu and Pra river basins face very similar environmental challenges. The primary cause of this problem is high pollution levels, mainly due to illegal mining and other human activities. These activities severely threaten the water ecosystem and the health of people living in the surrounding areas. However, some river basins in the country are performing better and not experiencing such high pollution levels. Therefore, it is suggested that a comparative study be conducted between one of these basins and either the Densu or Pra basins. Such a study would help gain a more in-depth understanding of how other basins

manage different interests in river basin management. The insights and lessons from this comparative study could help tackle the problems the Densu and Pra basins face more effectively and sustainably. By implementing the findings from this new study, it is possible to develop a more robust and comprehensive management plan for these river basins, which would help preserve the aquatic ecosystem and safeguard the health of people living in these areas.

This research study focused on analysing the interactions and collaborative efforts between the river basin offices and other key stakeholders in water resources management. The findings of this study can be used as a stepping stone to explore avenues for future research that could delve into the interactions among a broader range of stakeholders underscoring the imperative of advancing our understanding of water governance through comprehensive stakeholder engagement. This suggestion extends an invitation for researchers to embark on inquiries that surpass the current scope, aiming to unravel the intricate relationships, collaborations, and conflicts that exist within the multifaceted tapestry of water resource management. Further studies into the potential conflicts between different stakeholders and effective strategies to resolve them can help increase our understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of inclusive water governance and contribute significantly to identifying the suitable methods and approaches that can be adopted to engage more actors in water management. The ultimate goal of such research is to encourage the participation of various stakeholders in the decision-making process, even if it may require them to make compromises, and to bring about positive changes in the water resources management sector.

This thesis highlights the role of diverse interest groups in water governance. However, it also emphasises that stakeholder engagement and public participation alone are insufficient to achieve improved water resource management since many other challenges are plaguing water resource management. Further research is needed to focus on water resources assessment to understand the resources and the needs of key institutions involved in water governance. This information can then be used to develop tailored solutions to address these institutions' resource challenges. Understanding the specific needs of key players in water governance can help create an environment for better management of water resources. By doing so, we can ensure the sustainable use of water resources for future generations while promoting the welfare of society as a whole.

9.6 Concluding remarks

Through analysing the decision-making processes and implementation of water resources management decisions at the river basin level, this thesis has brought to light many significant issues that plague the governance system in charge of managing the country's water resources. The study thoroughly examined the network of stakeholders involved in decision-making and implementation processes within the Densu and Pra River basins. It investigated the multifaceted factors influencing their decisions, outlining the institutional frameworks, administrative regulations, and operational practices guiding their actions. By exploring these dynamics, the study provides a detailed map of the platforms available to stakeholders. These platforms provide opportunities for expressing diverse interests, addressing concerns, and fostering meaningful engagements within the socio-ecological and socio-political fabric of the Densu and Pra River basins.

Also, the research has uncovered a range of factors that severely limit the effectiveness of stakeholders in their efforts to manage water resources optimally. These constraints include, but are not limited to, political and economic factors, institutional capacity, and stakeholder participation. The findings of this research provide valuable insights which could inform policy reforms and interventions to improve the management of this vital resource. These insights shed light on the existing obstacles and present invaluable opportunities for transformative policy reforms and interventions to enhance water resource management. While challenges are evident, the outlined opportunities provide a blueprint for transformative action. By harnessing media advocacy, collaborating with task forces, obtaining the cooperation of traditional leaders, and promoting community participation, stakeholders and policymakers can forge a more resilient, inclusive, and sustainable trajectory for water resources management within the Densu and Pra basins. If holistically integrated and supported by concerted efforts, these strategies can prompt positive change, safeguarding these water sources for present and future generations. The understanding provided by this research into the challenges stakeholders face in achieving sustainable water governance can be a compass for environmental policy reforms.

Furthermore, the study's findings regarding negative behaviours of individuals and companies, coupled with weak law enforcement, underscores the necessity for robust regulatory frameworks and stringent enforcement mechanisms. Addressing conflicting interests and priorities also demands an approach that navigates divergent stakeholder objectives, advocating for consensus-building mechanisms and collaborative platforms to reconcile these differences.

The study findings moreover highlights the significance of the governance rules, practices, and processes in the Densu and Pra basins, which are similar to other river basins in the country. The institutional framework, administrative setup, and decision-making processes governing river basin management are comparable throughout the country. Therefore, the study's results have far-reaching implications, and the insights gathered from this study can be applied to other river basins in the country. The study has found that the success or failure of water-related decisions depends on the collaboration, cooperation, and communication among key actors involved in the decision-making process. This means that the interactions between these actors determine the outcome. Therefore, it is crucial to establish effective mechanisms for facilitating these interactions to ensure the optimal outcome of water-related decisions.

Collaboration among stakeholders for effective water resources management requires a comprehensive and inclusive approach involving local and central governments, state agencies, communities, traditional leaders, and private sector entities. For this collective effort to be successful, all stakeholders must be willing to adopt a multi-faceted strategy and work together in a cohesive and mutually beneficial manner. This entails a readiness to negotiate and find common ground to ensure that all parties involved contribute to and benefit from the outcomes. The success of this collaborative effort depends on the willingness of stakeholders to compromise and be flexible when needed. State agencies have a crucial role in this framework and should be open to new ideas to ensure that all stakeholders' interests are fairly considered. By fostering a collaborative environment that values flexibility and compromise, stakeholders can establish a sustainable model for water resource management. This model can serve as an example for other regions facing similar challenges.

One of the most important takeaways from the study is the urgent need for increased political commitment towards sustainable water governance. Without strong political will, it becomes difficult to implement effective policies and initiatives that can help manage water resources in the Densu and Pra basins. Therefore, there is a need for a paradigm shift in leadership engagement to prioritise water resource management in these areas.

The study on water governance in Ghana's Densu and Pra River basins aims to significantly contribute to river basin management. Its findings can guide policymakers, stakeholders, and experts in developing effective strategies for sustainable water resource management in the country. This study aims to offer a nuanced understanding of the complex interplay between socio-economic, environmental, and political factors, which can be useful in developing

comprehensive policies prioritising the preservation and equitable use of water resources while addressing conflicting interests and growing demands. Hopefully, overall, this research enriches academic discourse and is a practical resource for developing and implementing evidence-based initiatives promoting long-term sustainability and fair use of water resources in Ghana's river basins.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Introduction Letter to Interviewee

LETTER OF INTRODUCTION OF RESEARCH

CREAM – Building Climate-Resilience into Basin Water Management

This letter is to inform your office that a team of researchers will be visiting your communities for the purposes of data collection. During the visit, they will interview opinion leaders and residents to collect data ranging from socio-economic, water quality, and water flow regime. The data collection exercise is part of a project dubbed **Building Climate-Resilience into Basin Water Management (CREAM)** supported by the Danish International Development Agency (DANIDA). This project will be implemented in two river basins: the Pra and Densu which are among river basins in Ghana faced with numerous Water Resources Management challenges. In addition to small scale mining and deforestation problems, improper disposal of waste into these rivers has resulted in deterioration of the quality of water in the two rivers. Both land degradation and water pollution have negatively affected the ecosystems of the two basins and consequently the benefits of services derived from them. Climate Change and future socio-economic developments are likely to exacerbate the Water Resources Management challenges in the two basins by aggravating the already water stressed situation and deepening the uncertainties around the resource management. An integration of Climate Change and socio-economic developments into the WRM plans of the two basins are therefore required to develop more resilient Water Resources Management plans.

This project will create the knowledge base and capacity for integrating scenarios of Climate Change into Water Resource Management to enhance climate resilience, livelihood, water-food-energy security, and environmental conservation. In addition to contributing directly to the upcoming preparation of new Water Resources Management plans for the two basins, the project will develop tools and provide guidance to Water Resources Management at national and regional scale, such as implementing the Ghana Water and Climate Change Policies and Ghana Government's initiatives to restore degraded water bodies in the country. The output will also contribute directly to Ghana's achievement of the sustainable development goals, particularly goals 1 (no poverty), 6 (clean water and sanitation) and 13 (climate action); the 'greening of the economy' agenda of the Denmark-Ghana partnership policy; and Ghana's Nationally Determined Contribution to the Paris Agreement.

The CREAM Project will need your cooperation by creating awareness among your communities and get them to voluntarily grant interviews when the team visits. We shall communicate by telephone on the exact dates for the visit.

Counting on your cooperation

Project Coordinator
Dr. Emmanuel Obuobie

Appendix B: Semi Structured Interview Guides

Interview Guide for WRC and RBB (Basin Managers)

Presentation of interviewer and a short description of the purpose of the CREAM project.

The CREAM Project is being implemented in two river basins in Ghana, namely, the Pra (23,200 km², 6.2 million people) and Densu (2,600 km², 2.5 million people). The overall goal is to increase river basin resilience in two river basins in Ghana against Climate Change challenges to water infrastructure, livelihood, water-food-energy security, and environmental conservation.

NOTE: This interview will to be recorded to help with analysis on river basin resilience strategies and challenges in the two basins [the interviewee can see the transcript at any point in time]. We will not include any of your names in these analyses – names will be kept anonymous.

Q1. What do you see as the largest problem - if any - with Ghana's river basin policies today?

Q2. What is your organisation's commitment to policy implementation?

Support for the water policy implementation?

Q3. Constraints Limitations: (need funds to participate, lack of personnel, political or other barriers)

Q4. Opportunities to improve organisation's performance

Policy awareness and evaluation

Q5. Water policy instruments that have been implemented

-Command and control? (laws, rules, or standards established by government bodies like drinking water standards)

-Economic instruments? (taxes, water charges, subsidies, tradable permits, enforcement incentives, PES)

-Voluntary instruments/Information? (Public campaigns, environmental education, voluntary agreement)

Q6. How are they working to improve water quality?

Q7. How are they helping in avoiding water scarcity problems?

Q8. Reasons why policy instruments are not working (i.e. Organisational and interorganizational implementation behaviour, Management, Street level bureaucrats' skills, will and interests, target group behaviour)

Q9. Are all the inputs and resources required to implement the water policy available? (Financial resources, staff, political support.....)

Q10. What instrument(s) would work to improve water quality?

Q11. What instrument(s) would help in avoiding water scarcity?

Q12. Can PES instruments such as public payment schemes through which government pays land or resource managers to enhance ecosystem services on behalf of the wider public; • private payment schemes, self-organised private deals in which beneficiaries of ecosystem services contract directly with service providers; and • public-private payment schemes that draw on both government and private funds to pay land or other resource managers for the delivery of ecosystem services help solve the water quality and water scarcity problems?

Political economy analysis

Q13. In your view, what are the issues/problems confronting water resources management in the Pra and Densu river basins?

Q14. Are you aware of other actors (such as the WRC, EPA, NGOs....) and their roles in the process of addressing the issues.

Q15. How are decisions made regarding water resources management in the basin?

Q16. Who is party to these decision-making processes? Is the stakeholder part of the process?

Q17. Do the decisions cover the whole basin?

Q18. Once made, are decisions implemented?

Q19. Where are the key bottlenecks in the system?

Q20. How can these bottlenecks be overcome?

Q21. Do you think there is a relationship between climate change and water resources in the basin?

Q22. How does climate change affect the pursuit of your interests?

Q23. What plans are in place to respond to climate change to protect stakeholders' interests

Q24. Is climate change and future socio-development considered during decision-making on water resources management?

Q25. How do you act to ensure that you have a voice towards the decision-making? (what strategies do different stakeholders employ in the pursuit of their interests)

Q26. Whose interests are served with important decisions on water resources management in the basin?

Q27. What beliefs and values shape views around water resources?

Q28. To what extent do these serve to constrain change?

Participation

Q29. In your point of view, how important is stakeholders' collaboration and to what extent for good river basin management and policy implementation?

Q30. In recent participatory meetings on issues related to the Pra or Densu Basins, what was

the participation arrangement (place, time, participants).

Q31. Who were engaged in the meeting?

Q32. Who was leading the meeting?

Q33. How were the participants recruited? (Call, text, email)

Q34. Did stakeholders have any support material for the comprehension of the issues for consultation (reports, etc)? If yes, was that material adequate to their different levels of knowledge on the issues involved?

Q35. How actively were stakeholders involved at the meetings? (Hearing, group work, co-creation etc.)

Q36. Which groups of stakeholders were more collaborative in your opinion (if any)? Which stakeholders were conflicting (if any)?

Q37. Did stakeholder input help you in making better decisions?

Q38. Which tools were used when dealing with multiple stakeholders' interests?

Q39. How were conflicts among stakeholders solved (if at all)?

Q40. How frequent are the Basin Board meetings?

Q41. Do you bring together all stakeholder groups in the same consultation meeting? If so, do you get a high representativeness of all sectors? If not, what do you think can be done to engage them?

Q42. Do you experience that there are any stakeholder barriers for influencing decisions in these fora?

Q43. Do you think some stakeholders have more influence over water governance decisions?

Interview Guide for Governmental Organisations (national, regional, local)

Presentation of interviewer and a short description of the purpose of the CREAM project.

The CREAM Project is being implemented in two river basins in Ghana, namely, the Pra (23,200 km², 6.2 million people) and Densu (2,600 km², 2.5 million people). The overall goal is to increase river basin resilience in two river basins in Ghana against Climate Change challenges to water infrastructure, livelihood, water-food-energy security, and environmental conservation.

NOTE: This interview will to be recorded to help with analysis on river basin resilience strategies and challenges in the two basins [the interviewee can see the transcript at any point in time]. The interviews will also be used in writing up articles and reports. We will not include any of your names in these analyses – names will be kept anonymous.

Stakeholder analysis

Q1. Name of stakeholder organisation or group

national
regional or
local

Q2. Stakeholder description

Primary purpose
legal mandate
brief history
funding

Q3. Role of the interviewee in the organisation

Q4. What do you see as the largest problem - if any - in Ghana's river basin policies today?

Q5. How does your organisation support river basin management or water policy implementation?

Q6. What limits your support for policy implementation? *Limitations: (need funds to participate, lack of personnel, political or other barriers)*

Q7. What are the opportunities to improve the organisation's performance?

Policy awareness and evaluation

Q8. Do you know of any water policy instruments(measures) that have been implemented in the country?

-Command and control? (laws, rules, or standards established by government bodies like drinking water standards)

-Economic instruments? (taxes, water charges, subsidies, tradable permits, enforcement incentives, PES)

-Voluntary instruments/Information? (Public campaigns, environmental education, voluntary agreement)

Q9. Are they working to improve water quality? If yes, how?

Q10. Are they helping in avoiding water scarcity problems? If yes, how?

Q11. What are the reasons why policy instruments are not working (if this is the case) *Organisational and interorganizational implementation behaviour, Management, Street level bureaucrats' skills, will and interests, target group behaviour*

Q12. Are all inputs and resources are available *(financial resources, staff, political support.....)*

Q13. What instrument(s) would work to improve water quality?

Q14. What instrument(s) would help in avoiding water scarcity?

Q15. Can PES instruments such as

- **public payment schemes** through which government pays land or resource managers to enhance ecosystem services on behalf of the wider public;
- **private payment schemes**, self-organised private deals in which beneficiaries of ecosystem services contract directly with service providers; and
- **public-private payment schemes** that draw on both government and private funds to pay land or other resource managers for the delivery of ecosystem services help solve the water quality and water scarcity problems?

Q16. *Do you see any potential barriers for a system like this?*

Q17. What key activities have been completed by your organisation since implementation of the water policy?

Q18. What has been the effects of activities/interventions that have been implemented?

Q19. Are there some external factors influencing implementation of the water policy?

Political economy analysis

Q20. What is your interest in the Pra and Densu river basins?

Q21. What are the issues/problems confronting water resources management in the basin?

Q22. Are you aware of other actors (*such as the WRC, EPA, Basin board, NGOs....*) and their roles in the process of addressing the issues.

Q23. Who are the main stakeholders? Where do you see the largest conflicts?

Q24. How are decisions made regarding water resources management in the basin?

Q25. Who is party to these decision-making processes? Is the stakeholder part of the process?

Q26. Once made, are decisions implemented?

Q27. Where are the key bottlenecks in the system?

Q28. How can these bottlenecks be overcome?

Q29. Do you think there is a relationship between climate change and water resources in the basin?

Q30. How does climate change affect the pursuit of your interests?

Q31. Identify plans in place to respond to climate change to protect stakeholders' interests

Q32. Explore how climate change and future socio-development are considered during decision-making on water resources management?

Q33. How do you act to ensure that you have a voice towards the decision-making? (*what strategies do different stakeholders employ in the pursuit of their interests*)

Q34. Whose interests are served with important decisions on water resources management in the basin?

Participation

Q35. Could you please inform me about the size and aim of your organisation?

Q36. In your point of view, how important is stakeholders' collaboration and to what extent for good river basin management and policy implementation?

Q37. During the last five years, how many times have you been consulted by the WRC or the River Basin Board?

Q38. How were you consulted (oral, written, hearing, group work, co-creation etc)?

Q39. What were the consultations about? Could you describe the adequacy of the consultation?

Q40. How were you recruited for the consultation? (Call, text, email)

Q41. Did you express the concerns of the organisation or a section of the organisation?

Q42. Is it your experience that your input made a difference for the decisions taken?

Q43. How do you act to ensure that you have a voice towards the decision-making? Do you think that your representative' participation on the Basin Board is enough for it?

Q44. Have your urgent claims been attended to by the Basin Board?

Q45. Do you think that there are some issues from your organisation that are not yet fulfilled and which are urgent to fulfil? If the answer is yes, which are they? Are they for the whole organisation or for a section of the organisation?

Q46. What hinders your involvement in participatory processes on river basin management and water policy implementation if any?

Q47. In your point of view, what strategies should be implemented to enhance stakeholders and citizens' commitment and engagement in participatory processes for river basin management and water policy implementation?

Q48. How were conflicts – if any - solved (if at all)?

**Interview Guide for Non-governmental Organisations and companies
representing those suffering from pollution/water scarcity**

Presentation of interviewer and a short description of the purpose of the CREAM project.

The CREAM Project is being implemented in two river basins in Ghana, namely, the Pra (23,200 km², 6.2 million people) and Densu (2,600 km², 2.5 million people). The overall goal is to increase river basin resilience in two river basins in Ghana against Climate Change challenges to water infrastructure, livelihood, water-food-energy security, and environmental conservation.

NOTE: This interview will to be recorded to be included in our analyses on river basin resilience strategies and challenges in the two basins [the interviewee can see the transcript at any point in time]. The interviews will also be used in writing up articles and reports. We will not include any of your names in these analyses – names will be kept anonymous.

Stakeholder analysis

1. Name of stakeholder organisation or group
national
regional or
local
2. Stakeholder description
Primary purpose
legal mandate
brief history
funding
3. Role of the interviewee in the organisation
4. What do you see as the largest problem - if any - in Ghana's river basin policies today?
- Q5. How does your organisation support river basin management or water policy implementation?
- Q6. What limits your support for policy implementation? *Limitations: (need funds to participate, lack of personnel, political or other barriers)*
- Q7. What are the opportunities to improve the organisation's performance?

Policy awareness and evaluation

Q8. Do you know of any water policy instruments (measures) that have been implemented in the country?

-*Command and control? (laws, rules, or standards established by government bodies)*

-*Economic instruments? (taxes, subsidies, tradable permits, enforcement incentives, PES)*

-*Voluntary instruments/Information? (Public campaigns, environmental education, voluntary agreement)*

Q9. Are they working to improve water quality? If yes, how?

Q10. Are they helping in avoiding water scarcity problems? If yes, how?

Q11. Reasons why policy instruments are not working (if this is the case) *Organisational and interorganizational implementation behaviour, Management, Street level bureaucrats' skills, will and interests, target group behaviour*

Q12. Inputs and resources required to implement the water policy

Q13. Explore whether all inputs and resources are available (*financial resources, staff, political support.....*)

Q14. What instrument(s) would work to improve water quality?

Q15. What instrument(s) would help in avoiding water scarcity?

Q16. Can PES instruments such as

- **public payment schemes** through which government pays land or resource managers to enhance ecosystem services on behalf of the wider public;
- **private payment schemes**, self-organised private deals in which beneficiaries of ecosystem services contract directly with service providers; and
- **public-private payment schemes** that draw on both government and private funds to pay land or other resource managers for the delivery of ecosystem services help solve the water quality and water scarcity problems?

Q17. Do you see any potential barriers for a system like this?

Political economy analysis

Q18. What are the issues/problems confronting water resources management in the basin?

Q19. Explore stakeholder's awareness of other actors (*such as the WRC, EPA, Basin board....*) and their roles in the process of addressing the issues. Who are the main stakeholders? Where do you see the largest conflicts?

Q20. How are decisions made regarding water resources management in the basin?

Q21. Who is party to these decision-making processes? Is the stakeholder part of the process?

Q22. Once made, are decisions implemented?

Q23. Where are the key bottlenecks in the system?

Q24. How can these bottlenecks be overcome?

Q25. Explore stakeholder's awareness of the relationship between climate change and water resources in the basin

Q26. Identify how climate change affects the interests of stakeholders

Q27. Identify plans in place to respond to climate change to protect stakeholders' interests

Q28. Explore how climate change and future socio-development are considered during decision-making on water resources management?

Q29. How do you seek to influence policy? (*what strategies do different stakeholders employ in the pursuit of their interests*)

Q30. Whose interests are served with important decisions on water resources management in the basin?

Q31. What beliefs and values shape views around water resources?

Q32. To what extent do these serve to constrain change?

Participation

Q33. Could you please inform me about the size and aim of your organisation?

Q34. In your point of view, how important is stakeholders' collaboration and to what extent for good river basin management and policy implementation?

Q35. During the last five years, how many times have you been consulted by the WRC or the River Basin Board?

Q36 How were you consulted (oral, written, hearing, group work, co-creation etc)?

Q37. What were the consultations about? Could you describe the adequacy of the consultation?

Q38 How were you recruited for the consultation? (Call, text, email)

Q39. Did you express the concerns of the organisation or a section of the organisation?

Q40. Is it your experience that your input made a difference for the decisions taken?

Q41. How do you act to ensure that you have a voice towards the decision-making? Do you think that your representative' participation on the Basin Board is enough for it?

Q42. Have your urgent claims been attended to by the Basin Board?

Q43. Do you think that there are some issues from your organisation that are not yet fulfilled and which are urgent to fulfil? If the answer is yes, which are they? Are they for the whole organisation or for a section of the organisation?

Q44. What hinders your involvement in participatory processes on river basin management and water policy implementation if any?

Q45. In your point of view, what strategies should be implemented to enhance stakeholders and citizens' commitment and engagement in participatory processes for river basin management and water policy implementation?

Q46. How were conflicts – if any - solved (if at all)?

Interview Guide for Traditional Authority/Chief

Presentation of interviewer, a short description of the purpose of the CREAM project

The CREAM Project is being implemented in two river basins in Ghana, namely, the Pra (23,200 km², 6.2 million people) and Densu (2,600 km², 2.5 million people). The overall goal is to increase river basin resilience in two river basins in Ghana against Climate Change challenges to water infrastructure, livelihood, water-food-energy security, and environmental conservation.

NOTE: This interview will be recorded to be included in our analyses on river basin resilience strategies and challenges in the two basins [the interviewee can see the transcript at any point in time]. We will not include any of your names in these analyses – names will be kept anonymous.

Background Information about Community

- (i) Date of interview
- (ii) Name of community
- (iii) Name of District/Region

Beliefs

Q1. What role do the rivers play in the performance of their rituals or to what extent are the rivers important/useful to them in the roles they play in the communities as Fetish Priests?

Q2. Do they have any taboos that help to protect the rivers and what are they?

Q3. In what ways are the taboos undermined or adhered to and why?

Q4. How do they work with the Traditional Authority or the Chiefs to protect the rivers?

Q5. What steps do they take to ensure that the rivers are protected if they are useful to them in any way?

Q6. How do they work with other Chiefs along the same river body in upstream and downstream communities to protect the river body?

Political economy analysis

Q7. In your point of view, how important is stakeholders' collaboration and to what extent for good river basin management and policy implementation?

Q8. What are the issues/problems/conflicts confronting water resources management in the basin?

Q9. Do you know of stakeholders (*such as the WRC, EPA, Basin board, NGOs, traditional authority....*) who are working to address these issues? Do you know about stakeholders working against solutions of these problems?

Q10. Do you think the stakeholders in the basin are being effective at tackling the issues of water quality and water scarcity?

Q11. During the last five years, how many times have you been consulted by the WRC or the River Basin Board?

Q12. What were the consultations about?

Q13. How were you consulted? (written hearing, personal meeting etc)?

Q14. Could you describe the adequacy of the consultation?

Q15. Did you express the concerns of the whole community or the traditional council?

Q16. How do you act to ensure that you have a voice towards the decision-making? Do you think that your representative' participation on the Basin Board is enough for it?

Q17. How frequent are the Basin Board meetings?

Q18. Have your urgent claims been attended to by the Basin Board - Did your viewpoints make a difference to the decisions made in the basin?

Q19. Do you think that there are some issues from your community that are not yet fulfilled and which are urgent to fulfil? If Yes, what are they? Are they for the whole community or for the traditional council? Why have they not been fulfilled?

Q20. What hinders your involvement (if any) in participatory processes on river basin management and water policy implementation?

Q21. In your point of view, what strategies should be implemented to enhance stakeholders and citizens' commitment and engagement in participatory processes for river basin management and water policy implementation?

Q22. What are the taboos and practices involving water resources in your community?

Q23. Do you require water sources to be at a certain level to perform certain rituals?

Policy awareness and evaluation

Q24. Have you heard about the National Water Policy of Ghana?

Q25. Where did you learn about the water policy?

Q26. Do you know of the water policy instruments that have been implemented in the country to improve water quality and avoid water scarcity?

- *Regulatory instruments? (drinking water standards, effluent standards, specifications, for construction of boreholes)*

- *Economic instruments? (licensing of water uses (permits) for companies that construct boreholes, water tariffs, and charges, wastewater effluent discharge permits)*

- *Voluntary instruments/Information? (Public campaigns, environmental education, voluntary agreement)*

Q27. How are these instruments working to improve water quality (if at all)?

Q28. How are they helping in avoiding water scarcity problems?

Q29. What are the reasons why policy instruments are not working *Organisational and interorganizational implementation behaviour, Management, Street level bureaucrats' skills, will and interests, target group behaviour*

Q30. What instrument(s) would work to improve water quality?

Q31. What instrument(s) would help in avoiding water scarcity?

Q32. Can PES instruments such as **public payment schemes** through which government pays land or resource owners to enhance ecosystem services on behalf of the wider public;

• **private payment schemes**, self-organised private deals in which beneficiaries of ecosystem services contract directly with service providers; and

• **public-private payment schemes** that draw on both government and private funds to pay land or other resource managers for the delivery of ecosystem services help solve the water quality and water scarcity problems?

Q33. What is your general perception of a national water policy for Ghana?

Interview Guide for District MOFA Office

Presentation of interviewer and a short description of the purpose of the CREAM project.

The CREAM Project is being implemented in two river basins in Ghana, namely, the Pra (23,200 km², 6.2 million people) and Densu (2,600 km², 2.5 million people). The overall goal is to increase river basin resilience in two river basins in Ghana against Climate Change challenges to water infrastructure, livelihood, water-food-energy security, and environmental conservation.

NOTE: This interview will to be recorded to help with analysis on river basin resilience strategies and challenges in the two basins [the interviewee can see the transcript at any point in time]. The interviews will also be used in writing up articles and reports. We will not include any of your names in these analyses – names will be kept anonymous.

Stakeholder analysis

Q1. Name of stakeholder organisation or group

national

regional or

local

Q2. Stakeholder description

Primary purpose

legal mandate

brief history

funding

Q3. Role of the interviewee in the organisation

Q4. What do you see as the largest problem - if any - in Ghana's river basin policies today?

Q5. How does your organisation support river basin management or water policy implementation?

Q6. What limits your support for policy implementation? *Limitations: (need funds to participate, lack of personnel, political or other barriers)*

Q7. What are the opportunities to improve the organisation's performance?

Policy awareness and evaluation

Q8. Do you know of any water policy instruments(measures) that have been implemented in the country?

-Command and control? (laws, rules, or standards established by government bodies like drinking water standards)

-Economic instruments? (taxes, water charges, subsidies, tradable permits, enforcement incentives, PES)

-Voluntary instruments/Information? (Public campaigns, environmental education, voluntary agreement)

Q9. Are they working to improve water quality? If yes, how?

Q10. Are they helping in avoiding water scarcity problems? If yes, how?

Q11. What are the reasons why policy instruments are not working (if this is the case) *Organisational and interorganizational implementation behaviour, Management, Street level bureaucrats' skills, will and interests, target group behaviour*

Q12. Are all inputs and resources are available *(financial resources, staff, political support.....)*

Q14. What instrument(s) would work to improve water quality?

Q15. What instrument(s) would help in avoiding water scarcity?

Q16. Q16. Can PES instruments such as

- **public payment schemes** through which government pays land or resource managers to enhance ecosystem services on behalf of the wider public;
- **private payment schemes**, self-organised private deals in which beneficiaries of ecosystem services contract directly with service providers; and

- ***public-private payment schemes that draw on both government and private funds to pay land or other resource managers for the delivery of ecosystem services*** help solve the water quality and water scarcity problems?

Q17. *Do you see any potential barriers for a system like this?*

Q18. What key activities have been completed by your organisation since implementation of the water policy?

Q19. What has been the effects of activities/interventions that have been implemented?

Q20. Are there some external factors influencing implementation of the water policy?

Political economy analysis

Q21. What is your interest in the Pra and Densu river basins?

Q22. What are the issues/problems confronting water resources management in the basin?

Q23. Are you aware of other actors (*such as the WRC, EPA, Basin board, NGOs....*) and their roles in the process of addressing the issues.

Q24. Who are the main stakeholders? Where do you see the largest conflicts?

Q25. How are decisions made regarding water resources management in the basin?

Q26. Who is party to these decision-making processes? Is the stakeholder part of the process?

Q27. Once made, are decisions implemented?

Q28. Where are the key bottlenecks in the system?

Q29. How can these bottlenecks be overcome?

Q30. Do you think there is a relationship between climate change and water resources in the basin?

Q31. How does climate change affect the pursuit of your interests?

Q32. Identify plans in place to respond to climate change to protect stakeholders' interests

Q33. Explore how climate change and future socio-development are considered during decision-making on water resources management?

Q34. How do you act to ensure that you have a voice towards the decision-making? (*what strategies do different stakeholders employ in the pursuit of their interests*)

Q35. Whose interests are served with important decisions on water resources management in the basin?

Participation

Q36. In your point of view, how important is stakeholders' collaboration and to what extent for good river basin management and policy implementation?

Q37. During the last five years, how many times have you been consulted by the WRC or the River Basin Board?

Q38. What were the consultations about? Could you describe the adequacy of the consultation?

Q39. Did you express the concerns of the organisation or a section of the organisation?

Q40. How do you act to ensure that you have a voice towards the decision-making? Do you think that your representative' participation on the Basin Board is enough for it?

Q41. Have your urgent claims been attended to by the Basin Board?

Q42. Do you think that there are some issues from your organisation that are not yet fulfilled and which are urgent to fulfil? If the answer is yes, which are they? Are they for the whole organisation or for a section of the organisation?

Q43. What hinders your involvement in participatory processes on river basin management and water policy implementation if any?

Q44. In your point of view, what strategies should be implemented to enhance stakeholders and citizens' commitment and engagement in participatory processes for river basin management and water policy implementation?

Flood Recession Agriculture

Q1. Can you give us the locations of flood recession agriculture in the district?

Q2. In your view, what are the benefits of floods (if any) to fishing or farming?

Interview Guide for Community Focus Group Discussion

Presentation of interviewer, a short description of the purpose of the CREAM project and Introduction of members of members of the Focus Group

The CREAM Project is being implemented in two river basins in Ghana, namely, the Pra (23,200 km², 6.2 million people) and Densu (2,600 km², 2.5 million people). The overall goal is to increase river basin resilience in two river basins in Ghana against Climate Change challenges to water infrastructure, livelihood, water-food-energy security, and environmental conservation.

NOTE: This interview will be recorded to be included in our analyses on river basin resilience strategies and challenges in the two basins [the interviewee can see the transcript at any point in time]. We will not include any of your names in these analyses – names will be kept anonymous.

Please note that there are no right or wrong answers to focus group questions. We are interested in hearing the many varying viewpoints and would like for everyone in this group to contribute their thoughts. Out of respect, please refrain from interrupting others. However, feel free to be honest even when your responses counter those of other group members.

We will kindly ask you to respect the privacy of other focus group members by not disclosing any content discussed in the focus group.

Background Information about Community

- (i) Date of group interview
 - (ii) Name of community
 - (iii) Name of District/Region
 - (iv) Number of participants present (we should take down their names)
1. Each participant make a short introduction about herself/himself and give their SHORT interpretation of the currently largest problem – if any – in river basin management in the area

Policy awareness and evaluation

Q1. Have you heard about the National Water Policy of Ghana?

Q2. Where did you learn about the water policy?

Q3. Do you know of the water policy instruments that have been implemented in the country to improve water quality and avoid water scarcity?

- *Regulatory instruments? (drinking water standards, effluent standards, specifications, for construction of boreholes)*

- *Economic instruments? (licensing of water uses (permits) for companies that construct boreholes, water tariffs, and charges, wastewater effluent discharge permits)*

- *Voluntary instruments/Information? (Public campaigns, environmental education, voluntary agreement)*

Q4. Are these instruments working to improve water quality (if at all)?

Q5. Are they helping in avoiding water scarcity problems?

Q6. Reasons why policy instruments are not working *Organisational and interorganizational implementation behaviour, Management, Street level bureaucrats' skills, will and interests, target group behaviour*

Q7. What instrument(s) would in your opinion work to improve water quality?

Q8. What instrument(s) would in your opinion help in avoiding water scarcity?

Q9. Can PES instruments such as **public payment schemes** through which government pays land or resource owners to enhance ecosystem services on behalf of the wider public; • **private payment schemes**, self-organised private deals in which beneficiaries of ecosystem services contract directly with service providers; and • **public-private payment schemes** that draw on both government and private funds to pay land or other resource managers for the delivery of ecosystem services help solve the water quality and water scarcity problems?

Q10. Do you see any barriers for a system like this?

Q11. What is your general perception of the national water policy for Ghana?

Political economy analysis

Q12. In your point of view, how important is stakeholders' collaboration and to what extent for good river basin management issues and policy implementation?

Q13. Do you experience that stakeholder involvement facilitates better decisions?

Q14. What are the issues/problems confronting water resources management in the basin?

Q15. Do you know of stakeholders (*such as the WRC, EPA, Basin board, NGOs, traditional authority....*) who are working to address these issues? Do you know about stakeholders working against solutions of these problems?

Q16. Do you think the stakeholders in the basin are being effective at tackling the issues of water quality and water scarcity? Are there any stakeholders working against tackling these problems?

Q17. What key activities have been implemented in your community to help solve the water quality and water scarcity problems?

Q18. Which organisations were in charge of these activities/interventions?

Q19. What hinders citizens involvement in participatory processes on river basin management and water policy implementation?

Q20. What strategies should be implemented to enhance stakeholders and citizens' commitment and engagement in participatory processes on river basin management and water policy implementation?

Appendix C: Data Analysis with NVIVO 12

Densu Data (NVivo 12).nvp - NVivo 12 Pro

Name	Files	References	Created On	Created By	Modified On	Modified By
Addressing basin problems		14	07/06/2023 12:53 pm	VF	20/06/2023 11:52 am	VF
Adequacy of stakeholders engaged		0	07/06/2023 1:01 pm	VF	07/06/2023 1:22 pm	VF
Ateva Forest and Government		2	08/06/2023 11:48 am	VF	09/06/2023 2:42 pm	VF
Availability of resources		2	07/06/2023 12:54 pm	VF	23/06/2023 5:53 am	VF
Awareness of policy instruments and thei		5	07/06/2023 12:55 pm	VF	20/06/2023 10:42 am	VF
Barriers to addressing basin problems		5	08/06/2023 11:53 am	VF	19/06/2023 4:53 pm	VF
Behaviour of people and companies		5	07/06/2023 12:57 pm	VF	19/06/2023 4:41 pm	VF
Biggest environmental problem		13	07/06/2023 12:52 pm	VF	20/06/2023 2:52 pm	VF
Climate change and water resources		4	08/06/2023 1:28 pm	VF	20/06/2023 10:59 am	VF
Collaboration between stakeholders		4	08/06/2023 11:46 am	VF	20/06/2023 10:57 am	VF
Community engagement		0	07/06/2023 1:02 pm	VF	07/06/2023 1:24 pm	VF
Decision-making process		0	07/06/2023 12:33 pm	VF	07/06/2023 1:25 pm	VF
Ecological monitoring and field visits		0	07/06/2023 12:50 pm	VF	07/06/2023 1:25 pm	VF
Engagement of stakeholders by board		1	07/06/2023 12:48 pm	VF	09/06/2023 5:17 pm	VF
How stakeholders views are received and		1	07/06/2023 12:51 pm	VF	19/06/2023 4:31 pm	VF
Interests and motivation of stakeholders		5	07/06/2023 12:42 pm	VF	20/06/2023 11:09 am	VF
Involvement of stakeholders		0	07/06/2023 12:44 pm	VF	07/06/2023 1:27 pm	VF
Law enforcement		2	07/06/2023 12:56 pm	VF	20/06/2023 11:38 am	VF
Meeting attendance		1	07/06/2023 12:49 pm	VF	09/06/2023 5:13 pm	VF
Opportunities to solve problems		9	07/06/2023 12:58 pm	VF	20/06/2023 2:50 pm	VF
Perception of other implementation barri		5	07/06/2023 12:58 pm	VF	20/06/2023 2:58 pm	VF
Problem with National water policy		3	07/06/2023 3:42 pm	VF	20/06/2023 10:44 am	VF

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Densu Data (NVivo 12).nvp - NVivo 12 Pro

Name	Codes	References	Modified On	Modified By	Classification
ABUAKWA SOUTH MUNICIPAL ASSEMBLY		6	07/06/2023 12:20 pm	VF	
ADOAGYIR DISTRICT		7	07/06/2023 12:20 pm	VF	
CSIR_SIRCOOL		5	07/06/2023 12:20 pm	VF	
DENSU RIVER BASIN SECRETARIAT		17	09/06/2023 5:19 pm	VF	
INTERVIEW with Assembly Member		2	07/06/2023 12:20 pm	VF	
INTERVIEW WITH MUNICIPAL ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH DEPARTMENT		6	07/06/2023 12:20 pm	VF	
INTERVIEW_Fetish Priest		1	20/06/2023 3:09 pm	VF	
INTERVIEW_Ghana Water Kyebi		6	19/06/2023 3:25 pm	VF	
INTERVIEW_New Juaben North		7	07/06/2023 12:20 pm	VF	
INTERVIEW_New Juaben South		7	19/06/2023 4:24 pm	VF	
INTERVIEW_NGO 4H		6	07/06/2023 12:20 pm	VF	
Interview_NGO AROCHA		11	19/06/2023 5:05 pm	VF	
INTERVIEW_NSAWAM ADOAGYIRI		9	20/06/2023 10:59 am	VF	
INTERVIEW_ObaapayinKey Informant		2	07/06/2023 12:20 pm	VF	
MOFA		8	20/06/2023 11:47 am	VF	
MUNICIPAL ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH		0	07/06/2023 12:20 pm	VF	
Principal Dtsaster Control Officer_WEIJA GBABWE		7	13/06/2023 2:50 pm	VF	
WEIJA GBABWE MUNICIPAL ASSEMBLY		5	20/06/2023 3:03 pm	VF	

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